

TWINNED

By Stars

D1.1 ANALYSIS OF EXISTING COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL TOURISM IN THE ATLANTIC ORS AND MAPPING OF ACTORS IN THE QUADRUPLE HELIX

WPI STRENGTHENING AND SUSTAINABILITY OF COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL TOURISM IN THE ORS

TWINNEDBYSTARS

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND DIGITALIZATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES AND BUSINESSES IN ORS

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	07/08/2024	First draft sent to Teresa Gubern González Yen Elizabeth Lam González Matias Gonzalez Hernandez Beatrice Avagnina Silvia Pérez Patricia Solinis Camalich Sara Luzardo Rebeca Cejas Cabrera José Luis Guersi Sauret	Mohamed Cheikh Nicola Lombardi Ruiz Mónica Quesada Peña Elba Bueno Cabrera
0.7	22/08/2024	Second draft sent to all partners	Mohamed Cheikh Nicola Lombardi Ruiz Mónica Quesada Peña Elba Bueno Cabrera Patricia Solinis Camalich Sara Luzardo Rebeca Cejas Cabrera José Luis Guersi Sauret
1	29/08/2024	Final draft ready for submission	Mohamed Cheikh Nicola Lombardi Ruiz Mónica Quesada Peña Elba Bueno Cabrera Patricia Solinis Camalich Sara Luzardo Rebeca Cejas Cabrera José Luis Guersi Sauret
2	23/09/2024	Updated version as requested by the EC	Mónica Quesada Peña Rebeca Cejas Cabrera Marie-Claude Derné

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	TWINNEDbySTARS	
Project Title	UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND DIGITALIZATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES AND BUSINESSES IN ORS	
Type of action	EMFAF Project Grants	
Topic	EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR	
Project Start Date	01/10/2023	
Project Duration	36 months	
Work Package	WP1 – Strengthening and sustainability of cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the outermost regions	
Deliverable	D1.1 ANALYSIS OF EXISTING COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL TOURISM IN THE ATLANTIC ORS AND MAPPING OF ACTORS IN THE QUADRUPLE HELIX	
Due Date	31/08/2024	
Submission Date	23/09/2024	
Dissemination Level ¹	PU	
Deliverable Responsible	CMC	
Version	2	
Status	Final version for submission	
Author(s)	Mohamed Cheikh, Nicola Lombardi Ruiz, Mónica Quesada Peña, and Elba Bueno Cabrera	CMC
	Rebeca Cejas Cabrera, Sara Luzardo, Patricia Solinis Camalich, and José Luis Guersi Sauret	CETECIMA
Reviewer(s)	All partners	All partners

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Version History	1
Deliverable Information	2
List of figures	5
List of tables	6
Acronyms & Abbreviations	7
1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
2. INTRODUCTION	10
2.1 The project	11
2.2 The Consortium	12
2.3 The Work Package 1	13
2.4 The Quadruple Helix Approach (QH) vs The multi-actor approach	13
The Quadruple Helix approach	13
The multi-actor approach	14
3. ANALYSIS OF EXISTING COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL TOURISM IN THE ATLANTIC ORS.....	17
3.1 Alianza Marino-Marítima Macaronésica (A3M).....	17
Mission and objectives	18
Founding members and associated partners	18
Governance.....	19
Further steps	20
Collaboration between A3M and TWINNEDbySTARS.....	21
3.2 Red Náutica de Cooperación en la Macaronesia (NAUTICOM).....	21
Mission and objectives	21
Founding members and associated partners	22
Governance.....	22
Further steps	23
Collaboration between NAUTICOM and TWINNEDbySTARS	23
3.3 Analysis of other alliances, coalitions, conferences and consortia.....	24
Ocean Panel Initiative	24
Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR) Atlantic arc commission	26
European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC)	28

Red de Cruceros Costeros y Fluviales de los Destinos Náuticos Sostenibles de España (Red CCF)	31
SEAStarlight “Unidos por la mar, hermanados por las estrellas”	32
ATLAZUL “Impulso de la Alianza Litoral Atlántica para el Crecimiento Azul”	34
European Marine Board	36
Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster	40
Martinique Maritime Cluster	43
Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique	46
3.4 Analysis of synergies and opportunities for collaboration.....	49
Analysis of Synergies.....	50
Complementary collaborations	51
Roadmap to enhance the four partnerships analysed and benefits for TWINNEDbySTARS	53
4. MAPPING STAKEHOLDERS	55
4.1 Mapping methodology.....	56
4.2 Identification of Stakeholders	58
4.3 Data analysis	61
REFERENCES.....	70
ANNEX 1: Factsheets	72
ENTITY INFORMATION SHEET	72
INTERNATIONAL, EUROPE and NATIONAL.....	74
CANARY ISLANDS.....	92
MADEIRA	168
AZORES.....	204
MARTINIQUE	245

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Share of employment and GVA in the EU Coastal Tourism sector, 2021. Source: The EU blue economy report 2024	10
Figure 2. The QH approach adapted to the project. Source: CMC own production.	14
Figure 3. Nautical value chain where the colours and the design of the connections have been adapted to the TWINNEDbySTARS image. Source: Diagnosis of the Nautical sports and leisure sub-sector and its capacities. SMARTBLUE and NAUTICOM projects. CMC own elaboration. ..	15
Figure 4: Governance structure of the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M). Source: CMC own elaboration.	20
Figure 5: Territories belonging to the SEAStarlight network. Source: Sea Starlight website.	33
Figure 6: Responsibilities within the stakeholder identification process. Source: CMC own elaboration.	55
Figure 7: Infographic with data from the four regions. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.	62
Figure 8: Infographic with data on the Canary Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.	63
Figure 9: Infographic with data on the Martinique island. Source CETECIMA own elaboration. .	65
Figure 10: Infographic with data on the Azores Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.	66
Figure 11: Infographic with data on the Madeira Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration. .	68

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.....	12
Table 2: Founding members and associated partners of the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance. (A3M) Source: CMC own elaboration.....	18
Table 3: Founding members and associated partners of the Nautical Cooperation Network in Macaronesia (NAUTICOM). Source: CMC own elaboration.....	22
Table 4: Research institutions at European national level that are part of the European Marine Board. Source: website of the European Marine Board.....	36
Table 5: Entities that constitute the Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster, divided by activity. Source: website of the Guadeloupe maritime cluster.	40
Table 6: List of members of the Martinique Maritime Cluster. Source: website of the Martinique maritime cluster.....	44
Table 7: Entities that constitute the Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique, only those related to shipbuilding and nautical tourism are included. Source: website of the Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique.	46
Table 8.: Stakeholder groups description.....	57
Table 9.: Entities that are part of the industry category.	58
Table 10: Fact sheet template for the most relevant stakeholders.....	60

ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

A3M	Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance
AAA+G	Alentejo, Algarve, Andalucía and Galicia
ANEN	Asociación Nacional de Empresas Náuticas
ATLAZUL	ATLAZUL "Impulso de la Alianza Litoral Atlántica para el Crecimiento Azul"
AZ	Azores
BE	Belgium
CA	Canary Islands
CAP	European Common Agricultural Policy
CE	Consulta Europa
CMC	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias
CMM	Cluster Maritime Martinique
CPMR	Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions
CO	Project Coordinator
D	Deliverable
DG GROW	Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs
EC	European Commission
EMFAF	European Maritime Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund
ENMC	European Network of Maritime Clusters
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
FR	France
GA	Grant Agreement
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDRP	General Data Protection Regulation
GPAP	Global Plastic Action Partnership
GVA	Gross Value Added
IN	International
MAC	Madeira, Azores and Canarias
MAD	Madeira
MAR	Martinique

MARE	Directorate-General Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
MEPs	Members of the European Parliament
MUPA	Museo Paleontológico de Castilla-La Mancha
NACE	National Classification of Economic Activities
NAUTICOM	Nautical Cooperation Network in Macaronesia
OECD	The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development
ORs	Outermost Regions
PhD	Doctorate
PT	Portugal
QH	Quadruple Helix
R&D	Research and Development
R&D&I	Research and Development and Innovation
Red CCF	Red de Cruceros Costeros y Fluviales de los Destinos Náuticos Sostenibles de España
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEAStarlight	SEAStarlight “Unidos por la mar, hermanados por las estrellas”
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
VET	Vocational education and training
WP	Work Package

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

TWINNEDbySTARS aims at increasing the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Outermost regions while contributing to protect marine biodiversity, preserving the cultural heritage and develop marine astro-tourism, recalling ancient navigators as a sustainable destination for these remote territories, by strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building and co-creation for tourism products.

International alliances, coalitions, confederations and partnerships are essential for the development and sustainability of marine and coastal tourism because: (1) they allow for coordinated efforts to protect marine and coastal ecosystems, through international agreements, standards and regulations to be established for the preservation of natural habitats, ensuring that tourism development does not cause irreparable damage, (2) they facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices in the management of coastal and maritime tourism, as well as in the development of joint training programmes or public awareness programmes to address the problems of coastal and maritime tourism, (3) they facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices in the management of coastal and maritime tourism, (4) attract investment, financial resources from international bodies and even philanthropy, necessary for the development of a more sustainable tourism industry, (5) allow the creation of international tourism brands that highlight the offer of coastal and maritime destinations committed to sustainability, thus increasing their attractiveness in the global market, (6) the development of more resilient nautical destinations, which in islands such as the outermost regions is essential, (7) partnerships help align regional and national efforts with global commitments, especially those related to underwater life (SDG 14) and climate action (SDG 13), ensuring a coordinated and effective approach.

This document develops, after a brief introduction on coastal and maritime tourism, a summary of the project, the consortium and the stakeholder approach model, the analysis of the most relevant Atlantic cooperation networks and alliances in the field of the blue economy, and specifically those related to nautical tourism, highlighting the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M) and the Nautical Cooperation Network in Macaronesia (NAUTICOM) initiatives in which several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners are integrated, as well as two regional networks in the Caribbean, the Maritime Clusters of Martinique and Guadeloupe, which in the direct projection of an international alliance, can serve as relays in the Caribbean. Once the alliances or networks are detailed, we find an analysis of the synergies and opportunities for collaboration between the established networks. Likewise, this document contains the mapping of stakeholders, which outlines the methodology applied, the identification, an analysis of the data obtained and an annex with fact sheets of the most relevant entities for the project.

2. INTRODUCTION

In 2006, the European Commission launched the "European Destinations of Excellence" pilot project to support European tourism by highlighting the diversity and unique characteristics of European tourist destinations and promoting emerging destinations and activities with a focus on social, cultural, and environmental sustainability. In 2023 the European Commission decided to change the name and scope of the project to '[European Green Pioneer of Smart Tourism](#)', an initiative to reward smart and sustainable tourism practices in European cities.

Coastal and maritime tourism includes activities on the shoreline and marine environments, primarily for leisure and recreation, such as enjoying beaches, sailing, diving, coastal landscapes, and cultural offerings. EU coastal areas are top tourist destinations, making coastal and maritime tourism the largest sector in the EU Blue Economy in terms of GVA and employment. Over half of the EU's bed capacity is in coastal regions, generating significant national revenue, especially in Southern Europe. These regions also face high seasonality, with peak tourism in July and August.

Spain leads the coastal tourism sector in terms of employment contributing with 22% of jobs, followed by Greece with 19%, France with 13% and Italy with 9%. In terms of GVA, Spain leads with 23%, followed by France with 20%, and Italy with 11%.

Employment by Member State

Value Added by Member State

Figure 1. Share of employment and GVA in the EU Coastal Tourism sector, 2021. Source: The EU blue economy report 2024

In 2022, the European Commission's DG GROW launched the Transition Pathway for Tourism, detailing actions, targets, and conditions for achieving green and digital transitions and long-term resilience in the sector. This pathway calls for investments in circularity, improved data sharing practices, and skill development to ensure a qualified workforce.

The competitiveness of the EU tourism industry depends on its ability to become more sustainable. An October 2021 Eurobarometer survey showed that 82% of Europeans are willing to adopt more sustainable travel habits, such as consuming local products, reducing waste, traveling off-season, and choosing eco-friendly transport. Key interests when selecting

destinations include nature (41%) and culture (42%), with many willing to pay more to support local nature and communities.

Coastal and maritime tourism actors should develop sustainable tourism in line with the EU's new blue economy strategy and the mission to "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030." The outermost regions (ORs) of the EU are highly dependent on tourism, accounting for up to 35% of GDP, though they face seasonal fluctuations and limited air connections.

International alliances, coalitions, confederations and partnerships are essential for the development and sustainability of marine and coastal tourism because: (1) they allow for coordinated efforts to protect marine and coastal ecosystems, through international agreements, standards and regulations to be established for the preservation of natural habitats, ensuring that tourism development does not cause irreparable damage, (2) they facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices in the management of coastal and maritime tourism, as well as in the development of joint training programmes or public awareness programmes to address the problems of coastal and maritime tourism, (3) they facilitate the exchange of knowledge and best practices in the management of coastal and maritime tourism, (4) attract investment, financial resources from international bodies and even philanthropy, necessary for the development of a more sustainable tourism industry, (5) allow the creation of international tourism brands that highlight the offer of coastal and maritime destinations committed to sustainability, thus increasing their attractiveness in the global market, (6) the development of more resilient nautical destinations, which in islands such as the outermost regions is essential, (7) partnerships help align regional and national efforts with global commitments, especially those related to underwater life (SDG 14) and climate action (SDG 13), ensuring a coordinated and effective approach.

In addition to the aspects mentioned above, international partnerships play a binding role for the promotion and implementation of actions to increase the circularity and digitisation of the coastal and maritime tourism industry, through: (1) specific agreements and collaborations to develop integrated systems to reduce, reuse and recycle waste generated by tourism activity in marinas and offshore, (2) the design and testing of innovative nautical products and services that maximise reuse and minimise waste, (3) data management and integrated analysis through digital tools, and (4) the development of digital technologies adapted to territories such as the outermost regions, which improve the management and promotion of the nautical industry in these territories.

2.1 THE PROJECT

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to transform European outermost regions (ORs) into internationally recognized maritime ecotourism destinations that leverage tourism for marine biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. Building on the success of previous Macaronesian projects, the initiative involves co-designing and refining marine ecotourism products and activities with SMEs on various islands. Practices like on-board marine environmental education, respectful wildlife viewing, and unique interpretive experiences have led to high tourist satisfaction and more environmentally responsible behaviour from both SMEs and tourists. TWINNEDbySTARS seeks to expand these successes across EU ORs, promoting green and digital innovation, strengthening existing partnerships, and fostering co-creation.

The project draws on the results of previous initiatives, such as the NAUTICOM Interreg MAC project, which developed a week-long nautical experience for marine and pelagic bird watching across key natural reserves in Macaronesia, including Madeira, Desertas, Salvajes, the Chinijo Archipelago, and Lanzarote.

The project's success depends on tangible activities involving public and private entities representing the quadruple helix of the regions. Collaboration is based on established relationships from prior projects. The first half of the project focuses on analysis, mapping, stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and training definition. The second half will concentrate on training execution, marketing and commercialization plan implementation, and product testing.

2.2 THE CONSORTIUM

The TWINNEDbySTARS consortium has professionals with extensive experience in the nautical tourism sector, both in the applied and research fields, in business support through clusters and chambers of commerce, or in the regulation and promotion of activities of this type, such as in the public administration sector.

This project builds upon a university & a research centre, regional governments from ORs, a maritime cluster, SMEs and a chamber of commerce, a marina, and an EU-wide boating association.

Table 1. TWINNEDbySTARS consortium.

Partner No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC/TIDES	ES
1.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT/ULPGC	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Asociación Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
4	Océano de Experiencias SL	NAUTIC OCEAN	ES
5	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas	CETECIMA	ES
6	Associação MarinaFunchal	MARINA FUNCHAL	PT
7	Associação Comercial E Industrial Do Funchal	ACIF-CCIM	PT
8	Secretaria Regional do Mar e das Pescas	DRPM AZORES	PT
9	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique	CTM	FR
10	European Boating Industry	EBI	BE

2.3 THE WORK PACKAGE 1

The objectives of the WP1 are:

- Strengthening and sustainability of cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the ORs.
- Acting as a link between the quadruple helix representatives.
- Fostering the homogeneity of the network through the promotion of the certification (quality, tourism, environmental, Starlight...).
- Promoting the clustered participation in international fairs with the resulting product(s) within the "Trade Winds Starlight Adventure" and the promotion of a common brand image.

The tasks to be carried out to achieve these objectives are as follows:

T1.1. Analysis of existing cooperation networks in maritime and coastal tourism in the Atlantic ORs, mapping of actors in the quadruple helix and stakeholder engagement plan. Therefore, this report is included in this task.

T1.2. Homogenization and promotion of certification: enhancement of digitalization and circular economy.

T1.3. Elaboration and implementation of the internationalization and legacy plan.

2.4 THE QUADRUPLE HELIX APPROACH (QH) VS THE MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

There are two main methods for stakeholder engagement, the quadruple helix approach and the multi-stakeholder approach. Both methodologies are valuable for stakeholder engagement but differ in their approach and structure. The Quadruple Helix approach is more structured and focuses on collaboration between four key sectors (science, policy, industry, and society) to drive innovation and sustainable development. On the other hand, the multi-stakeholder methodology is more inclusive and flexible, allowing for the participation of a wide range of actors and adapting to diverse needs and contexts.

Although the stakeholder mapping is based on the involvement of stakeholders under a QH approach, given the similarities of the proposal with the multi-actor approach used mainly in agriculture, but also incipiently in projects linked to the EMFAF as well as in Cluster 6 of Horizon Europe, the project partners are taking into account the values brought by this approach in the development of the co-creation processes that are being developed in WP2 and WP3.

The two approaches are briefly described under the following sections.

The Quadruple Helix approach

The project targets the Quadruple Helix (QH) Model: science, policy, industry, and society, essential for long-term success. In the case of TWINNEDbySTARS, stakeholders include:

- **Citizens or Civil Society:** NGOs, trade unions, professional associations, sports associations, sailors, and customer associations.
- **Industry:** Companies, clusters, sectoral associations, business federations, investors, and the private sector.
- **Government:** Public institutions and administration.
- **Academia:** Universities, research centres, think tanks, and scientific organizations.

This "quadruple helix approach" ensures comprehensive stakeholder involvement.

Figure 2. The QH approach adapted to the project. Source: CMC own production.

In the project, co-creation is crucial for WP2 and WP3, transforming hierarchical processes into collaborative and horizontal ones. It applies to all stages, from capacity building to product definition and testing. By involving diverse people with different specializations and experiences, it generates innovative, interdisciplinary results that wouldn't be possible individually. This is the added value of co-creation using the quadruple helix approach.

The multi-actor approach

The multi-actor approach is a way of conducting R&D&I in a responsible manner that aims to make the R&D&I process and its results more reliable, demand-driven, shared, and relevant to

society. This involves more than just widely disseminating the results of a project or listening to the views of a committee of stakeholders.

The idea of this approach is to have **the whole value chain** of the products or services that are part of the project target represented, in the case of TWINNEDbySTARS we would be talking about the value chain of nautical activities which is included below in figure 3.

Figure 3. Nautical value chain where the colours and the design of the connections have been adapted to the TWINNEDbySTARS image. Source: Diagnosis of the Nautical sports and leisure sub-sector and its capacities. SMARTBLUE and NAUTICOM projects. CMC own elaboration.

This multi-actor approach has been effective in R&D&I projects related to the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and is also featured in the Horizon Europe Work Programme (2023-24), Cluster 6.9 on Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environment.

To ensure effective participation in multi-actor networks requires some processes that will give certain advantages to the initiatives, as outlined below:

- Effective engagement in multi-actor networks requires:
 - Openness and context awareness.
 - Face-to-face conversations.

- Time for informal interactions to build relationships.
- Field visits to facilitate communication and knowledge sharing.
- Advantages of the multi-actor approach include:
 - Access to extensive networks.
 - Introduction to other projects.
 - Engagement with a broad range of stakeholders.
 - Opportunities for external funding.
 - Support and new knowledge from partners.

3. ANALYSIS OF EXISTING COOPERATION NETWORKS IN MARITIME AND COASTAL TOURISM IN THE ATLANTIC ORS

TWINNEDbySTARS has a variety of partners who have worked together in previous proposals and many of them are already integrated in networks beyond the project such as the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M) and the NAUTICOM Network, integrating in this initiative new actors from other territories that broaden the range of action and give sustainability to these strategic alliances and networks.

This section analyses the most relevant Atlantic cooperation networks and alliances in the field of the blue economy, and specifically those related to nautical tourism, highlighting among them the **A3M "Macaronesian Maritime-Maritime Alliance"** and **NAUTICOM "Macaronesia Nautical Cooperation Network"** initiatives in which several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners are integrated. Other international, national and regional alliances analysed with influence on in the Atlantic area are: (1) Ocean Panel Initiative, (2) Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions – Atlantic arc commission (CPMR), (3) European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC), (4) Coastal and River Cruise Network of Sustainable Nautical Destinations of Spain (Red CCF), (5) SEAStarlight "United by the sea, twinned by the stars", (6) ATLAZUL "Promotion of the Atlantic Coastal Alliance for Blue Growth", (7) European Marine Board, (8) Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique and, two regional networks in the Caribbean, (9) the Maritime Cluster of Martinique and (10) the Maritime Cluster of Guadeloupe.

3.1 ALIANZA MARINO-MARÍTIMA MACARONÉSICA (A3M)

Among the many actions developed under the Macaronesian Research Strategy (MARES) project, 85% funded by the European Commission through the Interreg MAC Operational Programme 2007-2013, the Management Committee of the Macaronesian Maritime-Maritime Cluster was set up in 2013. The constitution agreement was signed in Funchal and was signed by several entities from Madeira, the Azores and the Canary Islands.

The project "Network of regional marine-maritime clusters for the competitiveness of SMEs in the blue economy" SMARTBLUE started in November 2016. Its main objective was to boost the competitiveness of blue economy companies through innovation and internationalisation processes. Its first specific objective was to strengthen regional cooperation with the creation of a network of marine-maritime clusters. The project was implemented, and the consortium was composed of 11 partners, 85% financed by ERDF funds through the Interreg MAC Programme 2014-2020.

Promoted by the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster through the SMARTBLUE Project, several public institutions, research centres and business associations from Madeira, Azores and Canary Islands signed the official constitution of the Alliance at the end of 2018 with the vision of promoting socio-economic activity, sustainable development and growth based on scientific-technical knowledge in the marine-maritime field through active cooperation at regional, national and international level.

Mission and objectives

The mission of the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M) is to foster socio-economic activity, sustainable investment and growth based on scientific and technical knowledge in the marine-maritime field. Active collaboration at regional, national and international levels aims to benefit all parties involved. The signatories committed to work together to identify areas of collaboration, share information and participate in research, technological development and innovation (R&D&I) initiatives, as well as to seek joint business development opportunities.

The objectives of the Alliance are:

- Promote new and existing relationships between the parties to enable companies operating in the marine-maritime field to access new market opportunities and combine the necessary expertise to enter these markets.
- Build new international consortia to address technology gaps where the need exists and facilitate access to funding opportunities.
- Maximise asset utilisation (and avoid duplication) by creating and maintaining an up-to-date asset inventory to identify available marine-maritime R&D&I facilities in the MAC area.
- Provide a commercialisation channel for universities and research institutes to help transfer knowledge to marine-maritime companies.
- Articulate the growing international demand for skills and job opportunities in the Blue Economy, to motivate "Blue Career" options for the workforce of the future.
- Collect experiences, data and promotional materials to maintain a strong and solid "blue" strategy and to carry out communication actions targeting opinion makers, funding agencies and policy makers at regional, national and international level.

Founding members and associated partners

Membership includes founding and regular members, with the possibility of inviting organisations such as non-profit organisations and government agencies, among others, as associate members. The table below lists the current partners of the A3M alliance:

Table 2: Founding members and associated partners of the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance. (A3M)
Source: CMC own elaboration

Entity name	Entity name
Founding Members	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias (CMC)
	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas (CETECIMA)
	Plantaforma Oceánica de Canarias (PLOCAN)
	Câmara de Comércio do Norte de Cabo Verde / Câmara de Comércio de Barlavento (CCB)
	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)

Entity name	Entity name
	Câmara do Comércio e Industria dos Açores (CCIA)
	Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação Tecnologia e Inovação da Madeira (ARDITI)
	Associação Comercial e Industrial do Funchal – Câmara de Comércio e Industria da Madeira (ACIF-CCIM)
Regular Members	Câmara do Comércio e Indústria de Angra do Heroísmo
	Câmara do Comércio e Indústria de Ponta Delgada
	Direção Regional de Políticas Marítimas
	Sociedad Canaria de Fomento Económico (PROEXCA)
Associate Members	ASNAUTICA
	AENAUTICA
	RODRITOL
	Associação Operadores Marítimos dos Açores (AOMA)
	Federación Provincial de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa del Metal y Nuevas Tecnologías de Las Palmas (FEMEPA)
	Asociación de Empresas de Energías Renovables de Las Palmas (ASERPA)
	Asociación Industrial de Canarias (ASINCA)
	Federación Canaria de Empresas Portuarias (FEDEPORT)
	Cámara de Comercio de Gran Canaria
	Confederación Canaria de Empresarios
	Consejo Económico y Social de Canarias
	Autoridad Portuaria de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)
	Astilleros Canarios (ASTICAN)

Governance

The Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance seeks the participation of regional clusters and business associations active in maritime sectors, as well as related government agencies. Membership includes founding and regular members, with the possibility of inviting organisations such as non-profit entities and government agencies, among others as associate members. A Steering Committee, consisting of representatives from the four Macaronesian regions, will make decisions by majority vote. Financial activities will be decided by unanimous vote, and the parties recognise the possibility of introducing subscription fees. Intellectual property developed will be

subject to applicable funding terms and contracts. It is agreed that the information provided will be kept confidential, and the MoU does not create a legal relationship between the parties, being a statement of will and intent without legal enforceability.

Below is the structure that governs under the governance code and operating model that was approved by the members of the alliance at the 1st general assembly that took place in May 2022.

Figure 4: Governance structure of the Macaronesian Marine-Maritime Alliance (A3M). Source: CMC own elaboration.

Further steps

The support to this alliance has been recently endorsed with the approval, by the Interreg MAC programme (85% financed by ERDF funds through the Interreg MAC Programme 2021-2027), of the **A3MAtlantic project** "Strengthening the sustainable growth and competitiveness of SMEs that make up the productive ecosystem of the Blue Economy sectors in the Mid-Atlantic", which has the general objective of Promoting innovation and internationalisation of SMEs in the Mid-Atlantic regions with blue economy activity, through pilot actions and joint solutions promoted by the quadruple helix, which make up the A3M Alliance, raising this initiative as a tool in Europe to make blue policies permeable at regional level and has partners from the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores, Cape Verde, Côte d'Ivoire and Ghana.

Collaboration between A3M and TWINNEDbySTARS

The A3M alliance is a solid alliance and is on a path of development and expansion in the Atlantic, thanks to the conviction of its members in its maintenance and usability. TWINNEDbySTARS is currently working with stakeholders from several of the regions involved in A3M (Canary Islands, Madeira and Azores), in co-creation actions, training, increasing competitiveness through the adoption of good practices to become more circular and digital, and in the implementation of a new coastal and maritime tourism product that, beyond this initiative, could be supported by A3M members through (1) dissemination actions for the general public, (2) technical support through the inclusion of TWINNEDbySTARS within one of the A3M thematic groups, (3) inclusion of this initiative as an example of good practice in one of the Policy briefs, as well as (4) inclusion of the product resulting from TWINNEDbySTARS in the A3M internationalisation plan, to be launched in the next five years.

3.2 RED NÁUTICA DE COOPERACIÓN EN LA MACARONESIA (NAUTICOM)

The NAUTICOM Network proposes a series of activities to build capacities and stimulate internationalisation in these companies, to implement a business support plan to consolidate a joint image of the region for the international market, and for the design and development of new transnational thematic products, and to promote the introduction of ICTs, energy efficiency, and improved environmental management in their activities.

This network arises from the NAUTICOM project "Nautical Cooperation Network in Macaronesia, promoting internationalisation, tourism competitiveness and Blue Growth of the MAC Macroregion" (MAC/2.3d/158), approved by the Interreg-MAC Programme 2014 - 2020 in its first call for proposals and co-financed 85% by ERDF funds.

Mission and objectives

The mission and objectives of the NAUTICOM network are:

- a) To increase research, promotion and analysis of actions aimed at creating conditions for the internationalisation of companies in the MAC macro-region;
- b) Encourage the exchange of experience and professional training in these matters;
- c) Promote the competitiveness of sports marinas and nautical companies in the MAC Macroregion, through the generation of opportunities, incentives and capacities for their internationalisation, smart specialisation and eco-innovation;
- d) Encourage collaboration with other entities with common or complementary interests, choosing entities linked to the business sector;
- e) To disseminate the collaboration of the application of good environmental management of this activity.

Founding members and associated partners

Membership includes founding members, with the possibility of inviting organisations such as enterprises, non-profit organisations and government agencies, among others, as associate members. The table below lists the current partners of the NAUTICOM network:

Table 3: Founding members and associated partners of the Nautical Cooperation Network in Macaronesia (NAUTICOM). Source: CMC own elaboration.

Entity name	Entity name
Founding Members	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas (CETECIMA)
	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias (CMC)
	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)
	Fundación Puertos de Las Palmas
	Instituto Tecnológico de Canarias (ITC)
	Clube Naval do Funchal
	Portos dos Açores
	Gran Canaria Blue
	ENAPOR
	Sport Fishing Clube do Mindelo
	COCV – Comité Olímpico Cabo-Verdiano
	Fédération Mauritanienne de Tourisme
	Direcção Geral dos Desportos do Cabo Verde
Associate Members	Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias
	Patronato de Turismo De Fuerteventura
	Asociación Marina de Funchal
	Colegio Oficial de Profesionales en Turismo de Canarias
	Marina de Mindelo

Governance

The operational framework of the network includes that:

- a) The entities involved shall collaborate in accordance with the principles of good faith, ethics and mutual trust.

- b) Taking into account the established objectives, the entities involved will develop cooperative efforts for the joint use of the equipment, means and data available to ensure the correct execution of the agreed objectives.
- c) Without prejudice to the previous point, each of the partners may use data and results from its own means and equipment for its specific objectives.
- d) All specific aspects of the programmes and actions to be undertaken between partners will be further developed by means of individual agreements which will be progressively incorporated into this Protocol as an addendum.
- e) Aspects related to the use and exploration of common data and results shall respect the rules of ownership and shall be framed within the programmes and actions foreseen in the previous point.
- f) Taking into account the objectives promoted, the entities involved shall develop joint cooperation efforts in the search for sources of financing.
- g) In the execution and development of this Protocol, all effective collaborators of both parties or those contracted by them may participate, as well as trainees, scholarship holders and interns who, during the term of this Protocol, are carrying out activities in the granting entities.

Further steps

The support to this network has been recently endorsed with the approval, by the Interreg MAC programme (85% financed by ERDF funds through the Interreg MAC Programme 2021-2027), of the **INNOVABLUE project** "Digital and sustainable growth of blue tourism in the Atlantic territories" which has the general objective of positioning the different Atlantic Regions as recognised and intelligent nautical destinations, through innovation, digital and green transition of the sector, reinforcing the competitiveness of the companies, as well as strengthening the competences of the blue tourism sector and has partners from the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores, Cape Verde, Senegal, Sao tome and Prince, and Ghana.

Collaboration between NAUTICOM and TWINNEDbySTARS

The NAUTICOM network is a partnership of actors with specific interests in the development of blue tourism (all those related to the sea), represents several of the regions that are part of TWINNEDbySTARS (Canary Islands, Madeira and Azores), and is currently working on extending this network to several countries in Atlantic Africa. The product and stakeholders participating in TWINNEDbySTARS will benefit from NAUTICOM in actions linked to the positioning of the different Atlantic regions as recognised and intelligent nautical destinations, through (1) the implementation of best practices and existing solutions for the management of end-of-life vessels, (2) the implementation of innovative pilot actions and standardisation of services, and their evaluation, (3) business training actions and (4) including the product resulting from TWINNEDbySTARS in the framework of actions, criteria and sustainability keys for the NAUTICOM network, to be implemented in the next five years.

3.3 ANALYSIS OF OTHER ALLIANCES, COALITIONS, CONFERENCES AND CONSORTIA

Other international, national and regional alliances analysed with influence on in the Atlantic area are: (1) Ocean Panel Initiative, (2) Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions – Atlantic arc commission (CPMR), (3) European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC), (4) Coastal and River Cruise Network of Sustainable Nautical Destinations of Spain (Red CCF), (5) SEAStarlight "United by the sea, twinned by the stars", (6) ATLAZUL "Promotion of the Atlantic Coastal Alliance for Blue Growth", (7) European Marine Board, (8) Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique and, two regional networks in the Caribbean, (9) the Maritime Cluster of Martinique and (10) the Maritime Cluster of Guadeloupe.

The selection of these alliances or consortia has been mainly linked to their range of action, in the Atlantic Ocean, as well as to their interests and objectives, which have to be linked to the sustainable development of the Blue Economy with particular actions for the development of coastal and maritime tourism.

Ocean Panel Initiative

a. Introduction and Objectives

The [Ocean Panel Initiative](#), formally known as the High-Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy, is a significant global effort to promote sustainable ocean management and conservation. Established in 2018, the initiative brings together world leaders, scientists, and policymakers to address the urgent issues facing our oceans today. Oceans play a critical role in regulating the global climate, supporting biodiversity, and providing economic sustenance, making this initiative highly relevant in contemporary environmental policy, which is essential for the development of new transnational tourism products in a sustainable way, as is the case with TWINNEDbySTARS.

The primary objective of the Ocean Panel is to foster a sustainable ocean economy where effective protection, sustainable production, and equitable prosperity are interconnected. This vision emphasizes that economic growth should not come at the expense of the health of ocean ecosystems. Specific goals include enhancing sustainable fisheries and aquaculture, reducing marine pollution, addressing the impacts of climate change on ocean health, protecting marine biodiversity, and promoting sustainable tourism and renewable energy. By setting these objectives, the Ocean Panel aims to ensure long-term benefits for both the environment and human societies.

b. Membership and Structure

The Ocean Panel comprises 18 member countries, representing a diverse array of geographical regions and economic development levels. The member countries are Australia, Canada, Chile, Fiji, France, Ghana, Indonesia, Jamaica, Japan, Kenya, Mexico, Namibia, Norway, Palau, Portugal, Seychelles, United Kingdom and United States of America. Each member country is represented

by its head of state or government, indicating a high level of commitment to achieving sustainable ocean management.

The organizational structure of the Ocean Panel includes a secretariat, a group of scientific experts, and a network of partners from various sectors. This multi-stakeholder approach ensures that a wide range of perspectives and expertise are integrated into policy recommendations and initiatives. The leadership provided by heads of state and government facilitates the alignment of national policies with the global objectives of the Ocean Panel, enhancing the initiative's effectiveness and impact.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Sustainable Ocean Economy and Marine Conservation

Promoting a sustainable ocean economy involves fostering economic activities that do not compromise the health of ocean ecosystems. This includes responsible fisheries management, sustainable aquaculture practices, and the development of marine-based renewable energy sources. Marine conservation efforts are also crucial for protecting critical habitats, conserving endangered species, and promoting biodiversity through marine protected areas and other conservation initiatives.

One notable initiative is the commitment of each member country to develop comprehensive sustainable ocean plans by 2025. These plans integrate economic, social, and environmental goals, ensuring a holistic approach to ocean management. Success stories such as Norway's leadership in sustainable fisheries and Portugal's advancements in marine renewable energy highlight the potential for significant positive change driven by the Ocean Panel.

Climate Change, Pollution Control, and Key Initiatives

Addressing the impacts of climate change on ocean environments is a major focus of the Ocean Panel. This includes understanding and mitigating phenomena such as rising sea levels, ocean acidification, and shifts in marine biodiversity. Efforts are directed towards enhancing resilience and adaptation strategies, ensuring that marine ecosystems can withstand and recover from climate-induced changes.

Marine pollution, particularly plastic waste, poses a significant threat to ocean health. The Ocean Panel advocates for policy measures, waste management innovations, and international cooperation to tackle this issue. The Global Plastic Action Partnership (GPAP) is a key initiative aimed at reducing plastic waste in marine environments through innovative solutions and collaboration with businesses and governments.

The Blue Carbon Initiative is another critical program focusing on preserving and restoring coastal and marine ecosystems that sequester carbon, such as mangroves, seagrasses, and salt marshes. These ecosystems play a vital role in mitigating climate change by capturing and storing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere.

d. Challenges and Criticisms

Major Challenges and Criticisms

Despite its successes, the Ocean Panel faces several challenges that must be addressed to achieve its ambitious goals. Coordinating actions among diverse member countries with different priorities and capacities can be difficult. Securing adequate financial resources for large-scale projects and initiatives is another persistent issue. There is also a call for greater inclusion of local communities and indigenous knowledge in decision-making processes.

In conclusion, the Ocean Panel Initiative represents a pivotal effort in the global movement towards sustainable ocean management. By bringing together high-level political leaders, scientists, and stakeholders, it has set a robust framework for balancing economic growth with environmental stewardship. While challenges remain, the Ocean Panel's work has already yielded significant progress and holds great promise for the future. International cooperation and continued commitment to sustainable practices are essential for the health of our oceans and the well-being of our planet.

The Ocean Panel's success will depend on the sustained commitment of its members, innovative solutions, and the engagement of the broader international community. Through collective action and a shared vision, the initiative aims to ensure that the oceans continue to provide essential services and benefits for current and future generations.

[Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions \(CPMR\) Atlantic arc commission](#)

a. Introduction and Objectives

The [Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions \(CPMR\) Atlantic Arc Commission](#) is a significant European initiative aimed at fostering cooperation among the regions of the Atlantic Arc to promote sustainable development, economic growth, and environmental protection. Established in 1989, the Atlantic Arc Commission is one of six geographical commissions within the CPMR, focusing on the specific challenges and opportunities of the Atlantic coastal regions.

The primary objective of the Atlantic Arc Commission is to enhance the socio-economic development of its member regions while ensuring the sustainable management of marine and coastal resources. This includes promoting blue growth, supporting the transition to a low-carbon economy, improving connectivity and transport, and protecting marine biodiversity. By addressing these objectives, the Atlantic Arc Commission aims to create a balanced and sustainable approach to regional development that benefits both the environment and the local communities.

b. Membership and Structure

The Atlantic Arc Commission comprises various regions from five countries: France, Ireland, Portugal, Spain, and the United Kingdom. These regions are represented by their local and regional governments, which work together to address common challenges and leverage shared

opportunities. The commission facilitates cooperation and dialogue among its members, fostering a collaborative approach to regional development.

The organizational structure of the Atlantic Arc Commission includes a General Assembly, an Executive Committee, and several working groups focused on specific thematic areas. The General Assembly, which meets annually, sets the strategic direction and priorities of the commission. The Executive Committee, composed of representatives from member regions, oversees the implementation of the commission's work program and ensures that the decisions of the General Assembly are carried out effectively. The working groups bring together experts and stakeholders to address specific issues such as maritime transport, energy, and environmental protection.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Economic Development and Marine Conservation

The Atlantic Arc Commission places a strong emphasis on promoting sustainable economic development in its member regions. This includes fostering blue growth, which involves the sustainable use of marine resources to drive economic growth, create jobs, and support innovation. Key sectors targeted by the commission include fisheries and aquaculture, maritime tourism, marine renewable energy, and marine biotechnology.

Marine conservation is also a critical focus area for the Atlantic Arc Commission. The commission works to protect marine biodiversity and ensure the sustainable management of marine and coastal ecosystems. This includes supporting the establishment and management of marine protected areas, promoting sustainable fishing practices, and addressing marine pollution. By balancing economic development with environmental protection, the commission aims to create a sustainable and resilient blue economy in the Atlantic regions.

Climate Change, Sustainable Transport, and Key Initiatives

Addressing the impacts of climate change is a major priority for the Atlantic Arc Commission: the commission supports initiatives to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, enhance climate resilience, and promote the transition to a low-carbon economy. This includes promoting renewable energy sources, such as offshore wind and tidal energy, and supporting energy efficiency measures in maritime and coastal activities.

Sustainable transport is another key focus area for the Atlantic Arc Commission: the commission works to improve connectivity and accessibility in the Atlantic regions by promoting sustainable and efficient transport systems. This includes enhancing maritime transport, developing multimodal transport networks, and supporting the integration of transport infrastructure with environmental and social sustainability goals.

The Atlantic Arc Commission has launched several key initiatives to achieve its objectives. For example, the Atlantic Strategy, adopted in 2013, provides a framework for cooperation and coordination among the Atlantic regions to promote sustainable growth and job creation. The strategy focuses on key areas such as innovation, sustainability, and connectivity, and includes a range of projects and actions to support its implementation.

d. Challenges and Criticisms

Major Challenges and Criticisms

Despite its successes, the Atlantic Arc Commission faces several challenges that must be addressed to achieve its goals. One major challenge is ensuring effective coordination and cooperation among diverse member regions with different priorities and capacities. Securing adequate funding and resources for large-scale projects and initiatives is another persistent issue.

The Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR) Atlantic Arc Commission represents a pivotal effort in promoting sustainable development and regional cooperation in the Atlantic regions. By bringing together local and regional governments, experts, and stakeholders, it has set a robust framework for balancing economic growth with environmental stewardship and social well-being. While challenges remain, the Atlantic Arc Commission's work has already yielded significant progress and holds great promise for the future. Continued international cooperation and commitment to sustainable practices are essential for the health and prosperity of the Atlantic regions and their communities.

The Atlantic Arc Commission's success will depend on the sustained commitment of its members, innovative solutions, and the engagement of the broader regional and international community. Through collective action and a shared vision, the initiative aims to ensure that the Atlantic regions continue to thrive, providing essential services and benefits for current and future generations.

European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC)

a. Introduction and Objectives

The [European Network of Maritime Clusters \(ENMC\)](#) is a pivotal organization established to foster collaboration and innovation across the maritime sector in Europe. Launched in 2005, the ENMC aims to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the maritime industry by promoting cooperation among national maritime clusters. These clusters consist of companies, research institutions, and other stakeholders involved in various maritime activities such as shipping, shipbuilding, marine equipment, offshore energy, and marine research.

The primary objective of the ENMC is to strengthen the maritime industry in Europe by facilitating knowledge exchange, innovation, and joint initiatives. The network seeks to address common challenges, capitalize on shared opportunities, and influence maritime policy at the European level. By aligning the efforts of its members, the ENMC aims to ensure sustainable economic growth and competitiveness in the global maritime market.

b. Membership and Structure

The ENMC comprises maritime clusters from several European countries, including Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Each national cluster brings together a diverse group of stakeholders from industry, academia, and government, fostering a collaborative approach to maritime innovation and development.

The organizational structure of the ENMC includes a General Assembly, an Executive Committee, and various working groups. The General Assembly, composed of representatives from each member cluster, meets annually to set the strategic direction and priorities of the network. The Executive Committee oversees the implementation of the network's work program and ensures effective coordination among members. Working groups focus on specific thematic areas such as maritime policy, innovation, and sustainability, bringing together experts to address common challenges and develop joint initiatives.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Economic Development and Innovation

One of the core focus areas of the ENMC is promoting economic development and innovation within the maritime sector. The network facilitates the exchange of best practices and the development of joint projects that enhance the competitiveness of European maritime industries. Key initiatives include collaborative research and development (R&D) projects, technology transfer, and support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the maritime sector.

The ENMC also plays a critical role in fostering innovation through its involvement in various European research programs and projects. By leveraging the expertise and resources of its members, the network aims to drive technological advancements in areas such as digitalization, automation, and sustainable maritime technologies. These efforts are essential for maintaining the global competitiveness of the European maritime industry and ensuring its long-term sustainability.

Maritime Sustainability and Key Initiatives

Sustainability is another major focus area for the ENMC. The network promotes sustainable practices across the maritime industry, addressing issues such as environmental protection, climate change mitigation, and resource efficiency. Key initiatives include promoting the use of green technologies, reducing emissions from maritime activities, and enhancing the sustainability of maritime transport and logistics.

The ENMC actively participates in European policy discussions and advocacy efforts to shape regulations and standards that support sustainable maritime practices. By influencing policy at the European level, the network aims to create a favorable regulatory environment for the adoption of sustainable technologies and practices in the maritime sector.

Notable initiatives led by the ENMC include the development of sustainable shipping practices, the promotion of energy-efficient ship designs, and the implementation of green port strategies. These initiatives demonstrate the network's commitment to reducing the environmental impact of maritime activities and promoting a sustainable blue economy.

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

Major Challenges and Criticisms

Despite its successes, the ENMC faces several challenges. One of the primary challenges is ensuring effective coordination and collaboration among a diverse group of member clusters with varying priorities and capacities. Additionally, securing adequate funding for joint projects and initiatives is a persistent issue.

The vision of the ENMC is to create a resilient and competitive maritime industry in Europe that is capable of leading global efforts in innovation and sustainability. Achieving this vision requires continued commitment from member clusters, effective collaboration, and proactive engagement with policymakers and stakeholders.

Future Directions and Long-Term Vision

Looking ahead, the ENMC aims to strengthen its role as a key player in promoting innovation, sustainability, and competitiveness in the European maritime sector. Planned future initiatives include:

- Enhanced Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing: The ENMC plans to enhance collaboration among its members by developing new platforms for knowledge exchange and joint R&D projects. This includes creating virtual hubs and digital networks to facilitate real-time collaboration and information sharing.
- Focus on Digitalization and Smart Technologies: The network aims to drive the adoption of digital technologies and smart solutions in the maritime sector. This includes promoting the use of big data, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to improve operational efficiency, safety, and sustainability in maritime activities.
- Strengthened Policy Advocacy: The ENMC intends to strengthen its advocacy efforts at the European level to influence policy and regulatory frameworks that support the maritime industry's growth and sustainability. This includes engaging with policymakers, industry stakeholders, and international organizations to shape policies that promote innovation and environmental protection.
- Development of Sustainable Maritime Strategies: The network will continue to develop and implement strategies that promote sustainable maritime practices. This includes initiatives aimed at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, protecting marine biodiversity, and promoting circular economy principles in the maritime industry.

In conclusion, the European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC) represents a vital effort to enhance the competitiveness and sustainability of the maritime industry in Europe. By bringing together national maritime clusters, the network fosters collaboration, innovation, and sustainable practices across the sector. While challenges remain, the ENMC's initiatives have already yielded considerable progress and hold great promise for the future. Continued international cooperation and commitment to sustainable practices are essential for the health and prosperity of the European maritime industry and its stakeholders.

The ENMC's success will depend on the sustained commitment of its members, innovative solutions, and the engagement of the broader European and international community. Through collective action and a shared vision, the network aims to ensure that the maritime industry continues to thrive, providing essential services and benefits for current and future generations.

Red de Cruceros Costeros y Fluviales de los Destinos Náuticos Sostenibles de España (Red CCF)

a. Introduction and Objectives

[Red CCF](#) is financed by the Tourism Experiences of Spain program, managed by the Ministry of Industry and Tourism with funds from the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan.

The project was created to set up a platform to serve as a national interlocutor to plan the development of nautical destinations and a standardized offer of coastal and river cruises in Spain and thus be able to compete with other major European nautical destinations. The aim of the project is to create nautical-cultural experiences and attract new audiences and tourists.

These experiences called "Coastal and River Cruises" consist of combined nautical itineraries that combine elements of natural and cultural heritage with different tourist services of the destination, both coastal and inland, and which seek to position themselves internationally as a prestigious brand of their own.

b. Membership and Structure

The project is led by AGAN+, Asociación Galega de Actividades Náuticas representing Galicia together with the company Destination Experiences and GDR Ribeira Sacra; Berdeago, the European Association for Sustainability, at a national level; the company Factor Ocio S. L. from Extremadura, the Diputación de Valladolid, AZTUR, Asociación Zamorana de Turismo Rural, GEOCyL and AIMRD, Asociación Ibérica de Municipios Ribereños del Duero in Castilla y León; Sail In Festival, from the Basque Country, Puerto Sotogrande S. A. and the Maritime-Marine Cluster of Andalusia in the same region; the Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Ceuta; the Maritime and Logistics Cluster of the Balearic Islands; PIMEC of Catalonia and Turitech, Turismo Integral en Red S.L. in the Canary Islands.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Weaknesses of the nautical tourism offer

Most current nautical products are associated with the concept of sun and beach and are mainly aimed at a more sailing or expert public. The offer does not include the enhancement of the heritage of nautical tourism destinations. The existing nautical offer is dispersed and there is a great lack of knowledge of the river nautical product, which hardly has any references or visibility at the level of the Spain brand. Many nautical destinations need to improve their sustainability

and digitalization in order to be more respectful of the natural environment and more accessible to all types of publics. Given the size of the companies in the sector, they do not have sufficient resources to properly promote and market their products at national and international level.

To overcome these barriers, the Red CCF has planned a roadmap with a total of 39 actions grouped under five main objectives:

1. Generate Network
2. Train and Create Product
3. Improve Resources
4. Communicate
5. Commercialize

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

The Red CCF network is a newly formed network with a very clear vocation for the commercialization of new sustainable tourism products in the field of navigation in sea and river waters, the main challenge facing this network is linked to the evaluation of the results of the initiative and the sustainability of the same.

Both the coordinator and the partners of this network have ample experience in the management of similar initiatives, which will undoubtedly make it possible to face the challenges detected and give sustainability to the initiative, not only at a national level in Spain but also at an international level.

[SEAStarlight “Unidos por la mar, hermanos por las estrellas”](#)

a. Introduction and Objectives

[Sea Starlight](#) project is financed by the Tourism Experiences of Spain program, managed by the Ministry of Industry and Tourism with funds from the Recovery, Transformation, and Resilience Plan.

The project represents the whole of Spain's coastline and claims the relationship that has always existed between navigation and astronomy. All the experiences developed by the Sea Starlight project are conceived in a collaborative way through a close relationship with astro-tourism operators in each of the participating territories, promoting circular economy and sustainability.

b. Membership and Structure

The national coordinator of the project is Nautic Ocean, and the territorial managers are Cabo Mayor in Cantabria, San Yago Charter in Galicia, Escuela Náutica Azimut in Asturias, Pakea Sailing Experience in the Vasque Country, Virazón Chárter in the Murcia region, Academia Náutica Lanzarote in Canary Islands, A Tod VELA in Andalucía, Academia Náutica Océano in la Comunitat Valenciana, and the Club del Navegante in Cataluña.

NUESTRO PRODUCTO

Figure 5: Territories belonging to the SEAStarlight network. Source: Sea Starlight website.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

“Star tourism”, or Astrotourism, is an emerging, innovative and high-quality modality of sustainable and responsible tourism, which in turn drives the local economy. Combining observation of the sky with activities linked to this natural resource: stars, galaxies and the dissemination of astronomy.

To promote this scientific tourism, it is necessary to protect the night sky, thus saving energy and mitigating the effects of climate change, while combining the stellar landscape with the natural, cultural, scientific, biodiversity and environmental assets of the places they occupy, taking care of the night sky. All members are already certified as Starlight companies by the Foundation, and therefore signatories to the "La Palma" manifesto.

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

SEA Starlight is a newly constituted network with a very clear vocation for the commercialisation of new sustainable nautical tourism products linked to the star observation under a competence certified by the Starlight Foundation, as well as relying on new technologies, the main challenge facing this network is linked to the evaluation of the results of the initiative and its sustainability.

Both the leader and the partners of this network are companies with great experience in the commercialisation of nautical products. Moreover, the leader, NAUTIC OCEAN, participates in the TWINNEDbySTARS project as one of the main promoters, so the viability of the initiative will have

a continuity and international expansion, beyond the borders of Spain, which will undoubtedly make it possible to face the challenges detected and give sustainability to the initiative.

ATLAZUL “Impulso de la Alianza Litoral Atlántica para el Crecimiento Azul”

a. Introduction and Objectives

ATLAZUL is an ambitious initiative aimed at fostering blue growth and sustainable development across the Atlantic regions. The objectives of ATLAZUL are the consolidation of regional governance structures in the regions of the AAA+G Euroregion, the definition of joint political strategies for the promotion of the Blue Economy, the definition of the interregional collaborative governance model, the promotion of new growth opportunities for Blue Economy companies and sectors, and the development of the Blue Economy.

b. Membership and Structure

ATLAZUL has a public-private nature, it is a cooperation structure between the Atlantic regions of Spain and Portugal to promote political coordination and cross-border Blue Growth projects in the Atlantic framework.

ATLAZUL is led by the General Secretariat for External Action of the Ministry of the Presidency, Public Administration and Domestic Affairs of the Regional Government of Andalusia, with a total of 18 partners (11 Spanish and 7 Portuguese) from the regions of Alentejo, Algarve, Andalusia and Galicia.

ATLAZUL's organizational structure includes a steering committee, an executive board, a technical coordination committee, a working committee, an advisory committee and if necessary, a technical secretariat, as well as an honorary chair and at least 5 thematic working groups. The executive board consists of a president, three vice-presidents, a secretary and a general treasurer and several working groups. The steering committee, composed of representatives from member countries and key stakeholders, sets the strategic direction and priorities for the initiative. The executive board oversees the implementation of ATLAZUL's work program and ensures effective coordination among members. Working groups focus on specific thematic areas such as marine research, sustainable tourism, fisheries management, and renewable energy, bringing together experts to address common challenges and develop innovative solutions.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Economic Development and Innovation

One of the core focus areas of ATLAZUL is promoting economic development and innovation within the blue economy.

Its functions are divided into the following:

Political impulse:

- Defining a strategic framework for cross-border cooperation.
- Networking with alliances in other regions

Economic promotion:

- Fostering cross-border collaboration projects in Blue Economy driving sectors.
- Promote the competitiveness of blue economy sub-sectors through open innovation processes for innovation, sustainability and digitalization of SMEs.
- Bringing funding closer to cross-border projects

Training and capacity building:

- Promote training actions at university and vocational training level.
- Promote training and informal education actions

Communication:

- To give visibility to the activity of the Alliance
- Organize relevant events in the framework of the Blue Economy.
- Establish communication and dissemination channels with companies.
- Disseminate information of interest among Alliance partners and companies.

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

Major Challenges and Criticisms

ATLAZUL is a newly constituted network with a very clear vocation for the blue policy advocacy, from a sustainability point of view: (1) economic, through the promotion of transnational cooperation and open innovation, (2) environmental, through the involvement of partners in this line and representing the fifth blade of the quintuple helix included in the network, and (3) social, through the promotion of training and capacity building, both formal and informal. Therefore, the main challenge facing this network is linked to the evaluation of the results of the initiative and its sustainability.

Future Directions and Long-Term Vision

Looking ahead, ATLAZUL aims to strengthen its role as a leader in promoting blue growth and sustainability in the Atlantic regions. Planned future initiatives include:

- Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer: The initiative aims to enhance the capacity of local communities and stakeholders to adopt and manage sustainable practices. This includes providing training, technical assistance, and knowledge transfer programs to build local expertise and support the sustainable development of the blue economy.
- Strengthened Policy Advocacy: ATLAZUL intends to strengthen its advocacy efforts at national and international levels to promote policies and regulations that support the sustainable development of the blue economy. This includes engaging with policymakers, industry stakeholders, and international organizations to shape policies that incentivize sustainable practices and support environmental protection.

- Development of Integrated Blue Economy Strategies: The initiative will continue to develop and promote integrated strategies that combine economic development with environmental sustainability.

The long-term vision of ATLAZUL is to create a resilient and competitive blue economy in the Atlantic regions that is capable of leading global efforts in innovation and sustainability. Achieving this vision requires continued commitment from member countries and regions, effective collaboration, and proactive engagement with local communities and stakeholders.

ATLAZUL’s success will depend on the sustained commitment of its members, innovative solutions, and the engagement of the broader regional and international community. Through collective action and a shared vision, the initiative aims to ensure that the blue economy continues to thrive, providing essential services and benefits for current and future generations.

European Marine Board

a. Introduction and Objectives

The European Marine Board was established in 1995 to facilitate increased cooperation between European marine science organizations with a view to developing a common vision on strategic priorities for marine science research in Europe.

The European Marine Board is a unique pan-European strategic forum for marine and ocean research and technology. It provides a strategic forum for developing marine research foresight, initiating cutting-edge analyses and translating them into clear policy recommendations for European institutions and national governments.

b. Membership and Structure

Members of the European Marine Board are leading national marine and oceanographic institutes, research funding agencies or national consortia of universities with a strong focus on marine research. The EMB currently has 38 members from 19 European countries, representing more than 10,000 scientists and technicians. The EMB consists of 20 research organizations, nine research funding organizations and nine consortia. These consortia represent a total of 120 organizations, 93 of which are universities.

Table 4: Research institutions at European national level that are part of the European Marine Board.
Source: website of the European Marine Board.

Country	Members
Belgium	Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO)
	Fonds National de la Recherche Scientifique (FNRS)

Country	Members
	Fonds voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek - Vlaanderen (FWO)
Croatia	Institut za oceanografiju i ribarstvo (IOF)
	Institut Ruđer Bošković (IRB)
Cyprus	Cyprus Marine and Maritime Institute (CMMI)
Denmark	Institut for Akvatiske Ressourcer (DTU Aqua)
Estonia	Eesti Teaduste Akadeemia (ETA)
France	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS)
	Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer (IFREMER)
	Universités Marines (UM)
Germany	Konsortium Deutsche Meeresforschung (KDM)
	Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel (GEOMAR)
Greek	Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)
Ireland	Marine Institute
	Irish Marine Universities Consortium (IMUC)
Italy	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)
	Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS)
	Consorzio Nazionale Interuniversitario per le Scienze del Mare (CoNISMa)
	Stazione Zoologica Anton Dohrn (SZN)
Netherlands	Nederlandse Organisatie voor Wetenschappelijk Onderzoek (NIOZ)
	Deltares
Norway	Havforskningsinstituttet (HI)
	Norges forskningsrad
	Norsk Marint Universitetskonsortium (NMU)
	NORCE Norwegian Research Centre (NORCE)
	SINTEF Ocean

Country	Members
Poland	Instytut Oceanologii Polskiej Akademii Nauk (IO-PAN)
Portugal	Centro de Investigação Marinha e Ambiental - Laboratório Associado (CIMAR - LA)
	Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT)
Romania	Romanian Black Sea Research Consortium (RBRC)
Spain	Instituto Español de Oceanografía (IEO)
	Centro Tecnológico del Mar (CETMAR)
Sweden	Göteborgs Universitet (UGOT)
Turkey	Türkiye Bilimsel ve Teknik Arastirma Kurumu (TÜBİTAK)
United Kingdom	Marine Alliance for Science and Technology Scotland (MASTS)
	Natural Environment Research Council (NERC)
	National Oceanography Centre (NOC)

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

The European Marine Board builds bridges between science and policy using different approaches, such as:

- Strategy: identifying scientific challenges and opportunities through foresight activities, analyses and studies, and providing high-level recommendations.
- Forum: bringing together European marine research stakeholders to share knowledge, identify common priorities, develop common positions and collaborate.
- Voice: expressing a collective vision of European marine research priorities to address future scientific and societal challenges and opportunities.

The Executive Committee (ExCom) oversees the functioning of the European Marine Board, is composed of a chairperson and six Vice-Chairpersons, elected by the members of the European Marine Board, and the Executive Director of the Secretariat (ex officio).

The ExCom provides strategic guidance to the Board and the Secretariat, oversees the implementation of actions agreed by the Board at plenary meetings and takes operational and financial decisions.

Marine Research and Innovation

One of the core focus areas of the EMB is promoting marine research and innovation. The EMB supports the development of cutting-edge marine science by fostering collaboration among research institutions, facilitating access to research infrastructure, and promoting interdisciplinary research initiatives. Key initiatives include large-scale research projects, joint research programs, and international collaborations aimed at advancing our understanding of marine ecosystems and their role in the Earth system.

The EMB also plays a critical role in driving innovation in marine technologies and solutions. This includes promoting the development of new tools and techniques for marine observation and data collection, supporting the integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and robotics into marine research, and fostering innovation in areas such as marine biotechnology and renewable energy. These efforts are essential for maintaining the competitiveness of European marine research and ensuring its contribution to addressing global challenges.

Policy Advice and Strategic Foresight

Policy advice and strategic foresight are key activities of the EMB. The EMB provides evidence-based advice to policymakers on a wide range of marine-related issues, helping to inform policy decisions and shape regulatory frameworks that support sustainable marine development. This includes providing input to European and international policy processes, developing policy briefs and position papers, and organizing policy dialogues and workshops.

Strategic foresight involves anticipating future trends and challenges in marine science and policy and developing long-term strategies to address them. The EMB conducts foresight studies and horizon scanning exercises to identify emerging issues and opportunities in the marine sector. This proactive approach helps to ensure that marine research remains relevant and responsive to societal needs and that Europe is well-prepared to address future marine challenges.

Notable initiatives led by the EMB include the development of the European Ocean Observing System (EOOS), which aims to enhance the coordination and integration of ocean observation efforts across Europe, and the publication of foresight reports such as "Navigating the Future," which provide strategic guidance on key marine research priorities and challenges.

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

Major Challenges and Criticisms

Despite its successes, the EMB faces several challenges. One major challenge is ensuring effective coordination and collaboration among a diverse group of member organizations with varying priorities and capacities. Securing adequate funding for large-scale research projects and initiatives is another persistent issue, particularly in the face of economic uncertainties and budget constraints.

The European Marine Board (EMB) represents a vital effort to advance marine science and technology in Europe. By bringing together leading marine research organizations, the EMB

fosters collaboration, innovation, and strategic foresight in the marine sector. Continued international cooperation and commitment to scientific excellence and sustainability are essential for the health and prosperity of the marine environment and its communities.

Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster

a. Introduction and Objectives

The [Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster](#) focuses on enhancing the maritime economy in Guadeloupe, integrating traditional sectors like tourism, fishing, and marine activities with emerging sectors such as renewable energy and digital technologies. It aims to support businesses through innovation, ecological transition, and internationalization efforts. Created by the Constituent General Assembly on 18 May 2011, the Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster, whose head office is located in Pointe-à-Pitre, is an association governed by the law of 1 July 1901 and the decree of 16 August 2001.

Objectives:

- the study of the possibilities for the development of the Blue Economy
- the promotion and defence of the marine and maritime sector and related activities of Guadeloupe
- the implementation of actions in the fields of intervention of these activities, in the context of freight and passenger transport, navigation, fishing, marine research and protection, ports and port services, maritime training and employment, maritime financing, shipbuilding, ship repair and renewable energies.

b. Membership and Structure

Board of Directors:

The Board of Directors is composed of at least 10 Members and a maximum of 18 Members, elected by the General Assembly and 1 Legal Member and 3 Members as natural persons. The term of office of the members is three years.

Elected members of the Board of Directors are companies, associations, organizations, qualified personalities and natural persons in categories 1 to 3 as defined in article 6 of the statutes. The members of the cluster are listed in the table below.

Table 5: Entities that constitute the Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster, divided by activity. Source: website of the Guadeloupe maritime cluster.

Activity	Entity name
TOURISM LEISURE AND SEA ACTIVITIES	ATMOSPHERE
	PPK Plongée

Activity	Entity name
	LD Marine
	REVE DE NAV
	ASSOCIATION DES PROFESSIONNELS DE LA MER
	BLEU OUTREMER
	BLUE LAGOON
	BRUDEY EXCURSIONS
	CARAIBES EVASION
	COCO MAMBO
	DREAMLANDS EXCURSIONS
	Antennaire Plongée
	GUADELOUPE EVASION DECOUVERTE
	GWADAVENTURE
	LES NAUTILUS
	LITEE
	MAXIMUM KIT & WING
	NICO EXCURSIONS
	REGY BALADE
	SADEMAR
	SOCIETE CIPRIN
	TALAMANCA
	TAMTAM PAGAIE
	TIKI BOAT
	TIOTO
	VERSION CARAÏBES
	VOU E MWEN
	WEST INDIES EXCURSIONS
	YO DEMAER
Sailing	Georges SANTTALIKAN
	Ligue Guadeloupéenne de Voile
	MARINA BAS-DU-FORT

Activity	Entity name
Shipbuilding industry	DOCKS SERVICES
	IMM YACHTING
Professional fisheries and aquaculture	COMITE REGIONAL DES PECHEES
	ETS BEKINELA
Maritime transport and services	CAMARSHIP
	Karu Ferry
	CEI.BA
	CMA CGM
	GINIT SARL
	GUADELOUPE PORT CARAIBES
	GPE YACHT CONCIÈRGE
	L'EXPRESS DES ILES
	SCDTG
	SYNDICAT PROFESSIONNEL DES PILOTES DE GUADELOUPE
	UMEP
Related activities	AGENCE DES 50 PAS
	ATRAM ANTILLES
	AMPI
	BRED
	COREGUA
	CTIG
	METIMER
	PETRA MARITIMA GUADELOUPE
	PARC NATIONAL DE GUADELOUPE
	SERVICE SOCIAL MARITIME

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

Economic Development and Innovation

One of the core focus areas of the Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster is promoting economic development and innovation within the maritime sector. In relation to the development of

sustainable blue tourism, the cluster carries out different actions, of which we highlight some of those carried out in 2023, as follows:

- promoted a free online training for tourism providers on sustainable development, supported by Atout France and developed by Green Flow.
- contributed to the Cruise Lab input to the Overseas Tourism Strategic Committee 2023.
- in consultation with the managers of the Grand Cul-de-sac Marin, represented service providers during discussions on the closure of Îlet Caret, initially planned for 4 months.
- raising awareness among the general public and school children of the importance and fragility of natural environments with the participation of 380 schoolchildren
- Consultation on mangroves and wetlands - Community nautical station label

d. Major Challenges and Criticisms

The Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster, established in 2011, is a solid tool that meets its objectives of supporting the sustainable development of the six main sectors in the region linked to the blue economy. This is a guarantee for the future, as it also has the support of both the private and public sectors to represent the blue economy in different dialogue tables, as well as to promote innovation and the attraction of new emerging sectors.

However, the promotion of innovation and the internationalisation of the cluster's actions is one of the challenges faced by the entity, in order to differentiate itself from the usual business associations, so participation in international projects could be a short-term strategy.

[Martinique Maritime Cluster](#)

a. Introduction and Objectives

The [Martinique Maritime Cluster](#) (CMM) aims to boost the maritime industry in Martinique by fostering innovation, supporting marine businesses, and promoting sustainable maritime activities. It collaborates with various stakeholders to enhance the region's maritime potential and environmental sustainability

The CMM is an organization created in 2012 by and for professionals. Its aim is to bring together local maritime stakeholders, implement their projects and develop the maritime sector in Martinique. From industry to services, the CMM is made up of companies of all sizes, competitiveness clusters, federations and associations, laboratories and research centres, schools and training organizations, local communities and economic actors, as well as the French Navy.

b. Membership and Structure

The CMM is building with its members a 'Martinique maritime hub', a real business-generating ecosystem. In an extremely competitive economy, it is imperative to create synergies between maritime stakeholders, so that the entire economy can benefit from the maritime innovation

capacities and business opportunities offered by activities at sea. The members of the cluster are listed in the table below.

Table 6: List of members of the Martinique Maritime Cluster. Source: website of the Martinique maritime cluster.

Entity name	Entity name
A2M	A&C YACHT BROKERS
ACTI Antilles	AIEX
AGENCE FRANCAISE POUR LA BIODIVERISTE	ASSOCIATION DES FORMATIONS PRO. MARITIME
BAC ANTILLES	BRED
BUREAU VERITAS - D	CARAIBE MARINE
CARENANTILLES	CARIBE DIVING COMPANY
CEGELEC MARINE	CENT
CMA CGM	CORRHOL ENGINEERING
DEAL	DIRECTION DE LA MER
EXPEDITION 7° CONTINENT	ECOMER EIRL
ENTREPRISE NOUVELLE ANTILLAISE (ENA)	FLAGSHIP COMPANY
GAZ DOM	GRAND PORT MARITIME DE LA MARTINIQUE (GPMLM)
GLOBAL MARINE	IMPACT MER SARL
INBOARD DIESEL SERVICE	INSTITUT DE SOUDURE INDUSTRIE
JOSEPHA Gérard	LINISE Alain
HYDRO TECH CARAIB	MARSHIP
MITHDM SARL	PETROSERVICES
POLYMAR	SAINT-JOURS EXPERT MARITIME
SACNAM	SCHEHERAZADE MARTINIQUE
SEREC	SERVICE PLONGEE
SERVICE SOCIAL MARITIME	SNSM
SOMARA	SOREIDOM
SUD MOTEUR	SYNDICAT DES TRANSITAIRES DE MARTINIQUE
SYNDICAT PROFESSIONNEL DES PILOTES DE MARTINIQUE	TOURNIER François

Entity name	Entity name
VALERE Laurent	VEETTES TROPICALES
YVES KINARD EXPERT MARITIME	MARTINIQUE YACHTING ASSOCIATION

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

The Martinique Maritime Cluster's statutes are centred around three key objectives:

- To promote and defend Martinique's maritime and marine activities and their related activities,
- To study their development potential,
- To carry out all actions in the fields in which these activities operate, in particular: freight and passenger transport, nautical, fishing, marine research and protection, ports and port services, maritime training and employment, maritime financing, shipbuilding and ship repair, and renewable energies.

To achieve its objectives, the Martinique Maritime Cluster sets up 3 vectors following the example of the French Maritime Cluster: institutional communication, operational synergies and leverage actions.

We highlight in this section lobbying actions that are undertaken for the benefit of and at the request of CMM members, or for the benefit of the maritime community as a whole. Undertaken to defend and promote strategic issues, they enable CMM to be recognized as representing the general interest of the maritime economy and as an effective advocate for the specific issues of its members (when they are of general interest).

The Martinique Maritime Cluster is the main promoter of the Martinique Boat Show and this 2024 was organized for its fourth edition in May. For TWINNEDbySTARS it was a crucial moment to approach companies and other representatives of the quadruple propeller for stakeholder involvement.

The Martinique Boat Show is considered to be the boat show of the Caribbean. After four editions, the Martinique Boat Show has increased the number of exhibitors, as well as allowing for parallel actions such as cooperative work between participants and highlighting maritime professions and opportunities for the development of the sector, adapting to the reality of the industry in the region and the environmental challenges it faces.

d. Major Challenges and Criticisms

The Martinique Maritime Cluster is a solid tool, established in 2012 and which meets its objectives of supporting the sustainable development of the sectors in the region linked to the blue economy. However, the remoteness of the metropole and the close relationship with the

national maritime cluster, whereby the CMM is a kind of branch of the national one, are circumstances that influence the development of this entity. To be able to build a consolidated network of companies, which see in this cluster a source of opportunities at regional level for innovation and internationalisation of their business, is the key challenge it faces. Therefore, their participation in international projects, which connect them with other national and international clusters, is a powerful lever to tackle these challenges. An example of this is TWINNEDbySTARS in which CMM participates through the Collectivité de Martinique.

Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique

a. Introduction and Objectives

Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique is a French competitive cluster based in Brittany, dedicated to maritime innovation and sustainability. It aims to foster technological advancements and sustainable practices in the maritime sector. The cluster focuses on six main areas: maritime safety and security, naval and nautical industries, marine energy resources, marine biological resources, environmental and coastal planning, and maritime ports and logistics.

The Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique is a competitiveness cluster dedicated to the blue economy. They bring together a community of more than 450 members (start-ups, SMEs and ETIs, large groups, R&D and research organizations and professional organizations).

The Pôle support maritime innovation through innovative research and development projects of their members, in particular by connecting academic and industrial actors. These projects lead and contribute to the services and products of a sustainable and responsible blue economy.

Their mission is, above all, to ensure support for innovation in two of France's most maritime regions: Brittany and Pays de la Loire. This territory thus constitutes the first French employment area, with nearly 50% of direct jobs in the blue economy.

With more than 20% of their members outside its two regions and in close collaboration with the Pôle Mer Méditerranée, they support the competitiveness of companies at the national and European level. The Pôle contribute to the structuring of the maritime sector through active participation in the strategic sectoral committee of maritime industrialists, within the animation of the maritime ecosystem for CORIMER (Conseil d'Orientation et de Recherche des Industriels de la Mer). They maintain a European dynamic both for their structure and for their members with active participation in European projects (Horizon Europe, INTERREG, etc.) as well as in organizations (DG-MARE, CINEA, etc.) and European programs (Copernicus).

Table 7: Entities that constitute the Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique, only those related to shipbuilding and nautical tourism are included. Source: website of the Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique.

Members	
Alliatech	Chantiers de l'Atlantique
Aqualines SAS	Compagnie du Ponant

Members	
Arco Ingénierie	Compagnie Maritime Nantaise-MN
Armen initiative	Coopération Maritime Conseil et Services
Avelaj	CWS
OceanWings	D-ICE Engineering
Beneteau S.A.	Eco Trans Océan
Benjamin Muyl Design	Ecole Navale
Birdyfish	Ecosoftec
Bluenav	EHM
BPN (Bretagne Pôle Naval)	EN MOTEURS
Brittany Ferries	Energy Observer Developments
Bureau d'Etudes MAURIC	Estaca
Campus des Métiers et des Qualifications	Europe Technologies CIAM
Cargomorphose	Farwind Energy
Chantier Naval de Martinique	Finistère Mer Vent
Finsulate France	Obsam
FinX	Océan Développement
Florian Madec Composites	Pantocarène
French touch oceans club	PIRIOU INGENIERIE
Geniwind Marine SAS	Pixel sur Mer
GICAN	Plastimo Group
Green Navy	Polyacht
GSEA DESIGN	Richard Marine Consulting
Hy Generation	Robin Marine
Imoca	Sailcoop
K-Challenge LAB SAS	SARL Vebrat
Kairos	SAS Beyond the sea
Kara Technology	Sea Impulse
Korzenn	SEA.AI
L'Hydroptere 2.0 SAS	SEAir Solutions
La vague asso	SerEnMar SAS - Ship As A Service
Louis Dreyfus Armateurs	Ship-ST

Members	
Maloric	SMO-NAVIS
Marinelec Technologies	SNE SMM
Marvin Series	SNEF - Agence Navale Bretagne
Meltemus SAS	Société Bretonne de Construction Navale
Mer Agitée	SRA
Mer Concept	Stirling Design International
Metalenergy	TE2M
MICHELIN – WISAMO	Telasto
Moteurs JM	Temo
Multiplast Groupe Carboman	Vectura System
Nautix	Wichard SAS
Naval Group Brest	Wind Support NYC
Naval Group Lorient	Yuniboat
Navalu	Zephyr & Borée SAS
Navexpo	Agence Think+
Naviwatt	Aronnax SAS
NDAR	Avel Robotics
Neoline Développement	Cegelec Marine
Neopolia	Chantier naval Delavergne
NumSmo Technologies	Direction du Service de Soutien de la Flotte de Brest
Grondin Marine	Euronav Ship Management
Switch SAS	

b. Membership and Structure

Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique includes a diverse array of stakeholders, including companies, research organizations, universities, and public institutions. This extensive network ensures a comprehensive approach to addressing the challenges and opportunities in the maritime sector.

The organizational structure of the cluster consists of a General Assembly and a board of directors consisting of 4 colleges (1) representatives of large companies, (2) small and medium-sized enterprises, (3) universities and large academic schools, training centres and research, innovation and technology centres, and (4) composed of professional organizations and blue economy and innovation development structures.

c. Key Focus Areas and Initiatives

By 2026, their ambitions for the benefit of their members and the blue economy are:

- To be a recognized actor at regional, national, European and global level to support innovation.
- To position and strengthen the visibility of the excellence of the actors in our territories.
- Contribute to a sustainable, responsible and sovereign blue economy.
- Facilitate capacity building in our territory in line with the emerging needs of industry.

The activities they will carry out to achieve the above objectives are as follows

- Promote and network the skills of its members
- Encourage synergies between research and training centres and businesses
- Encourage the development of the blue economy in Brittany and Pays de la Loire, in particular through support for innovative SMEs
- Promote the skills of its members, as well as the image of the cluster, in order to increase its attractiveness.
- Position the maritime innovation carried out by its members at national and international level by coordinating with the Pôle Mer Méditerranée.

d. Challenges, Criticisms, and Future Prospects

The challenges faced by the pole in this phase 5 of the development of its actions until 2026 are those linked to the objectives proposed in an international scope of application, taking into account that more than 70% of its partners are small and medium-sized enterprises.

The pole is an entity with solid governance, which guarantees the implementation of its roadmap and positions it as one of the most important alliances in the Atlantic, so the synergies with this entity are clear.

3.4 ANALYSIS OF SYNERGIES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR COLLABORATION

International alliances, coalitions, confederations and partnerships are essential for the development and sustainability of marine and coastal tourism because, among others, partnerships help align regional and national efforts with global commitments, especially those related to underwater life (SDG 14) and climate action (SDG 13), ensuring a coordinated and effective approach.

TWINNEDbySTARS aims at increasing the competitiveness of the maritime tourism sector in Outermost regions while contributing to protect marine biodiversity, preserving the cultural heritage and develop marine astro-tourism, recalling ancient navigators as a sustainable destination for these remote territories, by strengthening partnerships already in operation, capacity building and co-creation for tourism products. Several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners are integrated in the A3M "Macaronesian Maritime-Maritime Alliance" and NAUTICOM "Macaronesia Nautical Cooperation Network" therefore represent the starting point for our

initiative, however, we recognise that there are other alliances in the region with which joint initiatives can be generated to further the objective of these coalitions beyond the projects that set them in motion, facilitating the achievement of their objectives, which is why in the following section we include some proposals for synergies and opportunities for collaboration with both NAUTICOM and A3M.

Analysis of Synergies

1. Enhancing Collaborative Networks:

The existing cooperation networks in the Atlantic demonstrate strong foundations in fostering collaborative efforts among various stakeholders. Projects like TWINNEDbySTARS and other EMFAF Flagship projects showcase the potential of leveraging regional strengths through joint initiatives. These projects highlight the importance of integrating public and private sectors, research institutions, and local communities to promote sustainable maritime and coastal tourism.

2. Promoting Sustainable Blue Growth:

Synergies between various maritime clusters, such as the Canary Islands Maritime Cluster and the Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique, the Maritime Cluster of Martinique or the Maritime Cluster of Guadeloupe, offer substantial opportunities for promoting sustainable blue growth. These clusters can collaborate on projects focused on marine renewable energies, aquaculture, and eco-tourism. By sharing best practices and innovative technologies, these regions can enhance their economic resilience and environmental sustainability.

3. Strengthening Innovation and Digital Transition:

The emphasis on digital transformation and innovation in networks like NAUTICOM and initiatives under the Atlantic Action Plan 2.0 can be expanded through collaborative efforts. By fostering transnational cooperation, regions can accelerate the adoption of digital tools, enhance data sharing, and support the development of new maritime products and services. This approach can significantly improve operational efficiencies and market reach for SMEs in the maritime sector.

4. Leveraging Cultural and Natural Heritage:

The outermost regions have a unique blue economy potential thanks to their large Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZs), which represent more than half of the EU's EEZs, and rich marine biodiversity, being considered biodiversity hotspots. The rich cultural and natural heritage of these regions offers unique opportunities for creating distinctive tourism experiences. Initiatives like the A3M alliance, which focuses on blue vocations and support for the development of sustainable nautical tourism, can be integrated with other tourism initiatives to provide comprehensive, sustainable tourism packages. Collaborative marketing and branding efforts can further enhance the attractiveness of these regions as premier tourist destinations.

5. Enhancing Training and Capacity Building:

Ongoing projects, like those financed by EMFAF Blue careers calls, emphasize the importance of upskilling, reskilling, crosskilling and capacity building for tourism stakeholders. By developing joint training programs and workshops, regions can ensure that local businesses and communities are well-equipped to manage and promote sustainable tourism practices. This can lead to improved service quality, greater environmental awareness, and enhanced visitor satisfaction.

6. Expanding Eco-Tourism and Marine Conservation:

Projects like TWINNEDbySTARS underscore the potential of eco-tourism and marine conservation as key drivers of sustainable development. Collaboration among regions can lead to the creation of cross-border eco-tourism routes, conservation initiatives, and educational programs that highlight the importance of protecting marine ecosystems while providing unique tourist experiences.

Complementary collaborations

1. A3M alliance and ATLAZUL

Concept:

Integrated Blue Economy Strategies. A3M alliance and ATLAZUL could work together to develop and implement integrated strategies that promote blue growth while ensuring environmental sustainability, through actions to strengthen political advocacy for the promotion of the blue economy.

Benefits:

- **Holistic Development:** Address economic, environmental, and social dimensions of blue growth in a coordinated manner.
- **Resource Efficiency:** Optimize the use of marine resources through better planning and management.
- **Resilience:** Enhance the resilience of coastal communities to environmental pressures, including climate change.

2. A3M alliance and the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique

Concept:

Renewable Energy Projects: Collaborate on projects that combine A3M alliance's expertise with Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique's focus on marine renewable energy, and more specifically in

offshore wind. This can include developing digital tools for monitoring and optimizing renewable energy installations like offshore wind farms and tidal or wave energy plants.

Blue Economy Initiatives: Jointly develop initiatives that promote the blue economy, focusing on sustainable practices and digital innovation. This can involve in creating digital tools for blue economy stakeholders to share knowledge, collaborate on projects, and access funding opportunities.

Benefits:

- Strengthened blue economy through innovative and sustainable practices.
- Enhanced efficiency and performance of renewable energy projects.
- Improved and resource sharing among blue economy stakeholders.

3. NAUTICOM and Martinique Maritime Cluster

Concept:

Heritage and Innovation Tourism: Develop tourism packages that integrate Martinique's rich cultural maritime and marine heritage with regions and countries that are included in the NAUTICOM's network (Canary, Madeira, Azores and Cap Vert islands and Mauritania). This can include guided tours of historical sites and interactive exhibits showcasing the region's maritime history.

Blue tourism Workshops: Conduct joint workshops and seminars focused on blue tourism, highlighting sustainable practices and innovations in maritime and coastal tourism. This can include topics like sustainable sport fishing, and eco-tourism.

Benefits:

- Enhanced tourism offerings that attract history and innovation enthusiasts.
- Strengthened local economy through sustainable tourism and blue economy initiatives.
- Increased knowledge exchange and resource sharing between regions.

4. NAUTICOM and Red de Cruceros Costeros y Fluviales de los Destinos Náuticos Sostenibles de España (Red CCF)

Concept:

Nautical tourism destinations: the existing nautical offer is dispersed and there is a great lack of knowledge, and many nautical destinations need to improve their sustainability and digitalization in order to be more respectful of the natural environment and more accessible to all types of publics. Given the size of the companies in the sector, they do not have sufficient resources to properly promote and market their products at national and international level.

Benefits:

- Design and market product: advice to nautical/tourism operators for the creation of more sustainable sea-related tourism products and development and testing of products for their implementation involving local operators.
- Improve Resources: undertake public-private influence actions for the adaptation and improvement of facilities and means to advance the implementation of sustainable nautical destinations.

Roadmap to enhance the four partnerships analysed and benefits for TWINNEDbySTARS

The aim of TWINNEDbySTARS is not to create more networks, but to make the product and developments elaborated in this initiative compatible with other existing alliances and networks.

These reference networks are the A3M Alliance and the NAUTICOM Network, which, as we have seen in the previous section, also have synergies with other Atlantic alliances. Below are some short- and medium-term actions to foster the relationship with these alliances, mainly through direct contact with these other alliances or interest groups.

A3M Alliance with ATLAZUL and Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique

The A3M Alliance and ATLAZUL are together in the new project financed by the InterregMAC programme, called A3MAtlantic, where ATLAZUL participates as an associated partner, so the relationship between these two alliances will already be considered a reality in the coming years. As for the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique, it is considered a reference in its connections at European level, and as a strong advocate of the importance of the Atlantic Ocean and its regions in the policies related to the blue economy, so that within the actions of A3MAtlantic it will be considered as one of the possible entities associated with the agenda of strategic positioning for the blue economy, the strengthening of the A3M Alliance and expansion of this initiative in the Mid-Atlantic.

Blue policies and the importance of these in the development of maritime and coastal tourism are essential, so the product generated in TWINNEDbySTARS will be presented as a featured action in several of the actions of the A3M strategic positioning agenda. Once the TWINNEDbySTARS product has been launched, it will be presented both in the framework of the A3M alliance actions and in meetings with ATLAZUL and the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique, where minutes will be taken of the meetings held and the list of future actions to be carried out.

NAUTICOM with the Martinique Maritime Cluster and the Coastal and River Cruise Network of Sustainable Nautical Destinations of Spain (Red CCF)

NAUTICOM and Red CCF already have development links through the collaboration established by CETECIMA between the two networks, with the aim of creating spaces in which to generate actions to support maritime, coastal and river tourism. Within these actions, tourism products will be developed with synergies between the two networks and TWINNEDbySTARS. Likewise, for the

Martinique Maritime Cluster, actions for the sustainable development of coastal and maritime tourism are one of the main lines of action, and TWINNEDbySTARS and its partner in Martinique are working extensively to ensure that there is real collaboration both in the co-creation phase and in the implementation of the product.

Coastal and maritime tourism is currently facing challenges to make the sector more sustainable, green and digital, so NAUTICOM and its strategic partnerships with the Martinique Maritime Cluster and the Red CCF network, act as agents in the Atlantic so that products such as the one generated in TWINNEDbySTARS are widely accepted as good practice in this regard, for which they will hold specific meetings with these networks.

The NAUTICOM network is the basis of the new InterregMAC funded project, called INNOVABLUE, with a dedicated focus on the development of sustainable blue tourism products, which will give the opportunity to establish synergies with the TWINNEDbySTARS product developed beyond the project.

4. MAPPING STAKEHOLDERS

Mapping is an important step in understanding who the key stakeholders are, which expertise they have, and where and how they can contribute to the project. The objective of a mapping exercise is to ensure that potential external experts who might have an interest or a stake in the project's results have been identified.

The purpose of this stakeholder mapping was to make a logical categorization of stakeholders which require adapted approaches to engagement within TWINNEDbySTARS, and this activity is to ensure that, as far as possible, all relevant stakeholders are identified and contacted.

Figure 6: Responsibilities within the stakeholder identification process. Source: CMC own elaboration.

The stakeholder mapping process is an integral task of the TWINNEDbySTARS project in which all partners of the initiative are involved. Under the coordination of the CMC guiding the methodology to be followed and providing databases, the CETECIMA oversees carrying out the mapping task which is integrated in this deliverable. CE is also participating in this task, handling design and communication. They are responsible for defining, producing, and disseminating the necessary visual elements through the contact channels of the project, as well as the reception of the data from the surveys, taking care of the data management policy. All this under the vision and alignment with the co-creation processes which is being developed in WP2 and WP3 under the leadership of the TIDES Institute of the ULPGC, coordinator of the project and academic partner that provides the context and global perspective for the mapping, as well as the elaboration of the surveys and the development of the messages showing the benefits of being part of TWINNEDbySTARS.

The complete mapping which is integrated in this deliverable has the following phases:

- A. Definition of the scope and index of contents of the map: type of agents, competencies, capacities, nautical sectors where they operate, geographical scope of action, etc.
- B. Identification of stakeholders (initial list).
- C. Simplified Mapping (confirmed listing with partners) + partners sent invitational questionnaire to their own contacts.
- D. Collection of information about stakeholders (Excel form + some information sheet).
- E. First draft of the deliverable *Mapping of stakeholders in the quadruple helix*
- F. Review and input
- G. Validation

4.1 MAPPING METHODOLOGY

Generalities to consider when identifying stakeholders: (1) many stakeholder groups could be included in more than one category, as we have seen in figure 2, these entities could be considered in the 'overlaps' areas between the circles; (2) a stakeholder map is not analytically exhaustive, but a tool that illustrates the range of stakeholders and helps to develop the engagement plan; (3) it is important not to exclude any stakeholder during this identification phase, even if relations with them are not good, we believe they will be against the actions or feel unwilling to commit themselves; (4) the stakeholder map will evolve as the engagement process goes on and we learn more about our stakeholders, this is why it is an iterative process throughout the project; and (5) as we engage with stakeholders we should also ask them who else they think we should engage with.

The identification of stakeholders has focused on entities that meet the following requirements:

- **Territorial:** Supra-regional, regional, and insular entities based in the ORs (Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, and Martinique) of the Atlantic, and national, European, and international entities relevant to the theme of the TWINNEDbySTARS project.
- **Thematic:** That offer support services for nautical and tourism activities (marine activities, blue tourism, services to recreational and sport boats, astronomical observation, specialized tourist services, tourism diversification, promotion of cooperation in the marine-maritime field, etc.)
- **Sectorial:** Nautical in general or specialized in a specific one (marinas, tourism promotion, astronomical observation, sustainable tourism, etc.)
- **Type of entity:** Any type of entity: public or private, and legal personality (organizations, associations, foundations, commercial companies, etc.). The quadruple helix group to which the entity belongs is indicated.

The identification of stakeholders has been performed based on the experience of the project partners and considering the actors of the quadruple helix. related to the ORs involved (Canary Islands – CA; Madeira – MAD; Azores – AZ; and Martinique – MAR), the countries to which they

belong (ES, PT, FR) and the European (EU) or international level (IN), under the following categories:

- Academia (science stakeholders, research community, researchers, PhD students)
- Government (policy, and decision-makers, public administrations, authorities)
- Citizens or civil society (societal actors)
- Industry (nautical value and supply chain, as well as other representatives of active and experiential travel sector)

A description of the targeted stakeholder groups of TWINNEDbySTARS is provided below:

Table 8.: Stakeholder groups description.

Stakeholder groups	Description
<p>Government (Public administrations, authorities)</p> <p>Group 1</p>	<p>Government or public institutions and the entire public administration are included in this category; however, we mainly refer to organisations at regional, national, and European level on tourism and on destination marketing.</p> <p>Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted. At EU level several Directorates-General will be reached (GROW, MARE), the JRC, the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group and UNWTO.</p>
<p>Industry</p> <p>Group 2</p>	<p>This category of stakeholders is one of the most important for TWINNEDbySTARS and includes both large and small companies, clusters, sectoral associations, business federations, investors and, in general, the entire private sector.</p> <p>As this is the most extensive section, a dedicated table (table 3) has been prepared which includes the types of entities to be included in the group.</p>
<p>Academia (Research education)</p> <p>Group 3</p>	<p>Also called science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to tourism. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and PhD scientists working on universities, research centres, think tanks and other scientific and technological organizations, also tourism schools and VET and high schools.</p> <p>The academia category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.</p>
<p>Citizens or civil society (NGOs)</p> <p>Group 4</p>	<p>This category includes citizens and associations such as NGOs, trade unions, professional associations, sports associations, sailors, and costumer’s associations, etc.</p>

4.2 IDENTIFICATION OF STAKEHOLDERS

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), a stakeholder is “a person or an organisation that has a legitimate interest in a project or entity or would be affected by a particular action or policy” (Parry et al., 2007). With this definition, everyone involved in the project can be considered a stakeholder, including the project partners. However, when we refer to consortium members, we will generally use the term “project partner” or “consortium partners”, while stakeholder will be reserved for entities which are external to the consortium.

For the project, the most important stakeholders, are the business entities, so the objective is to involve them at the highest level of integration. To define the entities that are part of the industry category, we have based our classification on the European NACE Rev.2 distribution used by (1) the Spanish National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN) and the Complutense University of Madrid (UCM) in the study *Impacto Económico de la Náutica de Recreo*, (2) the categorisation described in the European IMPACTOUR project, (3) as well as the previous work carried out in the initiative financed by the INTERREG MAC programme called SMART BLUEF (MAC 2/2.3d/355), in which several of the TWINNEDbySTARS partners took part:

Table 9: Entities that are part of the industry category.

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
Ports and marinas	Private Nautical port managers Port services concessions
Services to recreational and sport boats	Repair and maintenance workshops Mechanics Radio electronics Nautical refrigeration Dry docks and winter storage Fuel supply Inspection
Manufacture and sale and purchase of recreational and sport vessels	Boat manufacturing Boat distributors Official services Accessories and supplies
Charter and maritime excursions	Nautical charter Maritime excursions Whale watching Fishing tourism and marine tourism
Coastal tourism and water	Scuba diving

SUBSECTOR	SEGMENT
sports activities	Snorkelling Freediving Open water swimming Sailing / foil sports: surfing, windsurfing, kitesurfing, and similar Light boat activities: rowing, canoeing, and kayaking
Services to coastal tourism and water sports activities	Sale and/or rental of equipment accessories for sailing, surfing, windsurfing, and kitesurfing activities Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for rowing, canoeing and kayaking activities. Sale and/or rental of accessories and equipment for recreational underwater activities: scuba diving and snorkelling.
Nautical training and qualifications	Academies Clubs Sport schools
Commercial services	Tour Operators Travel agencies
Investors	Investors
Active and experiential tourism	Active tourism SMEs Experiential travel SMEs
Business associations	Tourism and maritime clusters Tourism associations Regional business federations Chambers of commerce
Investors	Investors
Media	Regional, national, and European media Digital media

For the elaboration of the TWINNEDbySTARS stakeholder database the partners were asked to explore among their contacts to identify those who could be involved in the project as a stakeholder. To comply with GDPR regulations, the next step was for each partner to send an email to these pre-selected contacts with information about the project including the benefits of participating in TWINNEDbySTARS and to complete a simple survey agreeing to be contacted at

later stages of the project. Similarly, for stakeholder mapping, the project partners were asked to research various regional databases mainly for the detection of business associations, companies, and civil society. All this information will be included in an Excel file which also contains the contact details and the categorisation of the stakeholder according to 4 main groups (government, academia, industry, and civil society).

The process of stakeholder identification and mapping is an iterative and continuous process throughout the life of the project. Furthermore, if it is detected that there is a significant lack of participation of representatives of any group and/or region, the efforts of the partners will be focused on bridging this gap, and project partners will have the opportunity to propose new contacts at various stages of the project.

The full list of variables recorded for each stakeholder are listed below. The rich detail in the stakeholder pool will facilitate efficient targeting of stakeholders for the appropriate stakeholder engagement context.

- Region / Island
- Name of the entity
- Sector Quadruple Helix / Subsector
- Contact person
 - Direct email
 - General email
 - Phone number
 - Web / social media
- Other (observations etc.)
- Partner in contact
- Previous project

In addition, this deliverable has in Annex 1 a detailed fact sheet for the most relevant stakeholders, which includes only public data.

Table 10: Fact sheet template for the most relevant stakeholders.

Name of the entity		Logo	
Business name			
Entity Type			
Sector of quadruple helix	Group 1 / Group 2 / Group 3 / Group 4		
Type of activity / services			
Other relevant information			
Contact Details*	Address		

Informational Resources	Phone number		
	Mail		
	Web		
	Social media	Facebook	
		Instagram	
		Twitter	
		LinkedIn	

**Contact details with public access, complying with data protection regulations.*

Finally, we then have two main databases linked to stakeholder mapping: (1) an excel table of mapping entities in which only public data will be included and (2) an excel table with the data of those entities/individuals who have responded to the EU survey and have accepted to be contacted in later phases of the project. These two databases are available to all project partners in the internal document repository.

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS

To approach the analysis and visualization of the data, it was decided to conduct a comprehensive mapping based on a detailed study of the Excel document containing the stakeholder information. This mapping focused on three key values: region, island and quadruple helix sector, selected for their relevance to provide a meaningful and manageable view of the data.

Segmentation by region allows for the identification and comparison of common characteristics across geographies. The inclusion of island value facilitates more detailed analysis within each region, especially in island contexts with particular economic dynamics. The categorization by sector of the quadruple helix, which includes academia, industry, government and civil society, is crucial to understand the interactions in the economic ecosystem that concerns us, which is amply explained in the previous sections of this document.

With these values, both global and region-specific infographics were produced, providing a general and detailed overview. This makes it easier to understand complex data, identify patterns and trends, and make informed decisions. This visual approach enhances communication of findings to various stakeholders and supports effective strategic planning.

In this regard, we can highlight the following information:

Figure 7: Infographic with data from the four regions. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.

The image illustrates the significant diversity in the distribution of entities in the quadruple helix (business sector, NGOs, public administration and research and education institutions) between the island regions of Martinique, Madeira, the Azores and the Canary Islands. The differences in the amount of data collected in each area are mainly due to demographic and economic variations between these regions.

The Canary Islands stand out for having a greater amount of data collected in all the sectors analysed. With a population of more than 2 million inhabitants and an annual influx of more than 13 million tourists, this region has a more robust and diversified economic infrastructure. This economic dynamism is reflected in the number of industrial and business entities, NGOs, public administration bodies and research and educational institutions present in the Canary Islands, surpassing the other regions in all these aspects.

In contrast, Martinique, Madeira and the Azores, with significantly smaller populations (approximately 350,000 in Martinique and 250,000 in Madeira and the Azores), and reduced tourism flows compared to the Canary Islands, show a smaller number of entities in the same sectors. This lower economic and social activity in these regions translates into a relatively reduced data collection effort.

The pie chart in the Figure 7 highlights this disparity: the Canary Islands account for 86.3% of the total number of entities, while Martinique, Azores and Madeira represent only 7%, 3.8% and 2.9% respectively. This difference in the concentration of entities reflects how the demographic characteristics and economic dynamism of each region influence the amount of data collected. In short, the Figure 7 highlights the direct impact of these factors on the breadth and depth of information available on each region.

Figure 8: Infographic with data on the Canary Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.

Tourism in the Canary Islands is one of the fundamental pillars of its economy, attracting millions of visitors each year thanks to its warm climate, varied landscapes, and diverse cultural and leisure offer. This sector represents a significant part of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the archipelago and generates employment both directly and indirectly. The well-developed tourism infrastructure, ranging from hotel complexes to transportation services and recreational activities, has made the Canary Islands a world-class destination.

Within this general context, coastal and maritime tourism has a special relevance in the Canary Islands. This type of tourism focuses on the use of natural and marine resources, offering experiences ranging from diving and sport fishing to sailing and whale watching. The geographical position of the islands and the quality of their waters make this sector a crucial

component of what is called the Blue Economy, which not only contributes significantly to the regional GDP, but also focuses on sustainability and protection of the marine environment.

The **Barometer of the Blue Economy in the Canary Islands 2023** developed by CETECIMA highlights the pivotal role of nautical tourism within the Blue Economy. The report indicates that the Blue Economy contributes significantly to the Canary Islands, with sectors such as nautical tourism experiencing substantial growth. Specifically, the nautical tourism sector is highlighted for its vibrant activities in marinas, the increase in boat charters, and water sports, all of which have shown a robust recovery post-pandemic. This sector not only supports the overall economic framework but also emphasizes the importance of continuous investment in marine infrastructure to sustain this growth. The report underscores that these activities are crucial for the diversification of the Canary Islands' economy, creating jobs and enhancing the region's attractiveness as a prime destination for maritime tourism.

As for the image, it offers a detailed view of the distribution of entities related to industry and business, NGOs, public administration, and the research and education sector in the Canary Islands. There are **1.337 entities**, of which the majority (1.221) are linked to industry and business. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) account for 89 entities, public administration for 16, and the research and education sector for 11.

Tenerife and Gran Canaria, as the main economic and tourist centres of the archipelago, concentrate most of these entities with 494 and 320 respectively. Fuerteventura and Lanzarote also stand out with 220 and 164 entities, reflecting their importance within the tourism sector. The smaller islands, such as La Palma, La Gomera, El Hierro and La Graciosa have a smaller presence of entities (82, 60, 40 and 4 respectively), but they continue to be essential in the regional economic panorama, contributing to the sustainability and diversification of the Canary Islands economy.

Figure 9: Infographic with data on the Martinique island. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.

Martinique, a Caribbean island territory and overseas region of France, has tourism as one of the cornerstones of its economy, accounting for approximately **10% of the island's Gross Domestic Product (GDP)**, according to official data from the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE). This sector is a key source of employment and economic development, with a high dependence on coastal and maritime tourism due to the geographical characteristics of the island. Martinique has more than **350 km of coastline** and is famous for its beaches, coral reefs and waters ideal for sailing and diving, making it a favourite destination in the Caribbean. This type of tourism attracts a significant number of international visitors each year, especially from Europe, making a crucial contribution to the local economy.

Furthermore, in addition to the significant assets in traditional tourism (green tourism, gastronomic tourism, memorial tourism, scientific tourism...), the recent inscription of the Northern Pitons, forests and Mount Pelée as a UNESCO heritage site could further enhance the value of the destination. The challenge is to create a combined destination based on natural, scientific, memorial and heritage.

The Martinique snapshot provides a detailed overview of the **108 entities** operating on the island in key sectors such as NGOs, industry and business, public administration, and research and education. Industry and business lead the representation with 60 entities, suggesting an active business ecosystem, especially in areas related to tourism and complementary services. NGOs,

with 34 entities, is the second most represented, reflecting a strong commitment to environmental protection and social development, also linked to the number of clubs and associations for the development of sea sports, crucial for sustainable tourism.

Public administration has 8 entities, while the research and education sector are composed of 6 entities. Although fewer in number, these sectors are fundamental to the regulation and strategic planning of tourism and other economic sectors, ensuring that tourism growth is balanced with the preservation of the natural environment and local culture.

Figure 10: Infographic with data on the Azores Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.

The Azores archipelago, an autonomous region of Portugal located in the Atlantic, is known for its unique volcanic landscape and biodiversity, which has made tourism a vital sector for its economy. According to official data, tourism accounts for approximately **12% of the Azores Gross Domestic Product (GDP)**. Coastal and maritime tourism is one of the most important pillars due to the exceptional natural conditions of the islands, which attract visitors interested in activities such as whale watching, sport fishing, diving and sailing. The Azores have positioned themselves as one of the best destinations worldwide for whale watching, an activity that generates a significant economic impact and attracts tourists from all over the world. In addition, the region

has been recognized for its commitment to sustainability, being a model of responsible tourism that seeks to preserve its valuable natural environment for future generations.

The image analysis on the Azores reveals that the archipelago has **59** operating **entities** in various sectors. Industry and business is the predominant sector, with 46 entities, reflecting the importance of the private sector, particularly in the areas of services and tourism.

The research and education sector is represented by 9 entities, underscoring the focus on innovation and sustainability, essential for the future development of tourism in the islands. The public administration, with 3 entities, plays a crucial role in regulating and supporting economic development. Only one NGO is included, but there are relevant international organisations in the islands, especially those linked to environmental protection, although they are not included in this list.

In terms of geographical distribution, the islands of São Miguel and Faial concentrate the largest number of entities, with 27 and 12 respectively. These islands, which are the most developed in terms of tourism infrastructure and services, lead the economic activity in the archipelago, especially in terms of coastal and maritime tourism. Pico and Terceira have a smaller number of entities (9 and 7 respectively), but are still important for the local economy, with a focus on niche markets such as adventure tourism and scientific research.

This dataset reflects the economic structure of the Azores, where tourism, supported by a dynamic private sector and a strong focus on research and education, plays a crucial role in the regional economy.

Figure 11: Infographic with data on the Madeira Islands. Source CETECIMA own elaboration.

Madeira, also a Portuguese archipelago located in the Atlantic, is widely recognized for its tourist attraction, driven by its subtropical climate, mountainous landscapes and rugged coastline. Tourism is one of Madeira's main economic drivers, contributing significantly to its Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Coastal and maritime tourism, in particular, plays an essential role due to the unique geographical characteristics of the region, which make it ideal for activities such as sailing, whale watching, diving and other water sports. The luxury marina in Funchal and Madeira's popularity as a departure point for international cruises further reinforce the relevance of maritime tourism in the local economy. These activities not only attract numerous international tourists, but are also fundamental to Madeira's economic growth, fostering job creation and investment in tourism infrastructure.

As for the data presented in the image, Madeira has 46 entities active in several key sectors. Industry and business dominate with 38 entities, underlining the crucial role of the private sector in the local economy, especially in the field of tourism and related services.

The public administration sector is represented by 4 entities, indicating a governmental structure that, although compact, is significant in terms of regulation and support for sustainable

development. In addition, the research and education sector has 3 entities, highlighting the importance of innovation and training in supporting sustainable tourism.

Finally, 1 NGO is registered in Madeira, reflecting a smaller presence of non-governmental organizations compared to other sectors, although it still plays an important role in promoting sustainability and conservation of the natural environment, vital aspects to maintain Madeira as an attractive tourist destination in the long term.

These data show that tourism, especially coastal and maritime tourism, is a centrepiece of Madeira's economy, supported by a robust private sector that leads the development of tourism services and infrastructure. The public administration, although with a smaller representation, plays a key role in regulating and promoting sustainable development, ensuring that economic growth goes hand in hand with the preservation of the natural environment. In addition, the presence of entities dedicated to research and education underlines the region's commitment to innovation and training, essential to maintain Madeira as a competitive and sustainable destination in the long term. Overall, Madeira continues to position itself as a global tourist destination of reference, adapting to new market demands while protecting and valuing its natural and cultural wealth.

REFERENCES

Active tourism activities registered in the General Tourist Register of the Canary Islands. <https://datos.gob.es/es/catalogo/a05003638-actividades-de-turismo-activo-inscritas-en-el-registro-general-turistico-de-canarias>

ATLAZUL "Impulso de la Alianza Litoral Atlántica para el Crecimiento Azul". <https://atlazul.eu/>

CETECIMA. (2023). *Barometer of the Blue Economy in the Canary Islands 2023*. Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas (CETECIMA). <https://www.cetecima.es>.

Conference of Peripheral Maritime Regions (CPMR) Atlantic arc commission. <https://cpmr-atlantic.org/>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs, (2022). Transition pathway for tourism, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-statistical-reports/w/ks-ft-22-011>

European Commission, EUROSTAT (2023). Tourism Satellite Accounts in Europe 2023 edition. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2873/344425>

European Commission, Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries, Joint Research Centre, Borriello, A., Calvo Santos, A., Codina López, L. et al., The EU blue economy report 2024, Publications Office of the European Union, 2024, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2771/186064>

European Commission. BRUSSELS DECLARATION ON A EUROPEAN NETWORK OF DESTINATIONS OF EXCELLENCE FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM. Ares(2015)5822556 - 14/12/2015. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/tourism/awards-and-outreach-activities/eden_en

European Marine Board (EMB). <https://www.marineboard.eu/>

European Network of Maritime Clusters (ENMC). <https://www.enmc.eu/>

García Álvarez, J.; Aliaga de Miguel, H.; Charouni, L (2021), Stakeholders' engagement plan. IMPACTOUR project Deliverable 3.2. <https://www.impactour.eu/system/files/2021-11/D3.2%20-%20IMPACTOUR%20Stakeholders%27%20Engagement%20Plan%20-%20vFinal.pdf>

Governo dos Açores. (2023). Relatório de Atividades Turísticas nos Açores. Direção Regional do Turismo. <https://www.azores.gov.pt>.

Guadeloupe Maritime Cluster (CMG). <https://www.cluster-maritime-guadeloupe.fr/>

Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques (INSEE). (2023). *Economic Indicators for Martinique*. <https://www.insee.fr/fr/statistiques>.

Journal-officiel.gouv.fr. Associations, fondations et fonds de dotation Organisations syndicales et professionnelles Bulletin des annonces légales obligatoires. <https://www.journal-officiel.gouv.fr/pages/associations-recherche/>

List of vessels licensed for the activity of whale watching for tourism purposes. https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/turismo/dir_gral_ordenacion_promocion/observacion_cet_aceos/

Martinique Maritime Cluster. <https://www.cluster-maritime-martinique.org/>

Molina M. & Bueno, E. (2018). Diagnóstico del Subsector de la Náutica y sus capacidades. Deliverable of the SMARTBLUE and NAUTICOM projects.

NAUTICOM project (MAC/2.3d/158), from INTERREG MAC Program, cofounded by FEDER funds. Website: <https://www.proyectonauticom.com/>

Novales, A. et al (2018). Impacto Económico de la Náutica de Recreo. Asociación Nacional de Empresas Náuticas (ANEN) y Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM). https://www.ucm.es/data/cont/media/www/pag-36703/FullReportICAE_ANEN.pdf

Ocean Panel Initiative. <https://oceanpanel.org/>

Parry, M.L., et al., Eds. (2007) Climate Change 2007: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability, Contribution of Working Group II to the Fourth Assessment Report of IPCC, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge. https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/2018/03/ar4_wg2_full_report.pdf

Pole Mer Bretagne Atlantique. <https://www.pole-mer-bretagne-atlantique.com/>

Quesada, M. et al (2024). D1.2 Stakeholder Engagement Plan. TWINNEDbySTARS project (EMFAF-2023-PIA-FLAGSHIP-5-OR) co-funded by the European Union. <https://twinnedbystars.eu/>

Red de Cruceros Costeros y Fluviales de los Destinos Náuticos Sostenibles de España (Red CCF). <https://redccf.es/>

Regional Directorate of Statistics of Madeira. (2023). *Tourism Statistics in Madeira.* <https://estatistica.madeira.gov.pt>

Register of Associations of the Canary Islands. <https://www3.gobiernodecanarias.org/entidadesjuridicas/asociaciones/>

Register of Canary Islands Associations accredited to receive volunteers. <https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/derechossociales/voluntariado/>

SEAStarlight "Unidos por la mar, hermanos por las estrellas". <https://www.seastarlight.com/>

SMART BLUEF project (MAC 2/2.3d/355), from INTERREG MAC Program, cofounded by FEDER funds. Website: <https://www.smartblueproject.com/>

Yen E. Lam-González, Carmelo J. León, Javier de León (2019). Assessing the effects of the climatic satisfaction on nautical tourists' on-site activities and expenditure decisions, *Journal of Destination Marketing & Management*, Volume 14, 100372, ISSN 2212-571X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jdmm.2019.100372>.

ANNEX 1: FACTSHEETS

The selection of the entities included in this annex has been the result of an exhaustive process combining strategic and methodological criteria, ensuring that only those with the greatest potential to contribute to the success of the TWINNEDbySTARS project are included. This process involved the identification of key actors at various geographical scales, from international organizations to local entities in the Atlantic outermost regions, such as the Canary Islands, Madeira, Azores and Martinique.

To carry out this selection, relevance criteria were established that included impact at the international and European level, prioritizing those entities with significant influence on policies and practices in the maritime tourism and blue economy sectors. At the regional and national level, the focus was on entities that act as central nodes within their local ecosystems, playing a crucial role in the economic and sustainable development of their territories. In addition, a balanced representation of different sectors and functions within the blue economy was sought, including research, government, industry and tourism, to ensure a complete coverage of the marine and coastal tourism value chain.

Initial identification of entities was based on consultation and analysis of regional and national databases, complemented by information from secondary sources such as reports and studies. Collaboration with project partners was essential to validate and fine-tune the selection, drawing on their local knowledge and experience to ensure that the chosen entities had a proven track record of collaboration and innovative capacity. In addition, priority was given to those entities and companies that directly collaborated and subscribed to the project, thus ensuring their active engagement in the project's activities and objectives.

The result of this process is a set of fact sheets that not only identify key players within the maritime and coastal tourism ecosystem, but also provide a solid basis for future collaborations and synergies within the TWINNEDbySTARS project. These entities represent a strategic combination of capabilities and resources that together will drive the success and sustainability of the project's initiatives.

ENTITY INFORMATION SHEET

TERRITORIAL SCOPE

Azores

Madeira

Canary

Martinique

TYPE OF AGENT

Academia
(Research & education)

Group 3

Government (Public administrations, authorities)

Group 1

Industry
Group 2

Citizens or civil society (NGOs)

Group 4

INTERNATIONAL, EUROPE and NATIONAL

Business name	International Council of Marine Industry Associations - ICOMIA	Logo	
Company name	International Council of Marine Industry Associations - ICOMIA		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	International		
Type of service	<p>ICOMIA is an international non-profit organization that provides services to the recreational boating industry.</p> <p>Its aim is to help national nautical industry associations grow by promoting recreational sailing and highlighting ways of getting more people to take part.</p> <p>We also exert pressure on national governments and international organizations such as the European Commission, the International Maritime Organization and the United States Environmental Protection Agency to improve navigation safety, protect the environment and promote international trade.</p>		
Skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting the industry: Supporting, promoting and connecting the industry through conferences, events and networks, as well as regular newsletters and discussion forums. • Host groups and committees: Organize various groups and committees covering a wide range of industry topics and areas of interest. • Providing technical guidance: Providing guidance and technical support covering a variety of disciplines, from engines to chemical products. • Collect data, statistics and trends: Collect data, statistics and trends from all member countries. They are published in their annual statistical report. • Stock market intelligence: Share market intelligence with your members to help them better understand their markets and grow their businesses. • Advice on compliance and safety: Provide advice to its members to help them keep abreast of changes in compliance and safety legislation. <p>Some of the areas of interest in which they work are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Marinas - Superyachts - Superyates - Sustainability - Market Intelligence - Marin Engines (IMEC) - Management of biofouling and chemical products - Coatings 		
Capabilities	They directly support the development of ISO standards for the construction of boats and marine equipment, in order to guarantee compliance with strict standards when establishing the criteria for the construction of safe boats and equipment. ICOMIA		

	promotes sailing as a fun activity within everyone's reach. The growth of the nautical industry and its accessibility are integrated into all aspects of ICOMIA's work.		
Contact details	Direction	International Council of Maritime Industry Associations, Brigada, Pironlaan, 132 - B-1080, Bruselas, Belgium	
	Telephone	00 44 1932 509 686	
	Mail	Joe Lynch - Executive Director: joe@icomia.com Patrick Hemp - Technical Director: patrick@icomia.com	
Information resources	Web	https://www.icomia.org	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ICOMIA
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/FollowICOMIA
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/icomia/

Business name	World Tourism Organization - UNWTO	Logo	
Company name	World Tourism Organization - UNWTO		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	International		
Type of service	<p>The World Tourism Organization (UN Tourism) is the United Nations agency responsible for promoting responsible, sustainable and universally accessible tourism.</p> <p>Its main areas of activity are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainable development • Competitiveness • Innovation, investment and digital transformation • Ethics, culture and social responsibility • Technical cooperation • Statistics • Academics and training 		
Skills	<p>The organization's work is based on five distinct pillars:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Making tourism smarter, boosting innovation and leading the sector's digital transformation. 2. Make tourism more competitive at all levels by promoting investment and entrepreneurship. 3. Create more and better jobs and offer relevant training. 4. Reforming resilience and promoting safe and smooth travel. 5. Harness the unique potential of tourism to protect cultural and natural heritage and support communities in both economic and social terms. 		
Capabilities	<p>As a leading international organization in the field of tourism, UN Tourism promotes tourism as a driver of economic growth, inclusive development and environmental sustainability and offers leadership and support to the sector in advancing tourism knowledge and policies around the world.</p> <p>The organization supports the application of the World Code of Ethics for Tourism, in order to maximize the socio-economic contribution of tourism and at the same time minimize the possible negative impacts it could have and is committed to promoting tourism as an instrument for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with a view to reducing poverty and promoting sustainable development worldwide.</p> <p>It also generates knowledge about markets, promotes policies and instruments for competitive and sustainable tourism, promotes tourism education and training, and works to make tourism an effective development tool through technical assistance projects in more than 100 countries around the world.</p>		

	The organization is made up of 160 Member States, 6 Associate Members and more than 500 Affiliate Members representing the private sector, educational institutions, tourism associations and local tourism authorities.			
Contact details	Direction	Calle Poeta Joan Maragall, 42 - 28020 - Madrid - Spain		
	Telephone	(+34) 91 567 81 00		
	Mail	info@unwto.org		
Information resources	Web	https://www.unwto.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/WorldTourismOrganization	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/unwto/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/unwto	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/unwto-world-tourism-organization/	

Business name	Responsible Tourism Institute (RTI)	Logo	RESPONSIBLE TOURISM INSTITUTE
Company name	Responsible Tourism Institute (RTI)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	International		
Type of service	<p>The Responsible Tourism Institute (RTI) is an international non-profit NGO, in the form of an association, which promotes responsible tourism at an international level, helping all those involved in the tourism sector to develop a new way of traveling and getting to know the planet.</p> <p>The functioning of the organization is based on: the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the Responsible Tourism System (RTS), which consists of an integral methodology of sustainability, competitiveness, quality, differentiation, authenticity and satisfaction which, through the "Biosphere Circle" label, measures the sustainability of the 17ODS and climate change with the aim of functioning as a tool for continuous improvement and thus recognizing this commitment and commitment of tourist destinations, their companies and services. • Organization of summits and events, with which a double objective is pursued: to reach a consensus on the optimal criteria and methodologies for measuring the contribution of sustainable development objectives in tourism, and to raise awareness among decision-makers and the public in general regarding tourism's contribution to sustainability. • Implementation of online courses on sustainability, centred on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals. These courses aim to achieve truly global action through learning and on the basis that educators, policymakers, professionals and citizens need to make sustainability a reality in their communities and lifestyles. • Research and development of projects led by large groups of multidisciplinary specialists and international experts who work to add value to resources, projects and initiatives that strive for competitiveness through innovation, creativity and strategic planning in the service of sustainable tourism. • International cooperation, through a series of collaborations with international organizations with the aim of promoting cooperation within the framework of tourism sustainability. 		
Skills	<p>The organization aims to promote responsible tourism at an international level, helping all those involved in the tourism sector to develop a new way of travelling and getting to know our planet.</p> <p>Likewise, they collaborate with various associations of tourism entrepreneurs, as well as with governmental and non-governmental organizations, to carry out tourism activities and projects, located both in developed countries and in developing countries, where projects consistent with the principles of sustainable development are carried out.</p>		
Capabilities	Alliances and the search for synergies to pool efforts are the basis of the RTI's operation, where the participation of all the actors involved in tourism development is key to achieving integral sustainability.		

	<p>The structure seeks the joint participation and unity of the scientific field, government bodies, innovation management bodies, universities, tourist destinations, tour operators and booking sites, the media, responsible tourists and associations, among others.</p> <p>They work in responsible tourism, defining objectives and setting guidelines for the future, through three internal bodies: the Board of Directors, the Scientific Board and the General Secretariat, which are fundamental pillars in their activity.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	-		
	Telephone	(+34) 902 929 928		
	Mail	info@biospheretourism.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.responsibletourism.institute.com		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/BiosphereResponsibleTourism	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/biospheretourism/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/RTI_Biosphere	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	International Astronomical Union - IAU	Logo	
Company name	IAU-UAI Secretariat		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	International		
Type of service	The International Astronomical Union was created with the mission of promoting and safeguarding astronomy and science in all its aspects, including research, communication, education and development, through international cooperation.		
Skills	<p>The IAU's key activity is the organization of scientific meetings.</p> <p>Each year, the IAU sponsors 9 international IAU symposia. The IAU Symposium Proceedings series is the flagship of IAU publications. Every three years, the IAU holds a General Assembly, which offers 6 IAU symposia, some 15 focus meetings, and individual scientific and commercial meetings of divisions, commissions, working groups and workshops. The proceedings are published in "Astronomy in Focus". The triennial reports of the divisions and commissions, as well as the reports of the business meetings, are published in the "Transactions of the IAU".</p> <p>Among the IAU's other tasks are the definition of fundamental physical and astronomical constants, the definition of an unambiguous astronomical nomenclature and the creation of informal debates on the possibilities of future large-scale international installations.</p> <p>In addition, the IAU acts as the international authority for assigning designations to celestial bodies and the characteristics of their surface.</p> <p>The IAU also works to promote research, education and public outreach activities in astronomy. These activities culminated in the organization of UNESCO's International Year of Astronomy in 2009, which reached more than 800 million people from 148 countries. As part of this effort, the IAU also created the Young Astronomers Workshop (a joint venture with the Norwegian Academy of Sciences and Letters), the Astronomy for Development Workshop (a joint venture with the National Research Foundation of South Africa where astronomy is used as a tool to stimulate capacity building) and the Astronomy Outreach Workshop (a joint venture with the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan). The IAU recently launched an international call to set up the Astronomy for Education Workshop. Regional nodes have also been set up in other countries and in 2015 it actively participated in the International Year of Light. The IAU also carries out joint educational activities in association with COSPAR and UNESCO.</p>		
Capabilities	<p>The IAU's individual members, structured in divisions, commissions and working groups, are professional astronomers from all over the world, with doctorates, who are active in professional research, education and dissemination in astronomy.</p> <p>The IAU has a total of 12,743 individual and youth members in 92 countries around the world. Of these countries, 85 are National Members. In addition, the IAU collaborates with various scientific organizations around the world. The IAU's long-term policy is defined by the General Assembly and implemented by the Executive Committee, while day-to-day</p>		

	operations are directed by IAU Officers. The focal point of its activities is the IAU Secretariat, housed at the Institut d'Astrophysique de Paris in France. The IAU's scientific and educational activities are organized by its 9 scientific divisions and, through them, its 39 specialized commissions covering the entire spectrum of astronomy, together with its 48 working groups.			
Contact details	Direction	98-bis Blvd Arago, F-75014 Paris		
	Telephone	(+33) 143 25 83 58		
	Mail	iauinfos@iap.fr		
Information resources	Web	https://www.iau.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/InternationalAstronomicalUnion	
		Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCc3I9q-N0NA05vIYeNMmtTw	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/IAU_org	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-international-astronomical-union/?viewAsMember=true	

Business name	European Boating Industry - EBI	Logo	
Company name	European Boating Industry - EBI		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	European		
Type of service	The European Boating Industry (EBI) is responsible for representing the recreational boating and nautical tourism industry in Europe.		
Skills	<p>EBI works on a number of key strategic areas for the future of the nautical industry, such as the European Green Deal, the Directive on recreational craft, the circular economy/vessels at the end of their useful life, tourism, VAT, professional qualifications, the blue economy, access to finance, trade policy, EU water legislation and other issues.</p> <p>The EBI's activity encompasses the following subsectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boat builders (speedboats, sailboats, yachts, watercraft and other pleasure craft). • Engine manufacturers. • Equipment manufacturers. • Repair and maintenance companies. • Boat distributors and importers. • Other related companies. 		
Capabilities	<p>The EBI is made up of the national associations representing the recreational sailing industry in Europe, as well as various individual organizations as sponsoring members.</p> <p>On European waters there are at least 6 million boats, 36 million regular boaters and more than 6,000 inland and coastal sports ports. The European recreational boating industry is made up of 32,000 companies (mostly small businesses) that directly employ more than 280,000 people.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Square de Meeûs, 35, 1000 Brussels, Belgium	
	Telephone	(+32) (0) 472 44 59 57	
	Mail	office@europeanboatingindustry.eu	
Information resources	Web	https://www.europeanboatingindustry.eu/	
	Social networks	Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FEBI_Boating
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-boating-industry/

Business name	EU Blue Economy Observatory		Logo	
Company name	European Commission			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Europe			
Type of service	The EU Blue Economy Observatory monitors and analyses economic activities related to the oceans, seas and coasts. The blue economy plays a crucial role in harnessing the potential of our oceans, while ensuring the health and long-term sustainability of the marine environment.			
Skills	<p>The EU Blue Economy Observatory carries out its activities in the following sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biotechnology. ▪ Coastal tourism. ▪ Desalination. ▪ Infrastructure and robotics. ▪ Living marine resources. ▪ Non-living marine resources. ▪ Marine renewable energy. ▪ Military Marina. ▪ Maritime transport. ▪ Ocean energy. ▪ Port activities. ▪ New construction and repair of ships. ▪ Research and innovation. 			
Capabilities	Among the main activities carried out by the EU Blue Economy Observatory are data visualization, the preparation and publication of sector reports and the analysis of subsidies and funding opportunities.			
Contact details	Direction	European Commission, Rue du Champ de Mars 21, 1050 Brussels, Belgium		
	Telephone	(+32) (2) 299 11 11		
	Mail	-		
Information resources	Web	https://blue-economy-observatory.ec.europa.eu/index_en?prefLang=es&etrans=es		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EUmaritimefish	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCT_QjivHLqE_2MFD_Aakw2tg	
		Twitter	https://x.com/EU_MARE	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/eu-business-showcase/	

Business name	NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF NAUTICAL COMPANIES		Logo	
Company name	NATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF NAUTICAL COMPANIES			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Español			
Type of service	<p>The National Association of Nautical Companies (ANEN) is the national association of the nautical sector in Spain, bringing together more than ninety percent of the industrial and business network of recreational boating, made up of companies, regional nautical associations, nautical-sports facilities and other sectoral groups.</p> <p>They offer services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technical advice. - Legal and tax advice. - International consultancy. - Promotion in international markets. 			
Skills	<p>ANEN's mission is to defend the rights of its members and the entire nautical sector before public administrations and to achieve the best legal, fiscal, labour and administrative environment that favours the development of business activity.</p> <p>Promoting recreational boating as a sustainable and quality tourism option and having a favourable impact on public opinion are also objectives of the Association's work.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>Since its foundation, ANEN has had an active presence as an interlocutor in the main national and international forums related to boating, managing to attract the support and involvement of government bodies and institutions related to the nautical sector.</p> <p>ANEN is a member of EBI (European Boating Industry) and ICOMIA, (International Council of Marine Industry Associations), the two most representative organizations of recreational boating in Europe and the world, respectively. He is also a member of the Spanish Maritime Cluster (CME) and the Spanish Arbitration Association.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Paseo de la Castellana, 121, escalera izquierda, 9º B. 28046 Madrid		
	Telephone	(+34) 913 532 994		
	Mail	anen@anen.es		
Information resources	Web	https://www.anen.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/anen.nautica/	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCVt3_aWjngVymPpqbuOD7Fg	

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fanen_nautica
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/anen-nautica/

Business name	Ministry of Industry and Tourism	Logo	MINISTERIO DE INDUSTRIA Y TURISMO	
Company name	Ministry of Industry and Tourism			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Nacional (Spain)			
Type of service	The Ministry of Industry and Tourism is the department of the General State Administration responsible for proposing and implementing government policy on industry and tourism.			
Skills	<p>The competencies of the Ministry of Industry and Tourism include, among other things:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strategy and industrial development. ▪ Promoting entrepreneurship. ▪ Support for small and medium-sized enterprises. ▪ The promotion and defence of industrial property. ▪ The formulation of tourism policy. ▪ Legislation on tourism and industry ▪ The economic and employment drive. <p>In addition, it exercises the powers and duties conferred on it by the legal system.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>The Ministry of Industry and Tourism is responsible for, among other things:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developing and applying industry and tourism standards and regulations. - Develop economic support programs for industrial and tourist companies. - Boosting sustainability and digitalization strategies. 			
Contact details	Direction	P. de la Castellana 160, C.P. 28046 Madrid		
	Telephone	(+34) 913 49 46 40		
	Mail	-		
Information resources	Web	https://www.mintur.gob.es/es-es/Paginas/index.aspx		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/minturgob/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/minturgob?lang=ca	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ministerio-industria-comercio-turismo/?originalSubdomain=es	

Business name	Portuguese Association of Recreational Ports – APPR	Logo	
Company name	Portuguese Association of Recreational Ports		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	National (Portugal, including Azores and Madeira)		
Type of service	The Asociación Portuguesa de Puertos de Recreo (APPR) is a private non-profit association whose aim is to bring together all the recreational ports and recreational port facilities in Portugal.		
Skills	<p>The APPR has competencies in the following ports and marinas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NORTH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Douro Marina - CENTER <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Port of Figueira da Foz ▪ Marina da Ribeira, Peniche - Fishing Dock - LISBON <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cascais Marina ▪ Oeiras marina ▪ APL Port of Lisbon Administration ▪ Alcântara Recreational Dock ▪ Belém Recreational Dock ▪ Bom Sucesso Recreational Dock ▪ Santo Amaro Recreational Dock ▪ Marina Parque das Nações ▪ Clube Naval de Sesimbra ▪ Fontainhas Recreational Dock - APSS ▪ Tróia Marina - ALENTEJO <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sines Recreational Port - ALGARVE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lagos Marina ▪ Portimão Marina ▪ Albufeira Marina ▪ Vilamoura Marina ▪ Guadiana Recreational Port - AZORES <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ponta Delgada ▪ Marina D'Angra ▪ Horta Marina ▪ Lajes das Flores Nautical Recreation Center ▪ Lajes do Pico Nautical Recreation Center ▪ Marina Vila do Porto ▪ Marina das Velas - WOOD <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Port of Calheta 		
Capabilities	The APPR is in charge of ensuring that a constant relationship is maintained between all the recreational ports and port facilities supported by the association, as well as studying all the issues that concern them, representing them before the Public Administration, transmitting all the information that concerns them, creating		

	a conciliation committee for the disputes that affect them and carrying out all the actions of collective interest useful to the activities of its members.		
Contact details	Direction	Sines Recreational Port, Avenida de Sines, Building of the Port Administration of Sines and Algarve, 7520-101 Sines	
	Telephone	(+351) 289 310 560	
	Mail	appr.direcao@gmail.com	
Information resources	Web	http://marinasdeportugal.pt/pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	-
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-
LinkedIn		-	

Business name	The Yacht Harbour Association (TYHA)		Logo	
Company name	The Yacht Harbour Association (TYHA)			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Its radius of action is specifically linked to the United Kingdom, but its certifications are worldwide.			
Type of service	The Yacht Harbour Association is established to develop the marina industry by specifically supporting marina members of British Marine and International Members. They help boat users find good quality marinas and help marina businesses improve their services and operate to high, modern standards.			
Skills	They offer expert advice in a range of issues, marketing & promotional tools, specific training for marina management and the opportunity to work with other businesses to find the best way to address problems. These services work together to save money and valuable time.			
Capabilities	The development of marina standards is at the heart of their work, this is supported and recognised through the Gold Anchor global marina accreditation scheme which TYHA are proud to administer and deliver.			
Contact details	Direction	Tagus House. 9 Ocean Way – Southampton. SO14 3TJ		
	Telephone	+44 (0) 1784 223817		
	Mail	hcloke@britishmarine.co.uk		
Information resources	Web	https://www.tyha.co.uk/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/the-yacht-harbour-association-limited		

Business name	Associação Automóvel de Portugal. Divisão Náutica – ACAP/APICAN		Logo	
Company name	Associação Automóvel de Portugal. Divisão Náutica – ACAP/APICAN			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Portugal			
Type of service	ACAP is a private business association that has represented the entire automotive sector for more than 100 years.			
Skills	The Nautical Division - APICAN represents companies that carry out the activities of manufacturer / importer / distributor of boats, manufacturer and/or importer / distributor of marine engines, manufacturer and/or importer / distributor of nautical accessories, marine electronics and the like, manager and/or concessionaire of recreational harbour facilities, nautical retail and maritime-tourism activities.			
Capabilities	-			
Contact details	Direction	Av. Torre de Belém, 29. 1400-342 Lisboa		
	Telephone	+351 213 035 300		
	Mail	mail@acap.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.acap.pt/pt/sector/68/nautica-apican		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/acap.oficial	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/acapoficial	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/acapoficial/	

Business name	Fédération française des ports de plaisance (FFPP)		Logo	
Company name	Fédération française des ports de plaisance (FFPP)			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	France			
Type of service	The Fédération Française des Ports de Plaisance (FFPP) is a non-profit-making organisation serving all the seaports, river ports and inland ports it groups together. It is made up of Regional Associations or Unions, Direct Members and Corresponding Members covering mainland France, Corsica, the French overseas departments, Lake Geneva and part of the Inland Waters.			
Skills	The FFPP is represented within the main institutional networks and maintains relations with the various Ministries, in order to respond as effectively as possible to the demands of its members. In addition to defending the interests of its members, the FFPP's vocation is to unite marinas, to initiate studies and exchanges in the technical, legal, fiscal and environmental fields, in particular with the European 'Clean Ports' Certification, and to train marina staff.			
Capabilities	The FFPP is involved in major initiatives like the 'Qualité Plaisance' - 'Qualité Tourisme' label, to improve understanding of the services offered by marinas to yachting customers. The FFPP works with the trade unions to manage the Collective Agreement for Marina Employees within the framework of the National Joint Committee.			
Contact details	Direction	17, rue Henri Bocquillon. 75015 Paris		
	Telephone	+33(0)143352626		
	Mail	contact@ffpp.fr		
Information resources	Web	http://www.ffports-plaisance.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/ffpp-f%C3%A9d%C3%A9ration-fran%C3%A7aise-des-ports-de-plaisance/	

CANARY ISLANDS

Business name	Canary Islands Agency for Research, Innovation and the Information Society (ACIISI)		Logo	Gobierno de Canarias Consejería de Universidades, Ciencia e Innovación y Cultura Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información
Company name	Canarian Agency for Research, Innovation and the Information Society			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	The Canarian Agency for Research, Innovation and the Information Society (ACIISI) is an agency of the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands that provides services to promote and coordinate research, innovation and digital transformation, collaborating closely with socio-economic sectors, universities and research centres.			
Skills	The ACIISI is the highest body in charge of carrying out responsibilities relating to public policies and programs in the field of research, scientific and technological development, business innovation and the development of telecommunications infrastructures and information society services for the Public Administration of the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands and the entities dependent on it. It also coordinates the administration in its assigned areas.			
Capabilities	ACIISI carries out the following functions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Management of European funds for scientific research, business innovation and the information society. - Promoting public policies on scientific research, business innovation and the information society. 			
Contact details	Direction	c/ León y Castillo, 200. Edf. Servicios Múltiples III Planta 6ª. 35071 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 45 83 35		
	Mail	conocimiento@gobiernodecanarias.org		
Information resources	Web	https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/conocimiento/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ACIISI/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/aciisi/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/agenciaiisi	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/agencia-canaria-de-investigaci%C3%B3n-innovaci%C3%B3n-y-sociedad-de-la-informaci%C3%B3n-aciisi-0b327521/	

Business name	University Institute of Social Research and Tourism - ULL		Logo	
Company name	-			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	The University Institute of Social Research and Tourism of the University of La Laguna is an interdisciplinary centre focused on research, innovation and development applied to social disciplines. It also serves as a place for teaching and specialization in various areas of knowledge and the social sciences.			
Skills	<p>The activity of the University Institute of Social Research and Tourism of the University of La Laguna focuses on the following areas of knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Social Anthropology ▪ Commercialization and Market Research ▪ Applied Economics ▪ Financial Economics and Accounting ▪ Nursing ▪ Fundamentals of Economic Analysis ▪ Human Geography ▪ Ancient History ▪ Business Organization ▪ Painting ▪ Sociology 			
Capabilities	<p>The scope of action of the University Institute of Social Research and Tourism of the University of La Laguna mainly covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research projects in basic and applied social sciences. ▪ Social innovation. ▪ R&D contracts. ▪ Postgraduate and specialized teaching in social sciences. 			
Contact details	Direction	Camino La Hornera, 37. Faculty of Law. Module D-02. Apartado 456. Postal code 38200. San Cristóbal de La Laguna. S/C of Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 31 73 06		
	Mail	istur@ull.es		
Information resources	Web	https://www.ull.es/institutos/instituto-universitario-de-investigacion-social-y-turismo/		
	Social networks	Twitter	https://twitter.com/istur_y?lang=es	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Astronomy and Astrophysics – ULL		Logo	
Company name	Department of Astronomy and Astrophysics of the University of La Laguna			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	Centre for research and teaching in astronomy and astrophysics at the University of La Laguna (ULL).			
Skills	<p>The activities of ULL's astronomy and astrophysics department are focused on the following areas of knowledge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Astronomy. ▪ Astrophysics. <p>The department is organized into the following research groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Astrophysics and Theoretical Cosmology – Solar Spectropolarimetry – Binary stars – Blue Masked Stars – Evolution of galaxies – Stellar populations in galaxies 			
Capabilities	<p>The activities of ULL's astronomy and astrophysics department are mainly based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research and scientific dissemination. ▪ Specialized teaching. 			
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Astrofísico Francisco Sánchez, s/n. Faculty of Sciences. Physics Section. Apartado 456. Postal code 38200. San Cristóbal de La Laguna. S/C of Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 31 81 22		
	Mail	dastrofi@ull.es		
Information resources	Web	https://www.ull.es/departamentos/astrofisica/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development – TIDES	Logo	
Company name	University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development – TIDES		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	<p>The Instituto Universitario de Turismo y Desarrollo Económico Sostenible (TIDES), part of the Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), is a research institute whose objectives are to develop excellent tourism research, generating and disseminating scientific knowledge, and integrating into international tourism excellence networks. On the other hand, it provides education and training and raises awareness for improving tourism development. It also applies the knowledge it generates to drive improvements in the economic, social and environmental development of tourist destinations.</p>		
Skills	<p>The TIDES University Institute is born with a vocation for international action, as a multidisciplinary entity for research, innovation and coordination, which provides spaces for the exchange of knowledge in the tourism sector, economics, the environment and, in general, sustainable development, generating benefits and solutions for socio-economic progress at local, regional and global levels.</p> <p>The activities of the TIDES University Institute are based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Cooperation for Sustainable Development – Tourism Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Digitalization – Business and Tourism Management – Territorial Tourism Strategy – Education and Society – Tourism product design laboratory – Marketing and Tourist Experiences – Quantitative Methods and Statistical Analysis – Transportation and Tourism 		
Capabilities	<p>The functions of the TIDES University Institute are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote, organize and plan research objectives in the various fields of tourism, economics, sustainable development and their applications. Carry out research activities in collaboration with other public or private entities. ▪ To disseminate and publicize research and studies, on its own initiative or in coordination with publishers, magazines, and other dissemination media, or through conferences, seminars, congresses, colloquia and meetings, both national and international. ▪ Establish permanent relationships with other institutions and research centres that focus their activity on the aforementioned field. Transfer and exchange research results and information with other entities, both public and private. ▪ Establish relationships with the private and public sectors in order to promote technical advice and promote the realization of coordinated projects. Promote the training and perfecting of specialized personnel for teaching and research in the aforementioned fields. ▪ Organize and promote study seminars, doctoral courses and other activities of a similar nature, in the areas of its research activity, as well as joint curricular programs with other Spanish and foreign universities and companies on the topics indicated. 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ To provide an appropriate means of attracting external funding to help finance research activities.▪ Serving as a focus for attracting national and foreign scientists of recognized prestige in topics related to tourism and sustainable development, who carry out stays at the Institute, providing the appropriate technological means for the completion of work in progress, for the initiation of new projects and for the planning of joint projects with institutions in other countries and with other Institutes, Centers and University Departments.	
Contact details	Direction	Calle Saulo Torón, 4, Módulo E, Planta 0, Derecha 35017, Las Palmas, Spain	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 45 49 60	
	Mail	tides@ulpgc.es	
Information resources	Web	https://tides.ulpgc.es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/institutotides
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FINSTITUTOTIDES
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/tides-instituto-de-turismo-y-desarrollo-econ-mico-sostenible	

Business name	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias - IAC	Logo	
Company name	Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	International		
Type of service	The Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) is a Spanish public research organization focused on providing and supporting state-of-the-art facilities to carry out frontier research in the sciences of the universe, guaranteeing the best natural, technological and logistical conditions, while fostering a fruitful framework for international collaboration.		
Skills	<p>The IAC has expertise in areas related to the study of space and terrestrial meteorology.</p> <p>The IAC's mission is to carry out and promote any type of astrophysical or related research, as well as to develop and transfer its technology, disseminate astronomical knowledge, collaborate in the specialized university teaching of astronomy and astrophysics and train and qualify scientific and technical personnel in all fields related to astrophysics, administer existing astronomical centres, observatories and facilities and those that will be created or incorporated into its administration in the future, as well as the facilities at its service; and foster relations with the national and international scientific community.</p>		
Capabilities	<p>Among the activities carried out at the IAC are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Analysis of light, radio and air pollution. ▪ Continuous monitoring of atmospheric parameters related to astronomical observations. ▪ Design, development or implementation of new instruments for the characterization of observatories. ▪ Leader in research into atmospheric optics and new techniques for characterizing sites for the installation of large telescopes. ▪ Participation and organization of international campaigns to characterize sites for future infrastructure. ▪ Publication of results in specialized forums. ▪ Coordinating institutional efforts to characterize and protect the sky, acting as an interlocutor in formal agreements with agencies or institutions. ▪ Participation in international initiatives and as a board member of committees related to astrophysics and related areas. ▪ Spreading knowledge to the general public to show the importance of knowing and protecting the sky. <p>In turn, the IAC manages the following infrastructures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Headquarters of the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC). – Space, Medical Technology and Large Telescopes Building (IACTEC) – La Palma Astrophysics Centre – Teide Observatory – Roque de los Muchachos Observatory. 		

Contact details	Direction	C/ Vía Láctea, s/n E-38205 La Laguna - Tenerife, España		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 605 200		
	Mail	secadm@iac.es		
Information resources	Web	https://www.iac.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/InstitutedeAstrofisica-deCanarias	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/iac_astrofisica/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/IAC_Astrofisica	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/instituto-de-astrof-sica-de-canarias/	

Business name	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias (CMC)		Logo	
Company name	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias (CMC)			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	<p>El Cluster Marítimo de Canarias (CMC) is a non-profit association whose objective is to promote the development and international competitiveness of the Canary Islands Maritime Marine Sector and to improve the business, economic and social network of the region through the integration, creation, strengthening and sustainability of companies and institutions within the value chain of the maritime marine sector, promoting their international presence and raising the technological and innovative level of all the agents involved, in line with development policies and social demands.</p>			
Skills	<p>CMC carries out its activities mainly in the following sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ship repair. - Maritime transport. - Port infrastructures and services. - Marine renewable energies. - Sports and leisure boating. - Fishing and aquaculture. 			
Capabilities	<p>The CMC's areas of activity are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Innovation. - Internationalization. - Communication and awareness. - Training. - Business consulting. 			
Contact details	Direction	Explanada Vapores Insulares, (CC El Muelle) Puerto de La Luz y de Las Palmas 35008 - Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 629 018 287		
	Mail	gerente@clustermc.es		
Information resources	Web	https://www.clustermc.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ClusterMaritimoCanarias	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/clustermaritimocanarias/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FCMaritimoC	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cluster-mar-timo-de-canarias/?originalSubdomain=es	

Business name	Marine Science Technology Center (CETECIMA)	Logo	
Company name	Marine Science Technology Center		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	Centro Tecnológico de Ciencias Marinas (CETECIMA) is a private, non-profit company that offers a wide range of transversal and sectoral services in the field of the blue economy, such as R&D&I project management, technical and economic project analysis and consulting services.		
Skills	<p>All of CETECIMA's activities are related to the different areas of the blue economy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fishing. ▪ Aquaculture. ▪ Ports and maritime transport. ▪ Ship repair. ▪ Sports and recreational boating. ▪ Marine renewable energies. ▪ Etc 		
Capabilities	<p>CETECIMA offers a wide range of specialized sectoral services to address the specific needs of various segments within the scope of the blue economy, for example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Design of contamination contingency plans. - Port water quality control. - Port waste management. - Work to minimize environmental impacts in boat and port maintenance activities. - Digitization and implementation of enabling digital technologies in shipyards and other port services - Health surveillance services for fish products. - Planning, management and monitoring of aquaculture crops. - Environmental surveillance plans. - Maritime and nautical safety work. - Modelling and design of marine renewable energy installations and multipurpose platforms. - Etc. 		
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Andrés Perdomo S/N, Planta baja, Oficinas 3 y 4 del Edificio de la Zona Franca de Las Palmas, C.P. 35008, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 70 73 37	
	Mail	cetecima@cetecima.com	
Information resources	Web	https://www.cetecima.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CETECIMA/
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@CENTROCETECIMA

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FCE%2FTECIMA
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cetecima/

Business name	Las Palmas Port Authority	Logo	
Company name	Port Authority of Las Palmas		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Provincial (Las Palmas)		
Type of service	La Autoridad Portuaria de Las Palmas is a public body dependent on the State Ports that offers multipurpose services, such as base services for national and international fishing fleets, fuel supply station services, container transfer services, port infrastructure operation and maintenance services, base services for international cruises and regattas, humanitarian aid distribution services, etc.		
Skills	<p>The Port Authorities have the following competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The provision of general services, as well as the management and control of port services to ensure that they are carried out under optimum conditions of efficiency, economy, productivity and safety, without prejudice to the competence of other bodies. ▪ The planning of the port service area and port uses, in coordination with the competent land-use and urban planning authorities. ▪ The planning, design, construction, maintenance and operation of the works and services of the port, and that of the maritime signposts they have commissioned, subject to the provisions of this law. ▪ The management of the public port and maritime signalling domain assigned to them. ▪ The optimization of economic management and the profitability of the assets and resources they have assigned. ▪ The organization and coordination of port traffic, both maritime and land. 		
Capabilities	The Port Authority oversees managing five general interest ports in the province of Las Palmas: Puerto de La Luz and Las Palmas, Arinaga and Salinetas (Gran Canaria); Puerto de Arrecife (Lanzarote) and Puerto del Rosario (Fuerteventura).		
Contact details	Direction	Tomás Quevedo Ramírez, s/n 35008 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria - Islas Canarias	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 214 400	
	Mail	operacioneslpa@palmasport.es	
Information resources	Web	https://www.palmasport.es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LasPalmasPorts/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/puertos_de_las_palmas/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FLasPalmasPorts

		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/autoridad-portuaria-de-las-palmas
--	--	----------	---

Business name	Puertos de Las Palmas Foundation		Logo	
Company name	Puertos de Las Palmas Foundation			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Provincial (Las Palmas)			
Type of service	The Port of Las Palmas Foundation is a communication tool that was created with the objectives of bringing the activity of the Port Authority of Las Palmas closer to the general public, promoting synergies between associations and companies that make up the community of the ports of general interest in the Province of Las Palmas, and providing cultural and social support to the port community of the ports of Las Palmas.			
Skills	<p>The lines of action carried out by the Puerto de Las Palmas Foundation are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural - Social and educational - Sports - Outdoor Promotion - Research and development (R+D) - Technological innovation (IT) - Environment and safety <p>With these lines of action, it is intended that the Foundation will serve as an integrating instrument of resources in training, culture, sport and the environment for the identity of the ports and especially in the external promotion of Canarian companies through the development of international commercial actions.</p>			
Capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Supporting, promoting and collaborating in sporting events. - Internationalization with African, Latin American and European ports. - Support for community interest initiatives, particularly in neighbourhoods linked to the port. 			
Contact details	Direction	Ramírez, Edificio Autoridad Portuaria de Las Palmas, Explanada Tomás Quevedo, s/n, planta baja, 35008, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 21 45 39		
	Mail	fundacion@palmasport.es		
Information resources	Web	https://fundacionpuertos.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fundacion.puertosdelaspalmas/	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@fundacionpuertosdelaspalmas	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FFundaPuertosLPA	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/fundaci%C3%B3n-puertos-de-las-palmas-4b549948/		

Business name	Santa Cruz de Tenerife Port Authority		Logo	
Company name	Santa Cruz de Tenerife Port Authority			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Provincial (Santa Cruz de Tenerife)			
Type of service	La Autoridad Portuaria de Santa Cruz de Tenerife is a public body dependent on the State Ports that offers multipurpose port services, such as practice services, mooring and unmooring services, ship repair services, cruise ship services, commercial fuel supply services, commercial bus supply services, commercial ship consignment services, etc.			
Skills	<p>Under the premise of carrying them out under optimum conditions of efficiency, economy, productivity and safety, the Santa Cruz de Tenerife Port Authority has a wide range of competencies, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Carrying out, authorizing and controlling maritime and land operations related to port traffic. - Management and general port services. - Promotion of industrial and commercial activities related to maritime and port traffic. - Optimization of economic management and planning of the port service area and port uses. - Control of cruises and scales. 			
Capabilities	The Santa Cruz de Tenerife Port Authority is one of the 28 members of the state port system and currently manages the ports of Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Santa Cruz de La Palma, Los Cristianos, San Sebastián de La Gomera and La Estaca.			
Contact details	Direction	Av. Francisco la Roche, 49, 38001, Santa Cruz de Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 605 426		
	Mail	secretaria@puertosdetenerife.org		
Information resources	Web	https://www.puertosdetenerife.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://es-es.facebook.com/PortsSCTenerife/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/tenerifeports/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/portssctenerife	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/puertosdetenerife/	

Business name	Canary Islands		Logo	
Company name	Canary Islands			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	Puertos Canarios is a public business entity attached to the Public Works Department of the Government of the Canary Islands that is responsible for managing general interest ports, port facilities, shelters and dikes, as well as sports ports that are operated on a concession basis.			
Skills	<p>Puertos Canarios is responsible for the planning, operation and management of the port system owned by the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands. Specifically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The realization, authorization, promotion and control of maritime and land operations related to port traffic. • The planning of the port service area in coordination with the administrations and bodies responsible for land use planning and town planning. • Planning, design, construction, maintenance and operation of works in the port service area. • The management of the public port domain assigned to it and that which could affect the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands. • The coordination of the operations of the different modes of transport in the port space. • The coordination and inspection of the operation of maritime-port facilities whose management has been delegated to other public bodies or entities. • Optimizing the economic management and profitability of its assets and resources. • Control, in this case, over the management and operation of the ports under its jurisdiction. 			
Capabilities	<p>Puertos Canarios is in charge of managing and administering the following infrastructures:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 16 general interest ports. – 14 concessioned sports ports. – 12 port facilities. 			
Contact details	Direction	C/ Luis Doreste Silva nº 2, 35004, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 828 181 140		
	Mail	info@puertoscanarios.es		
Information resources	Web	https://puertoscanarios.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EPPuertosCanarios	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/puertoscanarios/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FPuertosCanarios	
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/in/puertoscanarios?trk=public_profile_browsermap-profile	

Business name	Federación Provincial de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa del Metal y las Nuevas Tecnologías de Las Palmas – FEMEPA		Logo	
Company name	Federación Provincial de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa del Metal y las Nuevas Tecnologías de Las Palmas – FEMEPA			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Provincial (Las Palmas)			
Type of service	La Federación Provincial de la Pequeña y Mediana Empresa del Metal y Nuevas Tecnologías de Las Palmas (FEMEPA) is an independent, non-profit business organization that contributes to improving the competitiveness of small and medium-sized companies in the metal and new technology sector in the province of Las Palmas, promoting associationism and defending the interests of its members, providing exclusive and innovative services and improving people's skills and professional opportunities within the sector.			
Skills	<p>FEMEPA mainly carries out activities linked to it:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promotion of innovation. ▪ Training and employment. ▪ Internationalization ▪ Corporate social responsibility. ▪ Quality, prevention of labour risks and the environment. ▪ Legal services. 			
Capabilities	<p>FEMEPA has the necessary resources to carry out the following functions and services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Promotion and management of high quality and specialized projects linked to the metal sector and new technologies. – Consulting and technical workshop services. – Boosting actions that promote the transfer of technology and knowledge, and the dissemination of innovation. – Organization and management of training activities and courses. – Placement agency. 			
Contact details	Direction	C/ León y Castillo, 89 4ª planta, 35004 - Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 29 61 61		
	Mail	femepa@femepa.es		
Information resources	Web	https://femepa.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/FemepaLP	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/femepa_lp/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FFEMEPALP	

		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/femepa/
--	--	----------	---

Business name	Federación Provincial de Empresas del Metal y las Nuevas Tecnologías de Santa Cruz de Tenerife (FEMETE)	Logo	Femete <small>FEDERACIÓN PROVINCIAL DE EMPRESARIOS DEL METAL Y NUEVAS TECNOLOGÍAS DE SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE</small>
Company name	Federación Provincial de Empresas del Metal y las Nuevas Tecnologías de Santa Cruz de Tenerife (FEMETE)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Provincial (Tenerife)		
Type of service	<p>La Federación Provincial de Empresas del Metal y las Nuevas Tecnologías de Santa Cruz de Tenerife (FEMETE) is a business organization that represents, manages and defends the professional interests of its members, particularly in matters related to the Administration and other Public Institutions, as well as to Workers' Professional Organizations. It also promotes the economic and social development of the community, and participation in commercial companies. It also aims to develop a spirit of solidarity and collaboration among its members.</p>		
Skills	<p>FEMETE mainly carries out activities linked to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Labor, tax and accounting advice. ▪ Innovation. ▪ Legality. ▪ Labor and industrial safety. ▪ Aid and subsidies. ▪ Projects. ▪ Technical consultancies. 		
Capabilities	<p>FEMETE's mission is to provide services that help its member companies obtain the best advantages to increase the productivity and profitability of their businesses. To this end, among other things, the organization is responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To study, promote and manage the necessary measures for the better development of the economic and social activities of the province of Santa Cruz de Tenerife. ▪ Drawing up recommendations and principles on wage and collective-contractual policy. ▪ Establish and facilitate services of common interest to the components of the Federation. ▪ Fostering progress in business management techniques. ▪ Promote and foster relations with other professional organizations of similar nature and purpose. ▪ Administer the economic resources of the Federation and their application to its purposes and activities. ▪ Developing conciliatory arbitration and expertise actions in the event of conflicts of interest between its components. ▪ To ensure the professional prestige and dignity of all its members, preventing any unlawful or unfair competition in any of its forms. ▪ Enhance the image of the entrepreneur in the eyes of public opinion. ▪ Promote and collaborate in improving the performance and productivity of companies and in the training and social promotion of their workers. 		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Impartiality of training courses on the metal sector.▪ To train and guide members of the metal sector and the population in general towards employment and integration into the labor market.▪ Enhancing the operational capacity of its members.▪ Strengthening the economic development of the metal sector in the province of Tenerife.▪ To advise and support the activities of its members, fostering collaboration between them.	
Contact details	Direction	Calle Mazo, nº 5 y 7. San Cristóbal de La Laguna	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 296 700	
	Mail	femete@femete.es	
Information resources	Web	https://femete.com.es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://es-es.facebook.com/federacionfemete/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/femete1979/?hl=es
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Ffemete
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/femete/?originalSubdomain=es

Business name	Santa Cruz de Tenerife Chamber of Commerce	Logo	
Company name	Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Santa Cruz de Tenerife		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Provincial (Santa Cruz de Tenerife)		
Type of service	<p>The Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Santa Cruz de Tenerife is an institution that represents, promotes and defends the general interests of commerce, services, industry, navigation and the consolidation of the economic fabric of the province.</p> <p>To this end, the Chamber offers advisory and management services for business creation and entrepreneurship, training, employment, internationalization, innovation and improving competitiveness.</p>		
Skills	<p>Among the competencies of the Santa Cruz de Tenerife Chamber of Commerce are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issuing certificates of origin and other certificates related to national and international trade. • To collect mercantile customs and usages, as well as business practices and usages, and to issue certificates about their existence. • To be an advisory body to the Public Administrations for the development of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Develop activities to support and stimulate foreign trade. • Participate with the competent administrations in the organization of practical training in work centres, especially in the selection and validation of work centres and companies, in the appointment and training of student tutors and in the control and evaluation of program compliance. • To process, in the cases in which they are required by the General State Administration, public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as to manage public services related to them when their management corresponds to the State Administration. • Manage a public census of all companies, as well as their establishments, delegations and agencies based in its demarcation. • Acting from single business windows, when required to do so by the competent Public Administrations. • Collaborate with the Public Administrations in the administrative simplification of procedures for the start-up and development of economic and business activities, as well as in the improvement of economic and business regulation. • Promote actions aimed at increasing the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises and foster technological innovation and transfer to companies. • To promote and collaborate with public administrations in the implementation of the digital economy of companies. • If the European Union fund management authority deems it appropriate, the Chambers may participate in the management of European Union funds aimed at improving competitiveness in companies. • Propose to the Public Administrations as many reforms or measures as they deem necessary or convenient for the promotion of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Collaborate in the preparation, development, execution and follow-up of plans designed to increase commercial and industrial competitiveness. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with public administrations as support and advisory bodies for business creation. • Collaborate with the Public Administrations by carrying out material actions to check compliance with legal requirements and verification of commercial and industrial establishments in compliance with current general and sectoral regulations. • Draw up the statistics, evaluation surveys and studies it deems necessary to carry out its duties. • Promote and cooperate in the organization of fairs and exhibitions. • Collaborate in training programs established by public or private teaching centres and, where appropriate, by the competent Public Administrations. • To inform of draft regulations emanating from the Autonomous Communities that directly affect the general interests of trade, industry, services or navigation, in the cases and with the scope that the legal system determines. • Handle public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as manage public services related to them, when their management corresponds to the autonomous administration. • Collaborate with the competent administration by informing it of the studies, work and actions carried out to promote trade, industry, services and navigation. • Contribute to the promotion of tourism within the framework of cooperation and collaboration with the competent Public Administrations. • Collaborate with the competent administrations to provide information and guidance on the evaluation and accreditation procedure for the recognition of professional skills acquired through work experience, as well as the provision of facilities and services to carry out certain stages of the procedure, when these administrations so stipulate. • The Chambers of Commerce may also perform any other function that the Autonomous Communities, in the exercise of their powers, consider necessary. 		
Capabilities	<p>The Santa Cruz de Tenerife Chamber of Commerce has set up a wide range of services available to businesspeople, entrepreneurs, professionals and the unemployed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing information and business advisory services. • To disseminate and impart training related to the company. • Providing certification and homologation services for companies. • Creating, managing and administering franchising, by-product, subcontracting and waste exchanges, as well as contracting lines. • Performing arbitration, mediation and commercial conciliation functions, both nationally and internationally, and using any other alternative dispute resolution system, in accordance with current legislation. • Creating, managing or participating in business incubators and technology parks. • Managing and delivering training, both professional and university, aimed at, among others, workers, unemployed people and entrepreneurs. • Promote, organize and carry out commercial promotion of products, goods and services, and commercial dynamization. 		
Contact details	Direction	Pl. de la Candelaria, 6, 38003 Santa Cruz de Tenerife	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 100 400	
	Mail	info@camaratenerife.es	
Information resources	Web	https://www.camaratenerife.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CamaraComercioSantaCruzDeTenerife/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camaracomerciosctenerife/

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fcamarasctfe
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/c-mara-de-comercio-santa-cruz-de-tenerife/

Business name	Gran Canaria Chamber of Commerce	Logo	
Company name	Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Gran Canaria		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)		
Type of service	The Gran Canaria Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation is an institution that represents, promotes and defends the general interests of the different agents that make up the economic fabric of the island of Gran Canaria, offering services in business advice and management, entrepreneurship, training, employment, internationalization, innovation and improving competitiveness.		
Skills	<p>The following are competences of the Gran Canaria Chamber of Commerce: public-administrative functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Providing information and business advisory services. ▪ To disseminate and impart training related to the company. ▪ Providing certification and homologation services for companies. ▪ Creating, managing and administering franchising, by-product, subcontracting and waste exchanges, as well as contracting lines. ▪ Performing arbitration, mediation and commercial conciliation functions, both nationally and internationally, and using any other alternative dispute resolution system, in accordance with current legislation. ▪ Creating, managing or participating in business incubators and technology parks. ▪ Managing and delivering training, both professional and university, aimed at, among others, workers, unemployed people and entrepreneurs. ▪ Promote, organize and carry out commercial promotion actions for products, goods and services, and commercial dynamization. ▪ Collaborate with the different competent administrations, participating in the realization of the studies, works and actions that they carry out. ▪ Propose to the Government of the Canary Islands the measures it considers necessary for the promotion and defense of the general interests represented by the Chambers. ▪ Informing the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands, when it is consulted by the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness, in advance of the preparation of the Canary Islands General Plan for Internationalization and the Canary Islands General Plan for Competitiveness. ▪ Collaborate with the competent public administrations in the promotion of regionalization, understood as the expansion of the business market to the entire archipelago. ▪ Collaborate and/or participate in the management of infrastructures and public records. ▪ Collaborate with the competent public administrations in the promotion of the internationalization of companies, without prejudice to what is established in the basic legislation of the State, with regard to actions of general interest. ▪ Collaborate with the competent public administrations in the development of advisory, training, promotion, support and stimulus activities for foreign trade through the Canarian general plan for internationalization. ▪ Collaborate with the competent public administrations in actions to attract investors. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Collaborate and/or participate in the management of public and private training centres in the Autonomous Community of the Canary Islands and in their training programs. ▪ Collaborate and/or participate with public administrations in the management of business incubators and technology parks. ▪ Collaborate and/or participate with public administrations in the promotion, organization and execution of actions for the commercial promotion of products, goods and services and commercial dynamization. 		
Capabilities	<p>The Gran Canaria Chamber of Commerce has a wide range of tailor-made services for companies and professionals: businessmen, entrepreneurs, professionals and the unemployed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support and advisory services for business creation. ▪ Development of activities to promote and stimulate foreign trade. ▪ Guidance and counselling services. ▪ Organization and delivery of courses and training activities. ▪ Human resources and employment guidance services. ▪ Logistical support and event organization. ▪ Help with the management of European projects. ▪ Advisory and study functions. ▪ Certification services. ▪ Financial advice and the search for grants. ▪ Processing of public aid programs for companies. ▪ Development of tourism promotion activities. ▪ Performing arbitration, mediation and commercial conciliation functions. ▪ Management of companies' livelihoods. ▪ Space rental services. 		
Contact details	Direction	C./ León y Castillo, 24, 1ª Planta, 35003 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, España	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 390 390	
	Mail	https://www.camaragrancanaria.org/formularios/contacto-general/	
Information resources	Web	https://www.camaragrancanaria.org/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CamaraGranCanaria/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camara_gran_canaria/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FCamaraGCanaria
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/c-mara-oficial-de-comercio-industria-y-navegaci-n-de-gran-canaria/

Business name	Fuerteventura Chamber of Commerce	Logo	
Company name	Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Fuerteventura		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Fuerteventura)		
Type of service	The Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Fuerteventura is a Public Corporation, configured as a consultative and collaborative body with the Public Administrations, whose purpose is to represent, promote and defend the general interests of commerce, industry, services and navigation on the island of Fuerteventura.		
Skills	<p>The Chamber of Commerce of Fuerteventura exercises the powers of a public-administrative nature assigned to it by law and those that may be assigned to it by the Public Administrations in accordance with the instruments established by the legal system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issuing certificates of origin and other certificates related to national and international trade. • To collect mercantile customs and usages, as well as business practices and usages, and to issue certificates about their existence. • To be an advisory body to the Public Administrations for the development of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Develop activities to support and stimulate foreign trade. • Participate with the competent administrations in the organization of practical training in work centres, especially in the selection and validation of work centres and companies, in the designation and training of student tutors and in the control and evaluation of program compliance. • To process, in the cases in which they are required by the General State Administration, public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as to manage public services related to them when their management corresponds to the State Administration. • Manage a public census of all companies, as well as their establishments, delegations and agencies based in its demarcation. • To act as single business windows, when required to do so by the competent Public Administrations. • Collaborate with the Public Administrations in the administrative simplification of procedures for the start-up and development of economic and business activities, as well as in the improvement of economic and business regulation. • Promote actions aimed at increasing the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises and foster technological innovation and transfer to companies. • To promote and collaborate with public administrations in the implementation of the digital business economy. • If the European Union fund management authority deems it appropriate, the Chambers may participate in the management of European Union funds aimed at improving competitiveness in companies. • Propose to the Public Administrations as many reforms or measures as they deem necessary or convenient for the promotion of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Collaborate in the preparation, development, execution and follow-up of plans designed to increase commercial and industrial competitiveness. • Collaborate with Public Administrations as support and advisory bodies for business creation. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with the Public Administrations by carrying out material actions to check compliance with legal requirements and verification of commercial and industrial establishments in compliance with current general and sectoral regulations. • Draw up the statistics, evaluation surveys and studies it deems necessary to carry out its duties. • Promote and cooperate in the organization of fairs and exhibitions. • Collaborate in training programs established by public or private teaching centers and, where appropriate, by the competent Public Administrations. • To inform of draft regulations emanating from the Autonomous Communities that directly affect the general interests of trade, industry, services or navigation, in the cases and with the scope that the legal system determines. • Handle public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as manage public services related to them, when their management corresponds to the autonomous administration. • Collaborate with the competent administration by informing it of the studies, work and actions carried out to promote trade, industry, services and navigation. • Etc 		
Capabilities	<p>The Fuerteventura Chamber of Commerce offers services such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business creation, consolidation and support. ▪ International and foreign trade consultancy. ▪ Search for aid and grants. ▪ Advice and management of innovation and digitalization. ▪ Training. 		
Contact details	Direction	C/Secundino Alonso 98, 1º Puerto del Rosario, 35600 Fuerteventura (Las Palmas)	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 861 070	
	Mail	comunicacion@camarafuerteventura.org	
Information resources	Web	https://camarafuerteventura.org/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/camarafuerteventura
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camaradefuerteventura/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fcamaraftv
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/c%3%A1mara-de-comercio-de-fuerteventura/

Business name	Chamber of Commerce of Lanzarote and La Graciosa	Logo	
Company name	Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Lanzarote and La Graciosa		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Lanzarote and La Graciosa)		
Type of service	The Official Chamber of Commerce, Industry, Services and Navigation of Lanzarote and La Graciosa is a consultative and collaborative body whose purpose is to represent, promote and defend the general interests of commerce, industry, services and navigation on the islands of Lanzarote and La Graciosa.		
Skills	<p>The Chamber of Commerce of Lanzarote and La Graciosa exercises the powers of a public-administrative nature assigned to it by law and those that may be assigned to it by the Public Administrations in accordance with the instruments established by the legal system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issuing certificates of origin and other certificates related to national and international trade. • To collect mercantile customs and usages, as well as business practices and usages, and to issue certificates about their existence. • To be an advisory body to the Public Administrations for the development of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Develop activities to support and stimulate foreign trade. • Participate with the competent administrations in the organization of practical training in work centres, especially in the selection and validation of work centres and companies, in the appointment and training of student tutors and in the control and evaluation of program compliance. • To process, in the cases in which they are required by the General State Administration, public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as to manage public services related to them when their management corresponds to the State Administration. • Manage a public census of all companies, as well as their establishments, delegations and agencies based in its demarcation. • To act as single business windows, when required to do so by the competent Public Administrations. • Collaborate with the Public Administrations in the administrative simplification of procedures for the start-up and development of economic and business activities, as well as in the improvement of economic and business regulation. • Promote actions aimed at increasing the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises and foster technological innovation and transfer to companies. • To promote and collaborate with public administrations in the implementation of the digital economy of companies. • If the European Union fund management authority deems it appropriate, the Chambers may participate in the management of European Union funds aimed at improving competitiveness in companies. • Propose to the Public Administrations as many reforms or measures as they consider necessary or convenient for the promotion of trade, industry, services and navigation. • Collaborate in the preparation, development, execution and follow-up of plans designed to increase commercial and industrial competitiveness. • Collaborate with public administrations as support and advisory bodies for business creation. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborate with the Public Administrations by carrying out material actions to check compliance with legal requirements and verification of commercial and industrial establishments in compliance with current general and sectoral regulations. • Draw up the statistics, evaluation surveys and studies it deems necessary to carry out its duties. • Promote and cooperate in the organization of fairs and exhibitions. • Collaborate in training programs established by public or private teaching centres and, where appropriate, by the competent Public Administrations. • To inform of draft regulations emanating from the Autonomous Communities that directly affect the general interests of trade, industry, services or navigation, in the cases and with the scope that the legal system determines. • Handle public aid programs for companies in the terms established in each case, as well as manage public services related to them, when their management corresponds to the autonomous administration. • Collaborate with the competent administration by informing it of the studies, work and actions carried out to promote trade, industry, services and navigation. • Contribute to the promotion of tourism within the framework of cooperation and collaboration with the competent Public Administrations. • Collaborate with the competent administrations to provide information and guidance on the evaluation and accreditation procedure for the recognition of professional skills acquired through work experience, as well as the provision of facilities and services to carry out certain stages of the procedure, when these administrations so stipulate. 		
Capabilities	<p>The Chamber of Commerce of Lanzarote and La Graciosa is positioned as the main ally on the road to success for entrepreneurs from the islands of Lanzarote and La Graciosa, informing and supporting them from the conception of their ideas until they reach global prominence.</p> <p>To this end, it offers services such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Information and advice for entrepreneurs. ▪ Improving innovation and competitiveness. ▪ Training and employment (placement agency). ▪ Support for internationalization. ▪ Aid and subsidy management and advisory services. ▪ Document and traffic management. ▪ Certificates. ▪ Carrying out economic and profitability studies. ▪ Arbitration and mediation. ▪ Digital coworking. 		
Contact details	Direction	Ctra. Arrecife - Tinajo, nº 48 - Arrecife 35500	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 82 41 61	
	Mail	info@camaralanzarote.org	
Information resources	Web	https://camaralanzarote.org/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CamaraLanzarote
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camaralanzarote/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FCamaraLanzarote
YouTube		https://www.youtube.com/user/LanzaroteCamara	

Business name	Sociedad Canaria de Fomento Económico – PROEXCA		Logo	
Company name	Sociedad Canaria de Fomento Económico (PROEXCA)			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	The Canary Islands Economic Development Society (PROEXCA) is a public company attached to the presidency of the Government of the Canary Islands formed by a network of delegates and facilitators who are experts in internationalisation, whose priority objectives are to promote the expansion and internationalisation of Canary Islands companies, strengthen the business fabric of the Canary Islands and attract strategic investment to the islands.			
Skills	<p>PROEXCA's activities are mainly based on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – External promotion of Canarian companies. – Training and retaining island talent. – Promoting investment in the Canary Islands business fabric. 			
Capabilities	<p>PROEXCA has an extensive network of agents distributed around the world, mainly covering the continents of Europe, Africa and America.</p> <p>It also offers a wide range of services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Internationalization services: ▪ Training services: ▪ Investment promotion services in the Canary Islands: 			
Contact details	Direction	C/Emilio Castelar 4, 5th floor. 35007 - Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 47 24 00		
	Mail	Info@proexca.es		
Information resources	Web	https://proexca.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/PROEXCAparacanarias/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/proexca/?hl=es	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fproexca	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/proexca-gobierno-de-canarias/		

Business name	Sociedad de Promoción Económica de Gran Canaria – SPEGC		Logo	
Company name	Sociedad de Promoción Económica de Gran Canaria S.A.U.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)			
Type of service	<p>The Society for the Economic Promotion of Gran Canaria (SPEGC) is an entity through which the Cabildo of Gran Canaria channels its efforts to create new opportunities for economic development on the island.</p> <p>SPEGC's mission is to diversify Gran Canaria's productive and business fabric beyond the tourism sector, promoting and supporting opportunities in other sectors, fostering innovation, creating a favourable framework for investment and always prioritizing that all initiatives lead to job creation and contribute to creating economic and social value on the island.</p>			
Skills	<p>The SPEGC works with various instruments which, in summary, focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fostering business innovation. ▪ Support for entrepreneurs and business growth. ▪ Promoting the island to attract investment, companies and professionals. <p>These instruments are designed to provide customized responses to the specific demands of Gran Canaria's local and foreign companies, sectors and professionals.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>Through its investment instruments, SPEGC acts as a lever to improve Gran Canaria's sectoral competitiveness conditions, providing infrastructure and services that boost the island's potential growth sectors.</p> <p>SPEGC provides the following services to entrepreneurs and innovative companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Advisory and support service for entrepreneurs and innovative companies. ▪ Support in the search for funding for business projects. ▪ Programs for the creation and acceleration of entrepreneurial initiatives. ▪ Workshops. ▪ Training for managers, professionals and entrepreneurs. 			
Contact details	Direction	Avda. de la Feria, número 1, Recinto Ferial de Canarias (Infecar), 35012, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 424 600		
	Mail	consultas@spegc.org		
Information resources	Web	https://www.spegc.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/SPEGC.INCUBE/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/spegc/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Fspegc	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/sociedad-de-promoci-n-econ-mica-de-gran-canaria-spegc-/		

Business name	Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias		Logo	 ASOCIACION DE PUERTOS DEPORTIVOS DE CANARIAS
Company name	Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	The main objective of the Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias is to ensure the development and improvement of the recreational and sports boating sector in all its technical, social, sporting and environmental aspects, with a special interest in achieving maximum integration between ports and cities.			
Skills	The Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias focuses its efforts on the recreational boating sector and the activities of the Canary Islands' sports ports.			
Capabilities	<p>The Asociación de Puertos Deportivos de Canarias offers the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management services and collective representation of its members before the public authorities and any other public or private entity. • Dissemination of the values and characteristics of the associated ports at International Boat Shows or tourist and promotional events. • Coordination of all its members, bringing together proposed initiatives and joint actions that serve the regional, national or international promotion of the associated ports. • Boosting the improvement of regulations related to the sports ports and nautical facilities sector. • Organization of congresses, conventions, symposiums, etc., on all topics of interest to its members. 			
Contact details	Direction	Puerto de Mogán, Torre de control 2, 35138 Mogán		
	Telephone	-		
	Mail	secretario@asociacionpuertosdeportivoscanarias.com		
Information resources	Web	https://ccelpa.org/organizaciones/asociacion-de-puertos-deportivos-de-canarias/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Maritime High Technology Incubator (IAT)	Logo	
Company name	Maritime High Technology Incubator (IAT)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)		
Type of service	The High Technology Incubator (IAT) in Data Analytics and Artificial Intelligence applied to the maritime environment is a national reference centre for entrepreneurs and companies that develop innovative projects in these technological areas, with the potential for local, national and international growth.		
Skills	<p>IAT operates in the various subsectors and economic activities of the Canary Islands marine-maritime and port ecosystem:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ship repair. ▪ Port services. ▪ Logistics and maritime transport. ▪ Offshore services. ▪ Marine renewable energies. ▪ Biotechnology and other subsectors of the blue economy. 		
Capabilities	<p>The IAT offers a program of services structured through specialized activities aimed at the application of Data Analysis and Artificial Intelligence technologies in the maritime marine environment, so that participating companies can meet their advisory needs in the different stages of the project's life and validate their solutions in experimental or real environments.</p> <p>IAT provides the following services for companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Integrated incubation and acceleration programs of different scope, taking into account the maturity and progress of the participating projects (seed, pre-commercial and commercial projects). ▪ Specialized and personalized advisory and consulting services in the following functional areas: business, internationalization and access to credit and financing instruments; legal and tax advice; advice on R&D&I financing and technological consulting. ▪ Specialized group workshops and programs geared to the Incubator's business and technological areas of expertise. ▪ Opportunities for testing and experimentation in real environments. ▪ Cloud computing service. ▪ Fostering collaboration between the entrepreneurs of the different projects, companies and collaborating entities. ▪ Work spaces at the Marine Maritime Innovation Centre (CIMM1), as well as other SPEGC facilities in Gran Canaria. ▪ Promotion programs and knowledge dissemination actions: regional, national and international events to promote the Incubator's capabilities and services, as well as those of the incubated companies, companies and collaborating entities. ▪ Participation in visibility and promotion events. 		
Contact details	Direction	Avda. de la Feria, número 1, Recinto Ferial de Canarias (Infecar), 35012, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 424 600	
	Mail	consultas@spegc.org	

Information resources	Web	https://iatmarinomaritima.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	-
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/iatmarinomar%C3%ADtima

Business name	Asociación Náutica y de Recreo de Canarias – ASNÁUTICA		Logo	
Company name	Asociación Náutica y de Recreo de Canarias – ASNÁUTICA			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Provincial (Santa Cruz de Tenerife)			
Type of service	Professional and independent association offering services related to the world of sports and professional boating.			
Skills	<p>ASNAUTICA's competencies include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nautical titles. ▪ Transfers. ▪ Patron services. ▪ Advice. ▪ Buying and selling boats. ▪ Consulting. 			
Capabilities	<p>ASNAUTICA broadly covers the world of boating, offering services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Advice on obtaining sailing titles (sporting or professional). ▪ Purchase and maintenance of boats. ▪ Sailing support services to improve knowledge and boat handling techniques. ▪ Advice for shipowners. ▪ Search for tea. ▪ Managing and advising on claims, valuations or fees (they can be auditors and legal experts). ▪ Nautical consultancy and advisory services for merchant, recreational and professional marinas. ▪ Recreational boating courses at different levels. 			
Contact details	Direction	Avenida de las Asuncionistas, nº 10, 1º, 38006 - Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Tenerife, Canarias		
	Telephone	(+34) 638 430 217		
	Mail	asnautica@asnautica.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.asnautica.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/asnautica/?hl=es	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	PROMOTUR – Turismo de Canarias	Logo	
Company name	PROMOTUR – Turismo de Canarias S.A.		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	<p>PROMOTUR is a public entity of the Canary Islands Government responsible for promoting the Canary Islands tourism brand, whose main purpose is to transform the Canary Islands tourism model into a more competitive one through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Contributing to improving the resilience of the Canarian tourism model. – Promote increased commitment to climate neutrality by the Canarian tourism industry. – Boosting the capacity of Canarian tourism to generate value for the economy and citizens of the Canary Islands. 		
Skills	<p>In order to achieve its objectives, PROMOTUR has established the following lines of action:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Digital leadership. – The direct connection with the visitor. – Valuing knowledge. – Improving the tourism product through innovation, creativity and technology. – The extension and cohesion of the value chain. – Learning and constant iteration. – Empowering destiny. – Co-governance and public-public and public-private collaboration. 		
Capabilities	<p>PROMOTUR's actions are carried out along the following lines: and programs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Demand generation lines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Promotion program aimed at the end customer. – Professional promotion program. ▪ Demand management guidelines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Provider-side marketing program. – Customer-side marketing program. ▪ Guidelines for improving supply: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Connectivity improvement program. – Environmental sustainability program. – Tourism product improvement program. ▪ Support Lines: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Digitization and technology program. – Tourism intelligence and planning program. – Corporate communication, institutional relations and crisis management program. 		
Contact details	Direction	<p>Las Palmas de Gran Canaria office</p> <p>C/ Eduardo Benot, 35 - 35008 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria -Edificio Woermann</p> <p>Santa Cruz de Tenerife office</p> <p>C/. Villalba Hervás 12, 3ºC - 38002 Santa Cruz de Tenerife</p>	
	Telephone	Las Palmas: (+34) 928 290 579	

Information resources		Santa Cruz de Tenerife: (+34) 922 229 466		
	Mail	info@turismodecanarias.com		
	Web	https://turismodeislascanarias.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/TurismodelIslasCanarias/?locale=es_ES	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/turismodeislascanarias/	
Twitter		https://twitter.com/TurismCanarias?ref_src=twsrc%5Egoogle%7Ctwcamp%5Eserp%7Ctwgr%5Eauthor		
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/promotur-turismo-canarias-s-a-		

Business name	Gran Canaria Blue	Logo	
Company name	Gran Canaria Blue Association		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)		
Type of service	Gran Canaria Blue is a business association that offers numerous nautical activities throughout the year, as well as a wide and varied range of accommodation, always with the maximum guarantee and quality offered by all the companies associated with the brand.		
Skills	Companies from various sectors are associated under the Gran Canaria Blue brand: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nautical activities. - Tourist accommodation. - Marinas and port services. - Maritime transport on ferries. 		
Capabilities	<p>Gran Canaria Blue offers numerous nautical activities through specialized companies associated with the brand:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sail. ▪ Catamaran excursions. ▪ Sightings of cetaceans. ▪ Yacht rental. ▪ Surfing. ▪ Motorboating. ▪ Parasailing. ▪ Jetboater. ▪ Paddle surf. ▪ Etc <p>It also offers accommodation possibilities in a wide and varied list of hotels, apartments and other infrastructures perfectly prepared and adapted to meet the needs of all types of clients.</p> <p>They also offer services at the sports ports of Mogán and Pasito Blanco, which have facilities and professionals prepared to receive all types of boats.</p> <p>The brand also operates with two regular ferry shipping companies.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	C/ Los Balcones 4, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 367 508	
	Mail	info@grancanariablue.com	
Information resources	Web	https://www.grancanariablue.com/es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/grancanariablue
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/grancanariablue/

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/grancanariablue
		LinkedIn	-

Business name	Gran Canaria Tourist Board	Logo	Web Oficial de Turismo de Gran Canaria
Company name	Gran Canaria Tourism		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)		
Type of service	Turismo de Gran Canaria is an autonomous public body, created by the Gran Canaria Council, whose main mission is to protect the tourist interests of the island, the basis of Gran Canaria's economic development.		
Skills	<p>The functions entrusted to Turismo de Gran Canaria go beyond the typical tasks of a destination marketing organization, and also take on the role of administrative management of the island's tourism sector.</p> <p>The lines on which the body's commitments are structured are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gran Canaria's external promotion. - The continuous improvement of destiny. - Public management of the island tourism system. 		
Capabilities	<p>Gran Canaria's tourism activity is carried out under the commitment to maintain Gran Canaria as a top tourist destination, directing, planning and developing policies in line with changes in the markets.</p> <p>Turismo de Gran Canaria directs its work towards direct and active collaboration with the business sector, as well as with the different levels of island, regional and national administration.</p> <p>With regard to external promotion, the organization carries out activities typical of a media, marketing and communication agency, with actions for a multitude of markets. It also works on the permanent development of the products that make up its offer and on tourism improvement projects generated in coordination with other public administrations.</p> <p>Turismo de Gran Canaria is also the body that manages the administrative files relating to tourist establishments on the island, a function that makes it possible to monitor the situation of the sector and the activity of the destination.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	c/ Triana, 93 - 35002- Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 219 600	
	Mail	info@turismograncanaria.com	
Information resources	Web	https://www.grancanaria.com/turismo/es/area-profesional/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/MyGranCanaria
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/visitgrancanaria/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/turismogc
	LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/turismodegrancanaria	

Business name	Fuerteventura Tourist Board	Logo	
Company name	Fuerteventura Tourist Board		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Fuerteventura)		
Type of service	The Patronato de Turismo de Fuerteventura is an autonomous public body whose main objective is to protect and promote the island's tourist interests and its economic development.		
Skills	<p>With the aim of managing the Public Service for the Development and Coordination of Tourism on the island of Fuerteventura, and without prejudice to the superior direction, supervision and inspection of the Council, the Fuerteventura Tourist Board will exercise the following powers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organize acts aimed at attracting tourism. - Improving the island's tourist image. - Publishing information and tourist information about the island. - Promote the study of island life in the tourism field, either directly or through the various specialized bodies and agree with them on promotional actions, as well as the training of those professions related to tourism, carrying out the necessary actions for this. - Realization and promotion of studies in the field of Tourism. - In general, as many tourism-related issues as are of interest to the island. 		
Capabilities	In exercising its powers, the Fuerteventura Tourist Board shall coordinate its work and activities with the competent Ministry of the Government of the Nation and with the competent bodies of the Government of the Canary Islands, as well as with any other institutions and bodies, whether regional, national or foreign, which carry out their tourism activities on the island of Fuerteventura.		
Contact details	Direction	Address: Calle Alnte. Lallemand, 1, 35600 Puerto del Rosario, Las Palmas	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 530 844	
	Mail	info@visitfuerteventura.es	
Information resources	Web	https://fuerteventuraturismo.es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/wearevisitfuerteventura
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ifuerteventuraofficial/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/iFuerteventura
LinkedIn	-		

Business name	Tourism Lanzarote	Logo		
Company name	Sociedad de Promoción Exterior de Lanzarote, S.A.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Lanzarote)			
Type of service	Turismo de Lanzarote is a commercial entity of a mixed nature whose corporate purpose is the promotion, development and enhancement of economic activities, especially tourism, which contributes to boosting the economic development of the island of Lanzarote.			
Skills	<p>Turismo de Lanzarote carries out its activities in the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting and boosting tourism in Lanzarote and abroad. - Unifying Lanzarote's tourism promotion policy. - Study, Research, Documentation and Information and dissemination of the image of Lanzarote. - Implementation of actions deriving from Lanzarote's Tourism Marketing Plan. - Activities aimed at improving the image and beauty of Lanzarote's landscape. - Design of guides, brochures and any other tools needed to promote the tourism sector. - The organization, by itself or in collaboration, of all kinds of events with the aim of promoting tourism. - Internet marketing and promotion of Lanzarote as a tourist destination. - Promotion of the island as a venue for congresses, holidays, conventions, seminars and sporting activities of special interest. 			
Capabilities	Turismo de Lanzarote acts as a tourist destination marketing organization, promoting the different tourist services offered by the island, as well as carrying out management and administration activities within the tourism sector.			
Contact details	Direction	Calle Triana, 38, 35500, Arrecife de Lanzarote.		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 81 17 62		
	Mail	info@turismolanzarote.com		
Information resources	Web	https://turismolanzarote.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/TurismoLZT	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/turismolzt/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/TurismoLZT	
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/turismo-lanzarote		

Business name	Tenerife tourism	Logo		
Company name	Sociedad de Promoción Exterior de Tenerife S.A.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	Turismo de Tenerife is a public company, dependent on the Tenerife City Council, which has the clear and defined objective of making the island of Tenerife a leading destination, an international benchmark, modern and diverse, and which responds to the demands of today's travellers.			
Skills	<p>The main competencies of Tenerife Tourism are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote tourism and the economy of the island of Tenerife. - Developing a plan of actions for sustainability and promoting the competitiveness of companies on the island. - Coordinating works to improve and boost areas of tourist interest in collaboration with other entities and institutions. - Create synergies with different entities in the tourism sector to help improve the promotion of Tenerife in the source markets. - Execute agreements, promotional actions and campaigns with tourism intermediaries (travel agencies, tour operators, airlines, etc.). - Designing communication campaigns. - Carrying out public relations and loyalty activities. - Boosting the attraction of investment for strategic projects, advising companies from abroad on the aid, credits and subsidies they can obtain. - Become a benchmark in quality, competitiveness and sustainability. 			
Capabilities	<p>Turismo de Tenerife has a marketing and communication strategy that places Tenerife as a strategic enclave that stands out for its architecture, heritage, gastronomy, oenology, nature and landscapes, as well as for its sun and beach offer.</p> <p>To carry out its activities, Turismo de Tenerife relies on the unconditional support of more than half a million associated companies, with whom it works hand in hand to achieve its objectives.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Avenida la Constitución, 12, Spain, 38005, Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Spain		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 237 870		
	Mail	info@webtenerife.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.webtenerife.com/corporativa/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/visittenerifees	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/visit_tenerife/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/VisitTenerifeES	
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/turismo-de-tenerife		

Business name	La Palma Island Council Tourism	Logo	
Company name	Tourism Board of the Island Council of La Palma		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (La Palma)		
Type of service	Turismo del Cabildo Insular de La Palma is the body responsible for promoting tourism on the island of La Palma.		
Skills	<p>To achieve its objective, Turismo del Cabildo Insular de La Palma has set a series of activities and skills:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boosting island tourism development in all its manifestations. - Carry out the study, planning, organization, programming, advertising and execution of tourism promotional actions at island, inter-island, national and international level. Coordinating promotional work with the municipalities, the Canary Islands Government, the Central Government, the European Union and other bodies to carry out actions aimed at achieving tourism promotion for La Palma. - Improve the island's tourist image by developing tourist resources and attractions in the island destination, as well as boosting tourist infrastructure and everything related to the development of rural, sporting and third age tourism and any other social manifestation with a tourist slant. 		
Capabilities	<p>Turismo del Cabildo Insular de La Palma provides the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Processing and resolving files relating to the operation of tourist accommodation establishments. - Classification and reclassification of tourist establishments. - Processing of applications for change of ownership and/or change of name of tourist establishments. - Registration in the General Tourist Register. Complaint sheets and inspection books. - Control, supervision, coordination and promotion of tourism actions and infrastructures by institutional and territorial bodies on the island of La Palma. - Promotion of island tourism and tourist activities, in coordination with the business sector. 		
Contact details	Direction	Avda. Marítima, 34 E-38700 - Santa Cruz de La Palma (Canary Islands)	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 423 100	
	Mail	informacion@visitlapalma.es	
Information resources	Web	https://visitlapalma.es/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/visitlapalmacanarias/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/visitlapalmacanarias/

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/visitalpalma
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/consejeriaturismolapalma

Business name	Patronato Insular de Turismo de la Gomera	Logo		
Company name	Patronato Insular de Turismo de la Gomera			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (La Gomera)			
Type of service	The Patronato Insular de Turismo de la Gomera is a public organization whose main purpose is to promote tourism on the island of La Gomera.			
Skills	<p>The competencies of the Gomera Island Tourism Board are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities to promote, advertise and provide tourist information about the island of La Gomera abroad (publicity campaigns, attendance at holidays, seminars, conventions, events...). - Management and promotion of collaboration agreements with public and private entities for tourism promotion. - Fostering entrepreneurial initiative in the field of tourism from the perspective of generating stable employment. - Tourist infrastructure and viewpoint network. - The management of transferred competencies in the field of Entertainment and Island Tourism and Classified Activities. - Organization of national or international tourist events. 			
Capabilities	<p>El Patronato Insular de Turismo de la Gomera carries out its activity based on the following strategic lines:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quality and permanent improvement of the tourist offer. - Training in sustainability and competitiveness. - Tourism information management. - Boosting tourist experiences. - Valuing tourism resources. - Positioning the "LA Gomera" brand. 			
Contact details	Direction	C. Real, 4, 38800 San Sebastián de La Gomera, Santa Cruz de Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 922 14 15 12 // (+34) 922 47 00 92		
	Mail	info@lagomera.travel		
Information resources	Web	https://lagomera.travel/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/lagomera.travel	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/lagomeratravel/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/TurismoLaGomera	
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/cabildo-insular-de-la-gomera	

Business name	El Hierro Tourist Board	Logo	
Company name	El Hierro Tourist Board		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (El Hierro)		
Type of service	El Patronato Insular de Turismo de El Hierro is a public organization created to promote tourism on the island of Hierro.		
Skills	<p>El Patronato Insular de Turismo de El Hierro oversees:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities to promote, promote and provide tourist information about the island of El Hierro abroad, such as advertising campaigns, attendance at holidays, seminars or conventions. - The management and promotion of collaboration agreements with public and private entities for tourism promotion on the island. - Fostering entrepreneurial initiative in the field of tourism from the perspective of generating stable employment. - The management of transferred competencies in the field of Entertainment and Island Tourism and Classified Activities. - Organization of national or international tourist events. 		
Capabilities	At the tourist information office of the El Hierro Tourist Board, located in the municipality of Valverde, visitors will be attended to by a specialized technical team who will provide them with all the information they need about the different tourist activities offered by the island (tourism, accommodation, gastronomy, leisure, etc.).		
Contact details	Direction	C/ Dr. Quintero 11, Valverde, EL Hierro, Santa Cruz de Tenerife	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 550 302 // (+34) 922 550 326	
	Mail	turismo@elhierro.es	
Information resources	Web	https://elhierro.travel/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/turismoelhierro/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/turismoelhierro/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/ElHierroTurismo
LinkedIn	-		

Business name	Official College of Tourism Professionals – COPTURISMO	Logo	
Company name	Official College of Tourism Professionals – COPTURISMO		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	The Official Association of Tourism Professionals of the Canary Islands (COPTURISMO) is a Public Law Corporation, with its own legal personality, created with the purpose of representing tourism professionals before the different bodies and looking after their interests.		
Skills	<p>The competencies established by the COPTURISMO Law are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The organization of the tourism profession in all its forms and specialties. – The exclusive representation of this profession. – Defending the interests of collegiate bodies. <p>All this without prejudice to the competences of the Public Administrations, or of trade unions and employers' organizations, within the specific scope of their functions.</p>		
Capabilities	<p>COPTURISMO offers the following services to institutions, public and private companies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Registration in the Canary Islands Register of Tourism Professionals. ▪ Active participation in Working Tables. ▪ Advice on hotels, guides, event organization and training. ▪ Preparation of ad hoc training in all areas of tourism. ▪ Market Surveys and Studies. ▪ Development and Presentation of Local Development Improvement Projects. ▪ Judicial Expertise. ▪ Mediation and Arbitration. ADR and ODR dispute resolution systems. ▪ Mystery guest services. ▪ Study and Advice on the Planning and Management of Hotel Departments. ▪ Search for financing and funds for the completion and execution of tourism-related projects. ▪ Active participation in initiatives aimed at improving the tourism sector. ▪ Involvement in Organizing Committees of Congresses, Conventions, Conferences and other Tourism Events. ▪ Formalization of Agreements and Conventions. ▪ Professional Scholarships for Companies and Institutions. 		
Contact details	Direction	<p>Santa Criz de Tenerife</p> <p>University School of Tourism of Tenerife, C. Jose Zarate Y Penichet, 5, 38001 Santa Cruz de Tenerife</p> <p>Las Palmas</p> <p>Casa del Turismo, Parque Santa Catalina S/N. 35007 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. Las Palmas</p>	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 22 50 06	

Information resources	Mail	info@copturismo.com		
	Web	https://www.copturismo.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/copturismo/?locale=es_ES	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/copturismo.official/?utm_source=ig_embed&ig_rid=4cfc2f5c-3e75-4deb-a238-ca295dd0eeb4	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Nautic Ocean	Logo		
Company name	Nautic Ocean - Ocean of experiences			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	National			
Type of service	Nautic Ocean is a travel agency focused on offering the best selection of nautical experiences.			
Skills	<p>In general, Nautic Ocean focuses its activity on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boat tours and excursions to the Canary Islands (Lanzarote and Fuerteventura), Greece, Croatia, the Balearic Islands (Ibiza, Mallorca, Menorca and Formentera), Tabarca Island (in Alicante), the Costa Brava, Barcelona and the Ebro Delta, among others. ▪ Boat rental: sailboats, catamarans and motorboats. Boat rental to go fishing or to discover the most emblematic beaches and coves. ▪ They offer accommodation in most of their destinations (hotels and villas) so that their clients can stay and board a boat the following day. ▪ Nautical services and experiences: excursions with sunsets, regattas, cruises around the Mediterranean and Canary Islands, sailing across the Atlantic, day trips on a sailboat, etc. ▪ Organization of nautical excursions in their destinations, such as walking routes, visits to the most emblematic places in each city, meals or scenes where the best gastronomy in the area is prepared, etc. ▪ Experience in the form of light sailing courses and sailing courses, with port manoeuvring classes, sextant handling classes, private sailing classes and intensive PER in the Balearics. ▪ Design of tailor-made vacation packages. ▪ Advice and assistance in private boat profitability processes. 			
Capabilities	Nautic Ocean offers nautical experiences of all kinds, adapted to the needs of its clients. In addition, they offer advice to personalize their experiences, accompanying their clients from the moment before sailing, planning their trip, providing advice on which is the best route for them, the best fish farms and coves to visit, the best restaurants to eat, and other information that will make their nautical experience unforgettable. Normally your excursions include the services of an expert and friendly guide, some on-board catering and more extras.			
Contact details	Direction	Can Bruguera, 3, Tiana, Spain		
	Telephone	(+34) 934 118 415		
	Mail	info@nauticocean.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.nauticocean.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/nauticocean	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/nauticocean/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/NauticOcean	
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/nauticocen		

Business name	Instituto Social de la Marina – ISM	Logo	
Company name	Instituto Social de la Marina – ISM		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	National		
Type of service	<p>The Instituto Social de la Marina (ISM) de España is a Social Security management body with its own legal personality, with a national scope, whose task is to manage, administration and recognition of the right to the benefits of the Special Social Security Scheme for seafarers, as well as the registration of companies, discharges and discharges of seafarers covered by this special scheme and other competences recognized in its regulatory rules.</p>		
Skills	<p>They are ISM competencies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The management, administration and recognition of the right to benefits under the Special Social Security Scheme for Seafarers. ▪ In collaboration with the General Treasury, the registration of companies, membership, ups and downs of workers, tax collection and control of quotations. ▪ Health care for seafarers and their beneficiaries within the national territory. ▪ The health care of seafarers on board and abroad, using its own means, such as the Radio-Medical Centre, Data Bank, Centres abroad, Health Bureaus and others that may be set up, or agreeing on the evacuation and repatriation of sick or injured workers. ▪ Health information for seafarers, education and distribution of the Onboard Health Guide, the practice of pre-boarding medical examinations, inspection and control of onboard health equipment and the hygienic conditions of vessels, and any other preventive medicine and health education functions that may be delegated to it. ▪ The professional training and promotion of seafarers, as well as their well-being on board or in ports (national or foreign) and that of their families, in compliance with the recommendations of the International Labor Organization. ▪ Promote, in collaboration with the State Employment Service, the actions that fall to it, when they refer to seafarers, both in the management of unemployment benefits and in the placement of seafarers. ▪ Carrying out studies, informing or proposing draft standards or programs and participating in the drafting of international conventions affecting the maritime-fishery sector. 		
Capabilities	<p>The ISM General Council is the highest body through which the participation of workers, entrepreneurs, fishermen's associations and public bodies in the monitoring and control of the Institute's management is carried out. Its main functions include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Developing the Marina Social Institute's performance criteria. ▪ Preparing the draft budget. ▪ Approve the annual report of the Marina Social Institute. <p>For its part, it is up to the General Council's Executive Committee to supervise and control the implementation of the General Council's agreements, as well as to propose, where appropriate, as many measures, plans and programs as necessary for this purpose.</p> <p>Likewise, the ISM Directorate, with the rank of general sub-directorate, will assume the competencies of planning, directing, controlling and inspecting the ISM's activities in order</p>		

	to fulfil its purposes. In addition, the Directorate will be responsible for information, public relations, international relations, documentary funds, publishing and distribution of publications, human resources and training of the Institute's staff and inspection and quality of services, as well as relations with IT services and the Delegated Legal Service.		
Contact details	Direction	C. León y Castillo, 322, 35007 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las Palmas	
	Telephone	928494645	
	Mail	laspalmas.dirprov.ism@seg-social.es	
Information resources	Web	https://www.seg-social.es/wps/portal/wss/internet/Conocenos/QuienesSomos/29421	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=1470407369854533&_rdt
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	https://x.com/ismrevistamar?lang=es
		LinkedIn	-

Business name	Global Port Canary Islands	Logo	
Company name	Global Ports Canary Islands, Sociedad Limitada.		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	<p>Global Ports Holding is an independent cruise port operator with an established presence in the Caribbean, Mediterranean and Asia-Pacific regions, which recently created a new sustainable terminal in the Las Palmas port.</p> <p>Its aim is to be a key facilitator of sustainable cruise tourism in its destinations, for the benefit of all stakeholders, bringing a conscious approach to the development and promotion of its ports and destinations.</p>		
Skills	<p>Global Ports Holding mainly carries out activities related to maritime and inland waterway transportation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Construction and operation of ship terminal services. ▪ Port logistics services such as handling, warehousing, storing and organizing the transport of goods. ▪ Trade in machinery. ▪ Assistance and management of commercial business for minors. 		
Capabilities	<p>Global Ports Holding operates or manages a network of cruise ports mainly through long-term concession agreements or management agreements, offering its customers and passengers leading levels of service tailored to their needs, delivered to leading standards of safety, security and performance worldwide.</p> <p>Through their business network, they offer a wide range of primary port services to cruise lines, passengers and crews, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Terminal services: Attend to boarding and disembarking needs, billing and crew operations for stopovers, guaranteeing the safety of passengers and crew. ▪ Port services: These include docking, mooring, provision of shore services and stevedoring. They also provide necessary services such as fuel, water and supplies for the ship. ▪ Maritime services: These include fishing and paddling, which are offered in some of its ports according to the scope of the concession. <p>As a complement to its main port services, we offer auxiliary services, whose main objective is to improve the experience of its passengers in the port and at their destination. These auxiliary services include transport services to and from the port, tax-free shops offering souvenirs, gifts and other items, restaurants, cafés and bars for eating and drinking, guest information centres providing information and assistance, services for crew members, transport, as well as convenience services such as currency exchange, storage of equipment and Wi-Fi. In addition, the port could establish alliances with local companies and organizations to provide these services, which could also contribute to the local economy.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Calle Muelle De Leon Y Castillo, S/N, Las Palmas De Gran Canaria, 35008, Las Palmas	

Information resources	Telephone	-		
	Mail	info@globalportsholding.com		
	Web	https://www.globalportsholding.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/globalportsholding	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/GlobalPortsHolding/	
Twitter		https://twitter.com/global_ports		
LinkedIn		https://uk.linkedin.com/company/global-ports-holding?trk=public_post-text		

Business name	FIFO Diving Shop		Logo	
Company name	Fifo Diving, Sociedad Limitada.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	FIFO Diving Shop is a company based in Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and dedicated to renting and selling items for leisure and water sports.			
Skills	<p>FIFO Diving Shop's activities are focused on the following areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sport diving. ▪ Underwater fishing. ▪ Apnoea. ▪ Snorkel. ▪ Swimming. ▪ Aquatic and underwater photography 			
Capabilities	<p>FIFO Diving Shop offers services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Renting items for water sports and leisure activities. ▪ Sale and rental of boating and submarining equipment. ▪ Charge, repair, sale of air and nitro tank. ▪ Cross-border order sending service. 			
Contact details	Direction	Centro Comercial Sotavento, C. Joaquín Blanco Torrent, LOCAL 15, 35004 Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 30 01 94		
	Mail	fifodivingshop@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://fifodivingshop.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fifodivingshop/?locale=es_ES	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/fifo_diving_shop/	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Keep Sailing	Logo	KEEP SAILING
Company name	Keep Sailing		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	Keep Sailing is a sports and leisure boat rental company that offers its customers the enjoyment of a sailing or motorboat, without the costs and worries of owning, mooring and maintaining a boat.		
Skills	<p>Keep Sailing offers services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renting with or without a deposit. • Sailing Club • Sailing School • Nautical Events • Boat transportation 		
Capabilities	<p>Keep Sailing offers two types of contracts to adapt to the needs of each particular client:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Keep Sailing Experiences: Single-day or weekend experiences that include dinner and service on board. ▪ Keep Sailing Seasons: Experiences designed to make your customers feel like they own a sailboat without the costs and worries of owning, mooring and maintaining a boat, by having a series of contracted sailings every month. For these services, customers must have at least a sailing license. <p>They also organize events for companies on the high seas and training courses.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco, San Bartolomé de Tirajana, 35110, Las Palmas	
	Telephone	(+34) 699 999 497	
	Mail	info@keepsailing.es	
Information resources	Web	https://keepsailing.es/#inicio	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/KeepSailingCanarias/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/keepsailingcanarias/?hl=es
	Twitter	-	
LinkedIn	-		

Business name	Acosta Maritime Engineering - ACOSTASUB		Logo	
Company name	Acosta Ingeniería Marítima S.L.U.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	<p>Acosta Ingeniería Marítima (ACOSTASUB) is a company linked to the marine-maritime sector that operates under two brands:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ BLUEMATT ACOSTA: Focused on professional buoyancy and subacute engineering services. ▪ ASUB: Focused on subacute training. 			
Skills	<p>ACOSTASUB's activities revolve around Blue Engineering, i.e. the engineering that specifies the sectors covered by the Blue Economy. The areas in which the group mainly operates are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maritime, sub-aquatic, port, coastal, naval and hydraulic engineering. ▪ Port and maritime services. ▪ Underwater work. ▪ Nautical. ▪ Training. ▪ Blue innovation. 			
Capabilities	<p>The ACOSTASUB group of companies provides various specialized maritime services, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Technical services and other activities related to technical advice on maritime, sub-aquatic, port, coastal and hydraulic engineering. ▪ Conducting studies and teaching courses and seminars. ▪ Planning and development of professional diving work. ▪ Etc 			
Contact details	Direction	C. Arquitecto, 1, 35219 Telde, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 63 57 54		
	Mail	Info@acosta-group.com		
Information resources	Web	http://acosta-group.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/ACOSTASUB/100039182508657/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/bluematt.acosta/p/CL9jWs3FMaa/	
		Twitter	-	
	LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/bluematt-acosta-ingenieria		

Business name	Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco		Logo	
Company name	Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco S.L.U			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco is the company in charge of managing the activities related to the infrastructure with the same name.			
Skills	<p>Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco offers the following services for vessels dedicated to maritime sports sailing:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conservation and maintenance services. ▪ Tie. ▪ Varadero ▪ Repair workshop. ▪ Acquisition and rental and/or sale of mooring points for sports and leisure boats. 			
Capabilities	<p>The Puerto Deportivo Pasito Blanco is located near the tourist centre of Maspalomas, in the south of Gran Canaria, and has capacity for 388 boats with a maximum length of 40 meters.</p> <p>This marina has extensive services to ensure the comfort of sailors and provide everything they could need for their boat.</p> <p>Supermarkets, laundries and cafeterias can be found in the vicinity of the port.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Carretera GC 500, Ed Oficinas, San Bartolome De Tirajana, 35106, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 14 21 94		
	Mail	info@pasitoblanco.com		
Information resources	Web	https://pasitoblanco.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/puertodeportivopasitoblanco	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/puertodeportivopasitoblanco/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/PdPasito	
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/puerto-deportivo-pasito-blanco	

Business name	Motonáutica Las Palmas	Logo	
Company name	Motonáutica Las Palmas Sociedad Limitada		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	Motonáutica Las Palmas is a company that acts as an intermediary in the trade of boats and nautical engines.		
Skills	<p>The working areas of Motonáutica Las Palmas are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boats. ▪ Marine engines. ▪ Nautical electronics. ▪ Towing 		
Capabilities	Motonáutica Las Palmas offers all kinds of trade and industrial services related to the representation and distribution of rights and products of national and foreign brands and companies related to boating.		
Contact details	Direction	C/ Los Dragos S/N - Polígono Industrial De Arinaga - Fase 4ª 35119 Agüimes (Las Palmas)	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 18 06 94	
	Mail	comercial@motonauticalaspalmas.com	
Information resources	Web	http://motonauticalaspalmas.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/motonauticalaspalmas/?locale=es_ES
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-
LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/motonautica-las-palmas-sl?trk=public_post-text		

Business name	DISTRIM		Logo	
Company name	Distrimar SI			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	DISTRIMAR is a company specializing in the purchase and sale of products for fishing and submarining.			
Skills	<p>DISTRIMAR offers services related to the following sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fishing. ▪ Nautical. ▪ Submarinism. ▪ Kayaks. ▪ Naval electronics. ▪ Boat engines. ▪ Camping. 			
Capabilities	<p>DISTRIMAR offers a quality, dynamic and efficient sales and after-sales service with a range of more than 40,000 items in permanent stock at highly competitive prices and from the most prestigious brands on the national and international market, being the official distributor of Yamaha Engines for the Canary Islands.</p> <p>They also work with other brands such as Lowrance, Simrad, B&G, C-Map, Compass, Navionics, Airmar, Raymarine, Garmin and Hondex among others.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Duraznero 27B - 35118-Agüimes - Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 928 172 881		
	Mail	comercial@distrimarsl.com		
Information resources	Web	https://distrimarsl.es/es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/distrimarsl/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/distrimarsl/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/distrimarsl	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	ARCOS nautical academy		Logo	
Company name	ARCOS nautical academy			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)			
Type of service	Company dedicated to online training and advice on driving and piloting nautical vessels and watercraft.			
Skills	Its activity is centred on online nautical and navigation training.			
Capabilities	<p>Its services include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional navigation courses and certificates. • Recreational boating courses and licenses. • Renewal and issuance of titles. • Nautical consultancy. • Multimedia services with simulators. <p>The courses have been developed based on the experience of the best sailors and designed using the most modern teaching techniques.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Calle de Pi y Margall, 58, 35006, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 618 46 90 02		
	Mail	info@academianauticaarcos.com		
Information resources	Web	https://academianauticaarcos.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/academianauticaarcos	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/academiaarcos/	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		https://es.linkedin.com/company/academia-n%C3%A1utica-arcos		

Business name	Pléyone Management Capital		Logo	
Company name	Pléyone Management Capital SI.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	Pléyone's mission is to offer advanced information and communication technology solutions to its clients and collaborators, with the aim of facilitating their business processes, adding a differentiating character to their value chain, in an environment of collaboration that makes them their trusted technological partners.			
Skills	Pléyone's activity is mainly focused on the sale and marketing of computer programs and applications developed by third parties or its own, as well as other services related to information technology, computer science and software engineering. They have carried out various projects of this kind in the maritime sector.			
Capabilities	<p>Pléyone offers services related to information technology and computing, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apps for workforce. • Outsourcing services. • Design of control panels. • Specialized and tailor-made software development. • Web design. • Business consulting. 			
Contact details	Direction	Calle Juan De Aguilar, 2 - Piso 4, 38008, Santa Cruz De Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 673 957 282		
	Mail	info@pleyone.es		
Information resources	Web	https://pleyone.es/		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/pleyone-management-capital?trk=public_profile_topcard-current-company	

Business name	Biosean - Whale watching & marine science		Logo	
Company name	Misael Danilo Morales Vargas			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Tenerife)			
Type of service	Biosen is a company that organizes marine excursions along the coast and in the marine environment of the island of Tenerife, which has a great biodiversity and a large fauna of dolphins and seals.			
Skills	<p>Biosean's activities are centred on the themes of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sightings of cetaceans and marine fauna. ▪ Scuba diving. ▪ Recycled marine waste. ▪ Scientific production and dissemination through projects, agreements and cooperation. 			
Capabilities	<p>Biosean offers services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Whale watching excursions. ▪ Private boat tours. ▪ Monitoring cetaceans and marine turtles. ▪ Removal of marine waste. <p>To carry out these services, the company has a 7.5-meter boat with capacity for 10 passengers. With it they can carry out the excursions in a personal environment and in contact with the guide, so that everyone can listen to the explanations on board. It is a stable, manoeuvrable and non-invasive semi-rigid boat (RIB), which allows for a perfect and, above all, respectful interaction with marine fauna.</p> <p>In addition, all cetacean sighting excursions are carried out with the company of a marine biologist guide and a hydrophone that allows you to hear the animals.</p> <p>On the other hand, the data collected during cetacean sighting trips is made available and processed through collaborations with various universities and research centres, as well as for passers-by, who often use it for their reports and theses. The aim is to understand the marine fauna and generate scientifically sound knowledge that is important for species conservation measures and marine protection.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Marina del Sur. Pantalán 4, 38631 Las Galletas, Santa Cruz de Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 647 94 99 64		
	Mail	info@biosean.com		
Information resources	Web	https://biosean.com/es/		
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/biosean/		

	Social networks	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/biosean.tenerife/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/biosean_?lang=es
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/biosean/

Business name	Náutica Nivaria – Watertaxi		Logo	
Company name	Nautica Nivaria Sl.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Tenerife)			
Type of service	Náutica Nivaria is a company that organizes marine excursions along the coast of Anaga, on the island of Tenerife. This area is mostly made up of high cliffs, so that many of the beaches at the mouths of the valleys can only be reached by sea or after a few hours of walking along paths that offer impressive views of the cliffs.			
Skills	<p>Náutica Nivaria's activity is focused on the exploitation of recreational boats, their purchase and sale, and the assignment of their use through charter and lease contracts.</p> <p>The company also plans, promotes and carries out sea excursions, both by boat and on foot along the coast.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>Náutica Nivaria offers boat trips and marine excursions along the Anaga coastline from different points (San Andrés, Antequera and Roque Bermejo).</p> <p>It also organizes excursions on foot to the Anaga cliffs and visits to coastal caves.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Calle Los Molinos, 16 - Piso 11 A, Santa Cruz De Tenerife, 38005, Tenerife		
	Telephone	(+34) 697 271 850		
	Mail	info@nauticanivaria.com		
Information resources	Web	http://www.nauticanivaria.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/nauticanivaria/?locale=es_ES	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/watertaxi_nivaria/	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/nautica-nivaria-sl?trk=public_profile_topcard-current-company			

Business name	Starlight Foundation	Logo	
Company name	Starlight Foundation		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	<p>The Starlight Foundation is a non-profit organization, with its own legal personality, created by the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) and with the majority of its capital contributed by Consultora Corporación 5, whose main purpose is the dissemination of astronomy and the promotion, coordination and management of the Starlight movement, centred on the protection of the night sky, the cultural dissemination of astronomy and local sustainable economic development through astrotourism.</p>		
Skills	<p>The pillars on which the Starlight Foundation's activities are based are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Night sky protection. One of the Foundation's priority objectives, contained in the "La Palma Declaration", is the protection and conservation of night skies, considered an important scientific, cultural, environmental and tourist resource. To this end, it is important to spread the culture of intelligent lighting among the population and to promote local, national and international initiatives that avoid light pollution, enable energy savings and mitigate the effects of climate change. • Cultural dissemination of astronomy. The Starlight Foundation also aims to disseminate astronomy in a different way, linking it to society through activities related to Starlight Tourism, the development of a network of rural Starlight Houses and Hotels, the promotion of Stellar Sites where astronomical festivals and activities can be organized, astrophotography competitions, etc. The aim is to spread the word about this science, but in a mild way, by introducing it to recreational activities that can be carried out, for example, in places that have achieved or are in the process of achieving certification as Starlight Tourist Destinations. In order to fulfil this purpose in an appropriate manner, it is also important to hold specialized training courses for those people (Starlight Astronomy Guides and Monitors) who will serve as liaisons with the public. In addition, the Foundation organizes seminars, days and specific courses for the dissemination of astronomy, and collaborates with national and international entities to bring knowledge of the Universe closer to society in general. • Star tourism. Another objective is to promote scientific tourism and, more specifically, star tourism, as an emerging, sustainable and quality segment. To this end, the 		

	<p>Foundation has a Certification System which accredits as Starlight Tourist Destinations those places whose sky quality and infrastructures make it possible to develop this type of activity.</p> <p>The Foundation also classifies as Starlight Reserves those places that maintain intact the conditions of natural illumination and clarity of the night sky, incorporating the starry landscape into the cultural assets of its nature. Starlight certification is supported by the UNWTO and the IAU.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intelligent lighting and energy savings. The Foundation also strives to establish a culture of rational use of lighting, which will enable energy savings, the development of star tourism in different parts of the planet and the protection of the many species that need a dark sky for their conservation. 	
Capabilities	<p>To achieve its objectives, the Starlight Foundation carries out activities and offers various products and services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management and administration of a certification system, which accredits those spaces that have excellent sky quality and represent an example of protection and conservation. ▪ Promotion of astro-tourism, which is a type of sustainable and responsible tourism that combines night and day sky observation, promotion and leisure activities related to astronomy. Astrotourism has a positive impact on the environment and empowers local communities. It is a resource for promoting areas with fewer opportunities that find star tourism an excellent opportunity to increase the number of quality visitors. ▪ Development of studies and systems for evaluating sky quality ▪ Organization of courses and training activities on general astronomy, observation techniques, prevention of light pollution, etc. ▪ Astronomy communication and dissemination. ▪ Organization of events, days and seminars on astronomy and tourism. ▪ Astrotourism consulting services. 	
Contact details	Direction	Calle Vía Láctea S/N 38205 San Cristóbal de La Laguna, Tenerife, España
	Telephone	(+34) 922 31 51 40
	Mail	gestion@fundacionstarlight.org
Information resources	Web	https://www.fundacionstarlight.org/
	Social networks	Facebook https://www.facebook.com/fundacionstarlight/?locale=es_LA
		Instagram https://www.instagram.com/fundacionstarlight/
		Twitter https://twitter.com/fundstarlight
		LinkedIn -

Business name	AstroEduca (AstroEduca Astronomy Tours & AstroShop in Gran Canaria) (AstroCanarias)		Logo	
Company name	Astroeduca Sociedad Limitada.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)			
Type of service	AstroEduca is a company specializing in astrophysics promotion, astronomical tourism in the Canary Islands and the sale of telescopes and astronomical observation equipment.			
Skills	AstroEduca develops activities in the areas of astronomy and astrophysics observation, research and instrumentation.			
Capabilities	<p>AstroEducason offers an extensive range of professional services to cover all your needs in the exciting world of astronomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organization of group and private astrotours for residents and astrotourists. From external astronomical viewpoints, with the accompaniment of a StarLight certified teacher, who will interpret the sky in a pleasant and didactic way, in plain sight and with advanced telescopes, showing the main constellations and celestial objects (stars, galaxies, nebulae, cumuli and double stars). • Astronomical auditing services and assembly of didactic / amateur astronomical observatories, thematization of astronomical viewpoints and scientific expeditions. • Design and promotion of activities for leisure, entertainment and environmental companies, tour operators, hotels, rural and country houses. • Implementation of school workshops with children and young people centred on the acquisition of scientific knowledge and critical thinking. • Selling astronomical equipment. The company is the first shop specializing in the sale of telescopes, prismatic telescopes, CCD cameras, microscopes, weather stations and all kinds of accessories in the province of Las Palmas. They work with leading brands in exclusive distribution, such as Celestron, Meade, ATIK, Lunt Solar, Sbig, Imaging Source, Takahashi, Vixen, Skywatcher, GSO, TS, ORION USA, William Optics, etc. They are distributors of original NASA products (metal models of space shuttles, Space Shuttle and the like) and have a shipping service throughout Europe. • Organization of expeditions around the world to record total eclipses of the Sun. <p>All AstroEducas professionals have a university degree and accredited experience in teaching, observational astronomy and astronomical instrumentation.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Location, Av. Tinamar, 46, 35320 Vega de San Mateo, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 665 82 92 75		
	Mail	astroeduca.astrotours@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.astroeduca.com/		

	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/AstroEduca/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/astroeduca/
		Twitter	http://www.twitter.com/astroeduca
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/astroeduca-sl

Business name	Astro GC		Logo	
Company name	AstroGC Astronomy Tours			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canarias)			
Type of service	Astro GC is a company dedicated to scientific and technical research in astronomy and the organization of astronomical events.			
Skills	Astro GC's activities focus on planning and carrying out workshops and open-air excursions dedicated to astronomical observation.			
Capabilities	<p>Astro GC organizes astronomy workshops, consisting of an excursion from Maspalomas and other tourist sites in Gran Canaria, to mountainous areas in the west of Gran Canaria with low light pollution, where its qualified professional staff show participants galaxies, stellar cumuli, nebulae, planets, etc. During the workshops, high-powered telescopes are used to provide clear, bright images, with at least one telescope for every 8 participants.</p> <p>During the workshops, explanations will be given about how telescopes work and some of the fundamental mechanisms of the Universe, as well as basic concepts for reading the sky. The workshops include a pick-up service.</p> <p>They also organize group astrotourism excursions.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Briel Bikes, Avenida Alejandro del Castillo, Urbanización Zafiro, 2000, 7 Local, 35100 Maspalomas, Las Palmas		
	Telephone	(+34) 663 32 29 93		
	Mail	astrogc.mail@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.astrogc.com/index-es.html		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Astrogc/?locale=es_ES	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/astrogc/top/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/astrogc	
	LinkedIn	-		

Business name	Gran Canaria Astronomy Association – AAGC	Logo	
Company name	Gran Canaria Astronomy Association – AAGC		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Gran Canaria)		
Type of service	La Agrupación Astronómica de Gran Canaria (AAGC) is a non-profit cultural association formed by people who feel curiosity and admiration for the nature of the Universe and all that constitutes it, and which is dedicated to scientific and technical research in astronomy and the organization of astronomical events.		
Skills	<p>The aim of the AAGC is to promote activities based on the contemplation, photography and study of the Universe, with the objective of the social work of disseminating scientific culture, acting as a source of non-formal education, which extends and complements the formal education imparted in conventional study centres. To this end, it promotes the learning of its members, in which each one builds their own path of astronomical knowledge.</p> <p>The association works in different fields and disciplines of astronomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Minor Planets (Comets and Asteroids). – Meteors. – Astrophotography. – Cosmology. – Archaeoastronomy. – Planetary. – Study of variables. – Supernovas. – Etc. 		
Capabilities	<p>In line with its aims, the AAGC promotes various activities for the dissemination and contemplation of astronomy:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exhibitions. • Observation of the stars. • Conferences and exhibitions in cultural centres. • Campaigns to observe astronomical events. • Courses. <p>In order to carry out these activities, the members of the grouping have advanced equipment, such as CCD cameras that make it possible to take very precise astrometric and photometric measurements, and telescopes with remarkable apertures that provide observations of great range and resolution.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Diseminado El Montañón - Finca no 6 del I.G.B. "Cortijo de la Avejerilla", Vega de San Mateo, Las Palmas de Gran Canarias.	
	Telephone	(+34) 645 50 52 85	
	Mail	aagc.contacto@gmail.com	

Information resources	Web	http://www.aagc.es	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/aagc1990
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/aagc.oagc/?hl=es
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/AAGC_OAGC
		LinkedIn	-

Business name	Canary Islands Observatories (OCAN)	Logo	
Company name	Canary Islands Observatories (OCAN)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Europea		
Type of service	<p>The Canary Islands Observatories (OCAN), which include the Roque de los Muchachos Observatory (ORM) in La Palma and the Teide Observatory (OT) in Tenerife, house the telescopes and instruments of some 60 institutions belonging to more than 20 countries. It is the largest collection of facilities for optical and infrared observations for astrophysics in the European Union. Various high-energy astrophysics experiments and the study of the cosmic microwave background complete the battery of facilities available at the observatories.</p> <p>The excellent astronomical quality of the Canary Islands sky, characterized in detail and protected by law, makes these observatories an "astronomical reserve" located in Spain and open to the international scientific community since the signing of the International Treaty for Cooperation in Astrophysics.</p>		
Skills	<p>The mission of the Canary Islands Observatories, considered to be unique scientific and technical infrastructures, is to provide and support cutting-edge facilities for carrying out frontier research in the sciences of the Universe, guaranteeing the best natural, technological and logistical conditions, while fostering a fruitful framework for international collaboration.</p>		
Capabilities	<p>The Canary Islands Observatories aim to become one of the best astronomical reserves in the world, promoting the installation and operation of top-level research infrastructures, enabling the Spanish scientific community to strengthen its leadership in astrophysics and fostering synergies with other major research infrastructures.</p> <p>Among the infrastructures available are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design and development structures and services (optical systems, laser communications, electronics, computer control applications, cryogenic, mechanical, etc.) • Various installations of large telescopes. • Over 200 pieces of equipment in optics, cryogenics, electronics, mechanics, software, metrology, biomedicine, communications, etc. • Laboratories (Optics, electromagnetism, imaging and sensors, metrology, electronic design, mechanical testing, photonics, optoelectronics, microwaves, etc.) • Workshops and rooms (electronics, design, maintenance, mechanical, aluminized, anodized, integration and verification of large instruments, etc.) 		
Contact details	Direction	-	
	Telephone	(+34) 922 605 200 / (+34) 922 605 199	

Information resources	Mail	otai@iac.es		
	Web	https://www.iac.es/es/observatorios-de-canarias		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/InstitutoDeAstrofisicadeCanarias	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/iac_astrofisica/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/IAC_Astrofisica	
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/instituto-de-astrofisica-de-canarias		

Business name	Asociación Astronómica y Educativa de Canarias – AAEC		Logo	
Company name	Asociación Astronómica y Educativa de Canarias "Henrietta Swan Leavitt"			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)			
Type of service	A scientific-cultural association with an educational and research vocation whose main objective is to promote scientific-technical, socio-humanistic and artistic vocations from Astronomy.			
Skills	The association aims to boost scientific-technical skills and activities among young Canarians, make the work of historical and present scientists visible and help materialize future vocations and professions in the Canary Islands.			
Capabilities	<p>The association's activities are based on the development of its own and collaborative research projects carried out within a framework of action that aims for a transversal and holistic approach that promotes critical thinking combined with the scientific method. This methodology allows for the development of vocational skills in different educational and cultural contexts, always under supportive attitudes that also promote inclusion. All this, with special sensitivity to the crucial and silenced role of women throughout humanity in all areas of knowledge related to Astronomy, considering a pragmatic point of view.</p> <p>On the other hand, the functioning of the association is based on the development, continuous and collaborative training of its members, both in person and on online platforms.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	C/. Artemi Semidán, 3; C.P. 35460 Gáldar; Islas Canarias. Spain.		
	Telephone	-		
	Mail	aaec@astronomiayeducacion.org		
Information resources	Web	https://astronomiayeducacion.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/AAECCastro	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/aaec_astro/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/aaecastro	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Canarian Association of Active Tourism and Ecotourism Companies	Logo	
Company name	Canarian Association of Active Tourism and Ecotourism Companies		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Canary Islands)		
Type of service	Activa Canarias, is the organization representing companies and individuals dedicated to active tourism in the archipelago and which represents the Canary Islands at state level.		
Skills	<p>Activa Canarias brings together the main companies in the tourism sector in the Canary Islands, guaranteeing the criteria of Quality, Sustainability and Safety in its services, so that it has a direct impact on users.</p> <p>In addition, Activa Canarias represents and advises active tourism companies, and defends common business interests.</p> <p>The main leisure and sporting activities of the association are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multi-adventure events (zip line, archery, gymkhanas, abseiling, climbing wall, etc.). - Canoeing. - Bicycle. - Environmental education. - Climbing. - Adventure sports. 		
Capabilities	<p>The sector of nature activities, active tourism and adventure sports is regulated and there are regulations that must be complied with by the companies and promoters that provide these services.</p> <p>These promoters must ensure the quality of the service, user care and, above all, safety during the activity, by having qualified staff, using approved materials, knowing the techniques for their development and having the necessary means and guarantees to resolve any incidents during the activity.</p> <p>In this sense, the companies associated with Activa Canarias offer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Total guarantee in terms of security coverage, quality of service and customer satisfaction. - Official registration number that qualifies them as an Active Tourism service provider. - Technicians qualified for the activities they carry out. - Safety elements: communication, emergency protocols, approved and revised materials, equipment and knowledge of first aid... - Activity planning and forecasting. - Prior to practicing the activity, they will go over any self-protection and safety rules that may be necessary with their clients. - Adopt measures to preserve the environment and comply with environmental regulations. - Existence of a civil liability insurance policy and accident or assistance insurance, the risks of which include rescue costs. - Existence of complaint sheets. 		

Contact details	Direction	Avenida Primero de Mayo, 17, Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	
	Telephone	(+34) 928 91 51 33	
	Mail	info@activacanarias.org	
Information resources	Web	https://www.turismoactivocanarias.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/activacanarias
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/canarias_activa/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/Canarias_activa
	LinkedIn	-	

MADEIRA

Business name	Madeira Chamber of Commerce and Industry ACIF – CCIM	Logo	
Company name	Commercial and Industrial Association of Funchal - Madeira Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ACIF – CCIM)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>The Commercial and Industrial Association of Funchal - Madeira Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ACIF-CCIM) is an organization that offers services of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support for companies in the Trade, Industry, Tourism and Services sectors. ▪ Chamber of Commerce and Industry. ▪ Information and business support. ▪ Statistics. ▪ Certified and accredited training. ▪ Event organization. ▪ Protocols with benefits for members. ▪ Legal advice. ▪ Organization of business missions. ▪ Sectoral projects. ▪ Technical services. 		
Skills	<p>Among the skills associated with ACIF-CCIM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Internationalization. ▪ Research. ▪ Associations. ▪ Dissemination of European and International information linked to the sea. ▪ Sensitize companies to the importance of the ocean in the economy. 		
Capabilities	<p>ACIF-CCIM has the capacity to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organize marine research missions. ▪ Carrying out economic studies on the sea. J ▪ Organize awareness-raising days on the importance of the sea in the economy. ▪ Hold workshops with companies in the maritime sector. ▪ Promoting marine sustainability. ▪ Promote the creation of regional sea protection legislation. ▪ Statistical compilation of marine economic activities ▪ Development of European projects linked to maritime activity and nautical tourism. ▪ Planning training actions for good practices and better use of the ocean's potential. 		

Contact details	Direction	Rua dos Aranhas, 24-26, 9000-044, Funchal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 206 800		
	Mail	geral@acif-ccim.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.acif-ccim.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ACIF.CCIM/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/acifccim/	
		Twitter	https://www.youtube.com/user/ACIFccim	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/acif-ccim/	

Business name	Funchal Marina	Logo		
Company name	Funchal Marina			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Funchal - Madeira)			
Type of service	The Funchal Marina, located on the island of Madeira, is a space owned by the Madeira Port Authority and managed by the Clube Naval do Funchal and the Centro de Treino Mar, whose main objective is to provide sailors and boats with a range of basic support services.			
Skills	<p>Among the services offered by the Funchal Marina are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Management of the mooring reservation system. ▪ Water and electricity supply. ▪ Bone. ▪ Laundry. ▪ Nautical supplies shop. ▪ Candle repair services. ▪ Fuel supply. ▪ Restaurant and bar services. ▪ Corrections officer. ▪ 24-hour marina surveillance service. ▪ Environmental and technological management of the marina ▪ Promotion of marina services 			
Capabilities	<p>The Funchal Marina port is located in a protected area within Madeira's main port, 530 nautical miles from Lisbon and 36 nautical miles from Porto Santo.</p> <p>The infrastructure of the Funchal Marina has 210 yacht berths and a mooring area for boats engaged in nautical and recreational activities.</p> <p>The Marina has capacity to host international regattas.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Edif. Marina Club, Loja Clube - Av. Arriaga, 9000-000 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 912 304 508 / (+351) 291 232 717		
	Mail	geral@marinadofunchal.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.marinadofunchal.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/MarinaDoFunchal	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/marinadofunchal	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxCq_2Yqe_588SiKVLBxp0A	
LinkedIn		https://pt.linkedin.com/in/marina-funchal		

Business name	Clube Naval do Funchal	Logo		
Company name	Clube Naval do Funchal			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Funchal - Madeira)			
Type of service	The Club Naval do Funchal offers the following services: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Nautical training.• Sports activities, mainly of a nautical nature and the promotion and cultural, social, environmental, recreational and leisure satisfaction of its members (sailing, scuba diving, canoe, adapted sports, etc.).			
Skills	The Club Naval do Funchal has the following specific aims: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Promotion and practice of recreational and performance sports activities, both professionally and non-professionally, whether integrated or not into competitive frameworks, in the modalities of swimming, canoeing, judo, sailing, rowing, motor boating, gymnastics, karate, fishing and boating, among others.- Organization of sports competitions, training schools in the various sports disciplines and training to obtain nautical diplomas.- Organization of conferences and training sessions on sport, tourism and the environment.			
Capabilities	The Club has the capacity to organize and participate in activities, events and projects.			
Contact details	Direction	Rua da Quinta Calaça, nº 32, 9000-108, Funchal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 762 253		
	Mail	atendimento@clubenavaldofuncchal.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.clubenavaldofuncchal.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ClubeNavalFunchal	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/clubenavaldofuncchal/	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/CNFXPT	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/clubenavaldofuncchal	

Business name	University of Madeira – UMa	Logo	 UNIVERSIDADE da MADEIRA
Company name	University of Madeira		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>The University of Madeira (UMa) is a public education institution structured into various departments (student support services, administrative services, academic affairs, social action, cooperation and projects, employment centre, human resources and library).</p> <p>UMa has the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development of scientific research activities. ▪ Promoting the dissemination and social and economic valorisation of knowledge and technological innovation. ▪ Promoting and supporting actions and programs that contribute to the inclusion of its graduates in the world of work. ▪ Fostering the spirit of initiative and entrepreneurship, as well as the mobility of students and graduates, particularly in the European higher education space. 		
Skills	<p>UMa aims to find appropriate solutions that, within a framework of responsibility, equity and sustainability, contribute to the development and affirmation of Madeira in a globalized and dynamic world.</p> <p>UMa has two associated centres of interest to the project:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Center for Research, Development and Innovation in Tourism: CITUR-UMA 2.Astronomy: Group UMA 		
Capabilities	<p>UMa collaborates with the community, government bodies, companies, professional colleges and higher education and research institutions, discovering, disseminating and applying knowledge, training staff and carrying out research and development projects, as well as providing other services.</p> <p>It also develops a teaching and research policy considering the specificities of the Autonomous Community in which it operates, collaborating in the formulation of national and regional education, science and culture policies, and expressing opinions on the legislative projects that concern it. UMa is also an essential element in deepening the internationalization of the Madeira region, seeking to contribute to a greater connection with the diaspora and to the construction of the Lusophone space and the European space of education, science and culture. By its very nature and dynamics, UMa maintains a relationship of commitment and interdependence with the economic, social and cultural development of the Madeira region.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	University of Madeira - Campus Penteadá, Funchal, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 291 705 000	
	Mail	gcm@mail.uma.pt	

Information resources	Web	https://www.uma.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/UMaGIRP
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/universidadedamadeira/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/UMaGCM/
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/UMadeiraGIRP

Business name	Center for Research, Development and Innovation in Tourism - CiTUR-UMa	Logo	
Company name	University of Madeira		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>The Centre for Research, Development and Innovation in Tourism (CiTUR) is a Research and Development Unit born from the polytechnic subsystem of higher education in tourism and hospitality.</p> <p>In addition to the objectives common to all academia, polytechnics and university schools with a polytechnic matrix are expected to generate and disseminate knowledge that can be recognized by society and companies as applicable, in the sense that it can be listed for immediate use in production processes and/or social intervention.</p> <p>CiTUR's mission is the development of multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary applied research, the production and exchange of scientific knowledge in tourism.</p>		
Skills	<p>In terms of internal organization, CiTUR is structured into six regional hubs, based in Coímbra, Estoril, Faraón, Funchal, Guardia and Leiría. Based on this structure, the centre considers the following six thematic research groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tourism Economics and Management. ▪ Tourism, Hospitality and Catering. ▪ Electronic tourism. ▪ Territory and Tourist Destinations. ▪ Planning and Management of Tourism and Entertainment Products. ▪ Tourism, Culture, Society and Language. 		
Capabilities	<p>CiTUR is made up of 26 schools (universities and polytechnic institutes), in which around 200 researchers participate, approximately half of them "integrated".</p> <p>CiTUR's main objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Explore the benefits to be expected from an institution with real national reach. ▪ Regular involvement and participation in international networks, with special attention to those related to Europe and Portuguese-speaking countries. ▪ The promotion of a more relevant academic activity, increasing the quality of the various products that can characterize CiTUR's activity, namely the organization of events and scientific publications. ▪ Maintain a close relationship with the Network of Public Institutions of the Polytechnic Higher Education System with Careers in the Tourism Area (RIPTUR), taking advantage of the synergies that this proximity can bring to the achievement of the objectives of both structures. ▪ The use (and deepening) of the network of contacts formed by the different actors, public and private, who form part of the tourism and hospitality cluster, with the aim of adding value and carrying out applied and useful research. 		
Contact details	Direction	University of Madeira - Campus Penteadá, Funchal, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 291 705 000	

Information resources	Mail	citur@mail.uma.pt	
	Web	https://turismo.uma.pt/?page_id=959	
		https://citur-tourismresearch.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	-
		Instagram	-
Twitter		-	
YouTube		-	

Business name	Astronomy Group - UMA		Logo	
Company name	University of Madeira			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	The Astronomy Group of the University of Madeira has as its main objectives the Teaching, Research and Dissemination of Astronomy in the Autonomous Region of Madeira.			
Skills	The competences of the Astronomy Group of the University of Madeira are research in astronomical sciences and the dissemination of astronomical knowledge.			
Capabilities	<p>The Astronomy Group at the University of Madeira has participated in many astronomy research projects and has published more than a hundred scientific articles with the results of its research.</p> <p>It also has the capacity to teach courses on astronomy, as well as to organize science communication and dissemination events (more than 500 events have been held).</p> <p>The group has the infrastructure of the Astronomy and Instrumentation Laboratory (LAI), whose purpose is to support all the teaching and research activities of the Astronomy Group at the University of Madeira. It also has a large library and optical observation equipment.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Department of Mathematics - Faculty of Exact Sciences and Engineering, University of Madeira, Penteadá University Campus 9020-105, Funchal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 705 230 // (+351) 291 705 200		
	Mail	astro@uma.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://astro.web.uma.pt/Grupo/index.htm		
		https://www.uma.pt/investigacao/grupo-de-astronomia-da-universidade-da-madeira/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/astronomiamadeira	
		Instagram	-	
Twitter		-		

Business name	Portuguese Society for the Study of Birds - SPEA- Madeira		Logo	
Company name	Portuguese Society for the Study of Birds - SPEA- Madeira			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	The Portuguese Society for the Study of Birds (SPEA) is a non-governmental organization that works to protect Portuguese birds and the unique habitats on which they depend.			
Skills	SPEA focuses its activities mainly on observing and studying birds, as well as protecting them. It also carries out consulting and environmental education activities.			
Capabilities	<p>With the help of its members and volunteers, SPEA carries out the following activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Studying and monitoring the state of birds. ▪ Building nests. ▪ Elimination of invasive species. ▪ Promoting improvements in bird protection laws. ▪ Fighting environmental crimes. ▪ Environmental consultancy. ▪ Carrying out publicity and environmental education activities. ▪ Sale of didactic material centred on ornithological observation. <p>SPEA is a Portuguese member of BirdLife International.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Av. Almirante Gago Coutinho, 46A, Lisbon, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 919 382 722		
	Mail	spea@spea.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://spea.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/spea.Birdlife	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/spea_birdlife/?hl=pt	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/spea_birdlife	
	YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCG5grknj1ytOllsPHdhCLhA		

Business name	Port Authority of the Autonomous Region of Madeira – APRAM		Logo	
Company name	Administração dos Portos da Região Autónoma da Madeira S.A.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	The Port Administration of the Autonomous Region of Madeira (APRAM) is the company in charge of managing the port infrastructures of the Autonomous Region of Madeira, with the aim of guaranteeing the access and circulation of people and goods by sea, with quality, effectiveness and efficiency, both economic and operational, contributing to sustainable development.			
Skills	<p>APRAM carries out its functions as a port authority based on four pillars:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Quality: Striving for excellence in performance, striving daily to provide a qualified service, based on existing media and technology. ▪ Safety: Ensuring the safety of human life, the preservation of the environment and marine ecosystems and the protection of property. ▪ Attitude: Acting in an articulated manner, with the contribution of employees, to fulfil the organization's mission and meet the expectations of all members. ▪ Innovation: Encouraging and rewarding innovation, creativity and proactivity in the life of the organization, in order to ensure the sustained development of the business. 			
Capabilities	<p>Among the activities carried out by APRAM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Managing Madeira's entire port activity. ▪ Implementing port security. ▪ Collaborate in the management and execution of port projects. ▪ Provide advice to companies and entities operating in the region's ports. ▪ Environmental control in the port environment. 			
Contact details	Direction	Gare Marítima do Porto do Funchal, 9004-518, Funchal, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 208 600		
	Mail	portosdamadeira@apram.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.apram.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/apram.pt/?locale=pt_BR	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/portosdamadeira/?hl=es	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/portosdamadeira?lang=es	

		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCRuqKxbgkYHaPf2ZWpu69w
--	--	---------	---

Business name	Regional Development Institute IP - RAM	Logo	
Company name	Regional Development Institute IP - RAM		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>The Instituto de Desenvolvimento Regional IP-RAM (IDR) is an organization of the regional public administration of Madeira whose mission is to coordinate the planning and monitoring activities of the regional development model, as well as the coordination and management of the intervention of Community funds in the Autonomous Region of Madeira.</p>		
Skills	<p>The IDR's responsibilities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Analyse global economic and social developments, in general, and community and national developments, in particular, and monitor foresight studies carried out in the respective field. ▪ Analyse and follow the economic and social evolution of the region, identifying the main obstacles, study the prospects for development, in close connection with other services of the regional administration and with interested entities dedicated to the study of the problems of sustainable regional development. ▪ Developing the necessary studies to support and formulate proposals for the main lines of the development strategy, integrating and articulating sectoral and spatial policies, to draw up regional plans. ▪ Coordinate and prepare the final version of the regional plans, articulating the actions envisaged in them in collaboration with the bodies of the various regional secretariats and other entities involved. ▪ Coordinating the process of drawing up annual and medium-term plans. ▪ Monitoring the implementation of economic and social development policy and evaluating its sectoral and spatial repercussions. ▪ Prepare and draft the technical proposal for the Regional Administration's Investment and Development Expenditure Plan (PIDDAR) and monitor and evaluate its implementation. ▪ Prepare the framework for sectoral economic development plans and programs and evaluate their socio-economic impact. ▪ Establish the necessary connection with regional development planning bodies and cooperate with other entities within the scope of their activities. ▪ Ensure that the region is represented in national planning bodies. ▪ Ensuring proper coordination in the application of Community funds in the Madeira region. ▪ Carrying out technical and administrative functions inherent to coordinating the management, monitoring and evaluation of operational programs. ▪ To act as regional interlocutor for the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund (ESF) and the Cohesion Fund, before the national authorities and the European Commission, within the scope of its competencies and within the framework of representation mechanisms before these bodies. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ensure payment and certification functions for cooperation programs, within whose spatial scope the Autonomous Region of Madeira is integrated. ▪ Ensure the representation of the region in the bodies of the National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) in cases where these competencies are assigned to it. ▪ Ensure technical, administrative and financial support functions for actions co-financed by the ERDF, the Cohesion Fund and the ESF. ▪ Contribute to the definition of the general guidelines of the Structural Funds and to the effectiveness of the respective operational interventions. ▪ Contribute to the definition and standardization of access and management standards related to community support, in compliance with the norms and guidelines issued by the competent bodies. ▪ Ensure compliance with national and Community regulations applicable to Community funds in the field of information and publicity. ▪ Ensure efficient information systems for monitoring the interventions of the Community funds in the Madeira Autonomous Region, which allow the collection and processing of physical and financial indicators necessary for the management and evaluation of the support provided. ▪ Support the intermediary bodies for the management of operational interventions and their respective technical support structures, both in the training of their technicians and in the development of activities and/or the resolution of more complex issues. ▪ Ensure support for missions promoted by national and community bodies, within the scope of interventions co-financed with community funds. ▪ Promote the development of studies that are necessary for the proper application of Community funds in the Autonomous Region of Madeira and, when necessary, propose measures to support regional economic activity, participate in and monitor their application and evaluate their impact. ▪ Promote the evaluation of the impact and effects of the application of development instruments, in particular interventions co-financed by Community funds, in close coordination with the entities most directly involved. ▪ Promote the dissemination of studies and work carried out within the scope of its competencies or with its collaboration. ▪ Carry out other duties legally assigned to them. 		
Capabilities	The IDR has the necessary capacities to be able to manage and coordinate all the planning and follow-up activities of the regional development model, as well as the rest of the responsibilities that have been assigned to it.		
Contact details	Direction	Travessa do Cabido, 16, Funchal, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 291 214 000	
	Mail	idr@madeira.gov.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://www.idr.madeira.gov.pt/portal/Principal.aspx	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/idrmadeira
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/idrmadeira/
	Twitter	-	

		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC1K800z_rwo7bf9RcW5Yp_g
--	--	---------	---

Business name	Business Development Institute IDE - RAM	Logo	
Company name	Business Development Institute IDE - RAM		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	The Business Development Institute (IDE) - RAM is the coordinating body for all support for the secondary and tertiary sectors of the economy of the Autonomous Region of Madeira.		
Skills	<p>IDE focuses its activity on the integrated management of support instruments for the business sector, particularly about Investment, Financing and Operation.</p> <p>Effectively boosting the sustained growth of the regional economy, it focuses on the following areas of activity, among others:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Entrepreneurship. ▪ Business Innovation. ▪ Technological Development. ▪ Knowledge Society. ▪ Information and Communication Technologies. ▪ Quality, Environment and Energy. ▪ Internationalization. ▪ Capture. ▪ Investment structuring. ▪ Creating an environment for financial innovation and compensation for cost overruns. 		
Capabilities	IDE is one of the main instruments for operationalizing the economic, social and territorial development strategy of the Autonomous Region of Madeira for the 2030 horizon and its macro programming (Madeira 2030) reflects interventions guided by the objectives and goals of the cohesion policy and the main regional sectoral strategies and plans, in line with the European Pillar of Social Rights, the European Ecological Pact and the New European Bauhaus.		
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Arriaga nº 77, Edifício Marina Fórum , 4º andar, sala 403 9000-060, Funchal, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 291 202 170	
	Mail	ide@madeira.gov.pt	
Information resources	Web	http://www.ideram.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ideram.pt/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ideipram/
	Twitter	https://twitter.com/ideram	

		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCb_CI23a_hWha7K65FIBa6g
--	--	---------	---

Business name	Madeira Development Company - SDM	Logo	
Company name	Sociedade de Desenvolvimento da Madeira, S.A.		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>Sociedade de Desenvolvimento da Madeira (SDM) is the public company responsible, on behalf of the Regional Government of Madeira, for the management, administration and promotion of the Madeira International Business Centre (IBC), which currently comprises three investment sectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Industrial Free Trade Zone - The International Maritime Registry -MAR - International Services <p>SDM's mission is to contribute to the development, modernization and internationalization of Madeira and its economy through the IBC of Madeira, an effective instrument for attracting investment to the region.</p>		
Skills	<p>SDM competencies are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Incorporation of Companies. ▪ International Services. ▪ Electronic and technological commerce. ▪ Industry and storage. ▪ Registration of bouquets. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Boats and shipping companies. - Yachts and rental companies. ▪ Advice on tax benefits. ▪ Management and communication with co-respondents abroad. ▪ Promotional activities. ▪ Support services. ▪ Advice on legislation. 		
Capabilities	<p>SDM's responsibilities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The issuing of licenses for the installation and operation of companies in the IBC of Madeira, prior to the granting of the license for the activity by the Regional Government of Madeira. ▪ The construction of infrastructure in the Madeira Industrial Free Trade Zone. ▪ International market promotion. ▪ Management of the Wooden Goods Register - MAR ▪ Collaboration with Regional and National Governments in defining the terms on which the IBC's implementation and development should take place. ▪ The management of the annual task collection and installation fees owed to the Autonomous Region of Madeira by installed companies and registered vessels. ▪ Other IBC services related to operational, commercial, legal and regulatory aspects. 		

	At present, SDM has a team of around 30 professionals working in the Madeira workshops. Outside Portugal, an efficient network of correspondents covers the main international markets, which allows SDM to better understand the specificities and particular needs of these markets and to provide potential investors and consultants with local personal contact.			
Contact details	Direction	Edifício SDM, Rua da Mouraria 9, 1.er piso, 9000-047, Funchal, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 201 333		
	Mail	sdm@sdm.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.ibc-madeira.com/pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/sociedadesdesenvolvimento/?locale=sw_KE&_rdr	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/sociedadesdesenvolvimento/?locale=es_ES%2F	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/ibcmadeira	

Business name	Madeira Nautical Association – ANM		Logo	 Associação Náutica da Madeira
Company name	Madeira Nautical Association			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	<p>La Asociación Náutica de Madeira (ANM) is an organization dedicated to promoting sport among its members and the rest of the population of Madeira, developing training activities in the field of water sports, especially through its sailing school, promoting sailing courses for all ages.</p> <p>The ANM's mission is to make its activities a clear added value, both in the social and sporting spheres, optimizing the resources available to promote sporting and recreational practice in the nautical sphere, promoting its activities among the public, especially young people, and making the best possible use of the natural resources available from the sea.</p>			
Skills	<p>The ANM's activities focus on the organization and development of training courses and water sports competitions such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sail. ▪ Kayak. ▪ Canoeing ▪ Surfing and windsurfing ▪ Sport fishing. 			
Capabilities	<p>The ANM currently has around a hundred players, at children's, youth, junior, senior and master's level, who compete in local, national and international sailing championships.</p> <p>Its sailing school trains sailors in the Optimist, Europa, 420, Snipe, Match Racing and Cruising classes, becoming a benchmark institution in the region, with participation in European and World Championships.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Asociación Náutica de Madeira, Centro Náutico São Lázaro Hangar 8 Avenida Sá Carneiro, 9000-017, Funchal - Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 617 506 // (+351) 915 208 685		
	Mail	anm@anm.pt		
Information resources	Web	http://www.anm.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Associa%C3%A7%C3%A3o-N%C3%A1utica-da-Madeira-ANM/100067977674566/	

Business name	Porto Santo Sub		Logo	
Company name	Porto Santo Sub			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Porto Santo Sub is a scuba diving centre located in Poto Santo, with daily departures and offering recreational buceo training courses and other nautical sports.			
Skills	Porto Santo Sub's activity is centered on the following fishing activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Snorkel • Scuba diving • Paddle • Kayak 			
Capabilities	<p>Porto Santo Sub organizes maritime-tourist activities related to nautical sports, as well as offering scuba diving courses of different levels and specialties. They also have a recreational nautical school where they teach courses to obtain different sailing licenses and charters.</p> <p>They have a fully equipped centre for recreational, technical and rebreather boating, as well as 2 semi-rigid boats.</p> <p>They also offer a wide range of bushcraft equipment on a rental basis.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Estrada Jorge de Freitas - Penedo, Porto Santo - Madeira, 9400-240 Porto Santo, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 916 033 997		
	Mail	info@portosantosub.com		
Information resources	Web	https://portosantosub.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/PortoSantoSubCentroDeMergulho/?ref=bookmarks	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/explore/tags/portosantosub/	
		Twitter	-	
YouTube		https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCi_jXFZhaxkCZ0CoJR9bCRg?view_as=subscriber		

Business name	Mr.Humb Jet Fun	Logo	
Company name	Mr. Humb, Unipessoal Lda		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	Mr.Humb Jet Fun is a water sports company based on the island of Porto Santo, which acquires water bikes, water ski boards, kayaks, hydrofoils and water bicycles, as well as drag floats.		
Skills	<p>Mr.Humb Jet Fun's activity is focused on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Jet ski ▪ Kayak. ▪ Flyboard. ▪ Wakeboarding. ▪ Hydropedal. ▪ Aquatic cycling. ▪ Motorboat navigation. 		
Capabilities	<p>Mr.Humb Jet Fun offers watercraft rental services, as well as protection and safety equipment. They also offer rental services for canopies and canopies.</p> <p>They also offer guided excursions on watercraft around the bay and islands of Porto Santo. They also take dinghy trips and organize leisure and recreational aquatic activities.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Porto Santo beach, next to Pé na Água restaurant 9400-001 Porto Santo	
	Telephone	(+351) 965 661 409 / (+351) 961 890 056	
	Mail	mrhumbjetfun@gmail.com	
Information resources	Web	-	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/jetskiwatersports/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/mr.humb.jet.fun2024/?locale=fr_CA&hl=af
	Twitter	-	
YouTube	-		

Business name	VMT Madeira - Catamaran Trip		Logo	
Company name	VMT Madeira			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	VMT Madeira is a company that carries out tourist and whale watching excursions along the coast of Madeira.			
Skills	<p>VMT Madeira offers services centred on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cetacean watching. ▪ Kayak. ▪ Paddle. ▪ Scuba diving. ▪ Visits to islands. ▪ Marine excursions. ▪ Environmental awareness. ▪ Sport fishing. 			
Capabilities	<p>VMT Madeira owns three catamarans for the development of maritime tourism activities. Because they carry out maritime-tourism activities in a sustainable way, such as whale watching, each of the catamarans is considered an ecotourism vessel and has the Blue Flag award.</p> <p>All the boats have motors and sails for an even more relaxing trip, thus eliminating engine noise and reducing CO2 emissions. All the boats also have covered areas with seats, bow stools that serve as a solarium, bathrooms and a bar with all kinds of drinks and snacks.</p> <p>The company also offers a free awareness program on good practices related to the environment and marine life.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Do Mar Praça do Povo - Cais 8 9000-079 Funchal Madeira - Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351)963 796 860		
	Mail	info@vmtmadeira.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.vmtmadeira.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/vmtmadeira	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/vmtmadeira/?locale=es_ES%2F	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/vmt_madeira	
YouTube		https://www.youtube.com/user/madeiracatamaran		

Business name	Nautisantos	Logo		
Company name	Nautisantos - Atividades Desportivas, Lda.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Nautisantos is a company that offers nautical chartering services focused on deep-sea fishing.			
Skills	<p>Nautisantos' competencies can be summarized as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sport fishing. ▪ Marine excursions. ▪ Private carter. ▪ Observing cetaceans and turtles. 			
Capabilities	<p>Nautisantos offers its clients two boats fully equipped with all the fishing, electronic and safety equipment.</p> <p>They also have a catamaran for sea excursions.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Marina do Funchal - 9000-055 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 231 312 - (+351) 919 916 221		
	Mail	nautisantos@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.nautisantos.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/seaborncatamaran/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/seaborncatamaran/	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	-	

Business name	Nomad Response Lda (Madeira Free Trade Zone)	Logo	-	
Company name	Nomad Response Lda			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Nomad Response is a company located in the Madeira Free Trade Zone dedicated to consulting and business management activities.			
Skills	<p>The company's competencies are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Corporate promotion and marketing activities.▪ Market research studies.▪ Market analysis for major and minor trading.▪ Advice on imports and exports.▪ Provision of accounting and economic services.▪ Management of your portfolio of values.▪ Activities of acquisition, sale and any other form of exploitation of trademarks, patents and copyrights.			
Capabilities	The company offers technical consulting activities for the creation, development, expansion and modernization of industrial, commercial and service companies at an international level.			
Contact details	Direction	Estrada José Avelino Pinto, Apartamento Oceano 3.º Andar, F 9125-024 Caniço.		
	Telephone	-		
	Mail	-		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
YouTube		-		

Business name	Sea La Vie - Madeira Yacht & Sailing Charter	Logo		
Company name	Sea La Vie - Madeira Yacht & Sailing Charter			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Sea La Vie is a chauffeur service and nautical excursion company that offers well-structured tours around the beautiful south coast of Madeira Island, the Desertas Islands and Porto Santo.			
Skills	<p>Sea La Vie's activities focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Private excursions on canvas. ▪ Private tea management. 			
Capabilities	<p>The company Sea La Vie has several sailboats for rental and excursions.</p> <p>They also have a wide range of excursion options available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dawn or dusk. • Half day or full day. • Ponta de São Lourenço. • Desert Islands. • Garajaú Marina Reserve. • Puerto Santo. <p>All trips include snacks and appetizers.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Praça do Povo, 9000-900 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 965 710 036		
	Mail	mailtohola@sealaviemadeira.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.sealaviemadeira.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Sealaviemadeira	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/sealavie_madeira/	
		Twitter	-	
YouTube		-		

Business name	Happy Hour - Madeira Sailing Charter	Logo		
Company name	Happy Hour - Madeira Sailing Charter			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Happy Hour is a boat excursion and sailboat rental agency based in Funchal, which offers authentic and exclusive experiences, far from the traditional tourist routes.			
Skills	The competences of the Happy Hour company are the rental of sailing boats and the organization of nautical excursions along the coast of Madeira.			
Capabilities	<p>Happy Hour offers private boat trips to enjoy a personalized tour, away from the crowds and in total privacy, with quality service on board guaranteed by their crew, with food and drink included. They also offer the possibility of snorkelling on the high seas.</p> <p>They have three sails and a motor yacht.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Marina do Funchal, 9000-055 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 938 173 229		
	Mail	geral@happyhourmadeira.com		
Information resources	Web	https://happyhourmadeira.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/happyhourmadeira	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/happyhourmadeira/	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/@happyhourmadeira7791?app=desktop	

Business name	Magic Dolphin: Madeira Dolphin & Whale Watching	Logo	
Company name	Magic Dolphin Lda		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>Magic Dolphin is a family-run company specializing in ecological boat tours to see dolphins, whales, turtles and endemic birds from the south coast of Madeira.</p> <p>The company's mission is to be a leading dolphin and pelagic sighting company in Madeira and to support ocean conservation.</p>		
Skills	<p>Magic Dolphin's objectives can be summed up simply as limiting the effects of its activities on the environment and, at the same time, actively participating in the improvement of the Madeira biome.</p> <p>To do so:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organizes low environmental impact marine wildlife viewing tours. ▪ It promotes nautical ecotourism. ▪ Help with ocean conservation. ▪ It carries out environmental awareness and dissemination activities. ▪ Collaborates in marine research. 		
Capabilities	<p>Magic Dolphin offers excursions along the south coast of Madeira, both group and private, aimed at spotting dolphins, whales and bird's endemic to the area.</p> <p>The company focuses its efforts on continually improving its operations to ensure a non-invasive approach to its tours, using an Eco Catamaran equipped with electric/hybrid motors for silent, low-emission sailing. They also have a motor speedboat and a sailing boat.</p> <p>In addition, they collaborate with researchers on studies focused on different challenges and solutions to protect Madeira's ocean environment.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Magic Dolphin, Praca do Povo, Av. Do Mar, 9000-900 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 925 680 587	
	Mail	info@magic-dolphin.com	
Information resources	Web	https://magic-dolphin.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/magicdolphinmadeira/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/magicdolphinmadeira/?hl=en
	Twitter	-	

Business name	Green Storm	Logo		
Company name	GREEN STORM - Náutica e Empreendimentos Turísticos Unipessoal, Lda			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Green Storm is a family-run yacht rental company with a business model inspired by its ancestors and traditional Portuguese fishermen and sailors.			
Skills	The company's activity focuses on offering yacht rental services and organizing nautical excursions along the coast of Madeira Island.			
Capabilities	<p>The company offers various types of excursions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One-day trip (6 hours). - Half-day excursion (4 hours). - Morning excursion (2 hours). - Evening excursion (2 hours). <p>They also offer the option of renting the yacht for days or weeks.</p> <p>They have a newly refurbished yacht with three cabins, with capacity for up to 8 people and equipped with all kinds of amenities.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Marina do Funchal, 9000-055 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 963 469 557		
	Mail	vascobraz@greenstorm.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://greenstorm.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/GreenStorm.pt/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/yachtmadeira/	
		Twitter	-	
YouTube		-		

Business name	Aquadelic Visions	Logo		
Company name	Visões Aquadélicas - Actividades Marítimo Turísticas, Lda.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Visões Aquadélicas is a company based in Funchal dedicated to coastal and local transportation services for travellers.			
Skills	Visões Aquadélicas focuses its activity on tourist entertainment and the exploration of maritime tourist activities, specifically: <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Excursions and sightseeing tours by boat.▪ Sport fishing.▪ Purchase and sale of fishing equipment and supplies.▪ Sale of all types of nautical equipment.▪ Provision of services related and complementary to its main activity (operation of takeaway restaurants, bars, cafeterias, beverage establishments...etc.).			
Capabilities	-			
Contact details	Direction	Travessa Do Pilar, Lote 6 - R/c Dt 9000, Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	-		
	Mail	aquadelic.visions@netmadeira.com		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	-	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
YouTube		-		

Business name	Ventura - Nature Emotions		Logo	
Company name	Ventura - Nature Emotions			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Ventura - Nature Emotions is a nature tourism company based on the island of Madeira focused on organizing sustainable sightings of dolphins, dolphins and birds, as well as excursions by semi-rigid speedboat or sailing boat and other outdoor activities on the island.			
Skills	Ventura - Nature Emotions' activities focus on offering boat rental services and organizing whale watching excursions along the coast of Madeira.			
Capabilities	<p>Ventura - Nature Emotions offers various types of group tours:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Excursions on a semi-rigid speedboat: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ballena and dolphin spotting excursion. - Swimming excursion with dolphins. ▪ Sailing boat excursions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ballena and dolphin spotting excursion. - Excursions at dusk or dawn. - Excursion to Fajã dos Padres and the south coast of Madeira. - Tour of several Madeira bays. - Excursion to the Desert Islands. <p>It also offers a private tea service.</p> <p>The company also organizes excursions to inland areas of Madeira focused on observing bird's endemic to the island and the Macaronesian region.</p> <p>In order to offer these services, the company has a classic sailboat, two rigid pneumatic motorboats and a yacht.</p> <p>They also have a team of highly motivated, professional and experienced people (marine biologists, guides, tour guides) who help to create a pleasant atmosphere during their activities.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Cais 8, Marina do Funchal, 9000-055 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 914 843 205 (+351) 963 691 995		
	Mail	reservas@venturadomar.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.venturadomar.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Ventura-Nature-Emotions/100078808416396/	

		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/venturanaturemotions/?locale=es_ES
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/venturadomar?lang=es
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCmEXYZrHxeWg_Ep8s9YQKw

Business name	Gavião Madeira - Sailing Trips		Logo	
Company name	Gavião Madeira - Sailing Trips			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Gavião Madeira - Sailing Trips is a company that organizes yacht excursions around the archipelago of Madeira.			
Skills	The company's activities focus on organizing coastal excursions and observing marine fauna.			
Capabilities	<p>The company offers group excursions along the south coast of Madeira and cruises and expeditions to the Desertas Islands, as well as high-sea trips to spot dolphins, whales, sea lions and turtles.</p> <p>It also offers private teas, kayak tours and submarine trips.</p> <p>The company has a yacht with capacity for 20 people and 2 crew members. The boat is equipped with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bar service • Appetizers • Gowns and towels • 2 bathrooms • Air conditioning • High quality sound system 			
Contact details	Direction	Marina do Funchal, 9000-054 Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 291 241 124 / (+351) 919 587 915		
	Mail	gaviaomadeira@netmadeira.com office@gaviaomadeira.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.gaviaomadeira.com/pt/home/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/gaviao.madeira/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/sailinggaviaomadeira/?hl=es	
	Twitter	-		
YouTube	-			

Business name	VIP Dolphins		Logo	
Company name	Oceano Pioneiro Unipessoal Lda			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	VIP Dolphins is a boat excursion agency on the coast of Madeira based in Funchal.			
Skills	<p>The company's activities focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organization of marine excursions. ▪ Marine fauna observation tours. ▪ Management of a private catamaran rental service. 			
Capabilities	<p>VIP Dolphins offers services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Guided sea excursions along the coast of Madeira. ▪ Sighting tours of dolphins, whales and turtles ▪ Photographic report. ▪ Private tea service. <p>They have a catamaran where they offer free bar service and snacks, towels, snorkelling equipment and a photo reporting service.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Do Mar, Funchal, 9000, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 924 438 001		
	Mail	oceanopioneiro@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.vipdolphins.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/vipdolphins	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/vipdolphins/	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	-	

Business name	Madeira Sea Fishing	Logo		
Company name	Madeira Sea Fishing			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	Sport fishing charter company in Madeira from Funchal.			
Skills	The company offers trips mainly to fish for Tuna, Marlin, Mahi Mahi, Mero, Pargo, Pez Espada, Wahoo and Amberjack, depending on the day and conditions. The techniques you can use include light and heavy tackle, bottom fishing, big game fishing, trolling, jigging, spinning and popping.			
Capabilities	They have a fishing boat with capacity for up to 8 people, fully equipped with rods, reels, seines, tackle and other fishing tools, and with a license to fish at height. Snorkelling equipment is also available.			
Contact details	Direction	Funchal, Madeira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 963 756 868		
	Mail	madeira.seafishing19@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/madeiraseafishing	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/madeira.seafishing/?hl=es	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	-	

Business name	Madeira Astronomy Association - AAM	Logo		
Company name	-			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Madeira)			
Type of service	<p>The Madeira Astronomy Association (AAM) is a research group that focuses on astronomical research and space observation.</p> <p>The main purpose of the AAM is to promote the study of astronomical sciences in the Madeira region and to act as a meeting point for astronomy enthusiasts from the region.</p>			
Skills	The AAM's activities focus on organizing open-air meetings for observing astronomical phenomena, as well as disseminating knowledge about astronomy.			
Capabilities	<p>AAM has sufficient capacity to participate in transnational projects, such as ERASMUS+.</p> <p>They have various telescopes and equipment for space observation.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Casa do Arieiro, Funchal, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 912 299 244		
	Mail	aam@astronomiamadeira.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.astronomiamadeira.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/astronomiamadeira	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		YouTube	-	

AZORES

Business name	Regional Directorate for Maritime Policy – DRPM	Logo	GOVERNO DOS AÇORES
Company name	Regional Directorate for Maritime Policy		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The mission of the Regional Directorate for Maritime Policy (DRPM) is to support and promote the sustainable development of the seas of the Azores and its coastline, contributing to the blue economy and the definition of regional policy for the economic and environmental enhancement of the region's maritime space, in particular through its planning, the promotion of greater knowledge about the marine environment, the granting of licenses for the uses of the sea, including maritime tourism activities, as well as the adoption of measures to guarantee the preservation of the environment.</p> <p>Its main objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Getting the Azores Marine Park up and running. ▪ Finalize the Azores Maritime Spatial Planning Plan on the basis of solid scientific criteria. ▪ Contribute to the maintenance or restoration of the environmental quality of the sea. ▪ Generate new activities that use marine resources. ▪ Carry out the necessary coastal adaptations to climate change. ▪ Promoting an active and informed citizenry. 		
Skills	<p>The main competencies of the DRPM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formulating political priorities and strategies, as well as managing plans and projects related to regional, national and community policy. • Contribute to the formulation of regional guidelines within the framework of national or community policies. • Promote and manage the Azores Maritime Spatial Planning Situation Plan. • Exercising environmental authority in the marine environment. • Cooperating in the management of the maritime public domain. • Collaborate in the prevention of and fight against marine pollution. • Promote the economic and sustainable use of the sea, highlighting new activities. • Carrying out and supporting promotional activities, environmental education and technical dissemination in the marine field. • Promoting marine scientific research and innovation, proposing and implementing conservation and sustainability projects. • Coordinate the conservation of marine biodiversity and manage marine protected areas. • Promote the management and conservation of marine resources in collaboration with other entities. • Cooperate with the National Maritime Authority and other entities in the supervision of maritime activities. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the implementation of strategic guidelines on maritime space and the maritime economy. • Collaborate with other departments of the Regional Administration on issues of culture, maritime heritage, tourism, transport and the port sector. • Monitor coordination with regional, national, community and international organizations. • Manage maritime-tourism activities in cooperation with regional maritime transport, tourism and fisheries directorates, ensuring sustainability and granting licenses. 		
Capabilities	<p>The DRPM is responsible for identifying opportunities and needs and applying sustainable development techniques, i.e. basing action on the best available knowledge and maintaining a balance between the economy, society and the environment.</p> <p>Its services, among others, cover crucial areas such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maritime Licenses: Manages authorizations related to the Azores Maritime Spatial Planning Plan, the Maritime Public Domain and Maritime-Tourism activity. ▪ Protection and Conservation: Implement and strengthen marine protected areas, ensuring the conservation of marine ecosystems and species. 		
Contact details	Direction	Rua D. Pedro IV, n.º29, 9900-111 Horta, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 292 202 400	
	Mail	info.drpm@azores.gov.pt / maritimo-turisticas@azores.gov.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://portal.azores.gov.pt/web/drpm	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/MarPescasAcores/
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-

Business name	Ports of the Azores	Logo
Company name	Portos dos Açores, S. A.	
Type of organization		
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)	
Type of service	Puertos de Azores (PA) has as its object the administration of the commercial ports of the Autonomous Region of the Azores, with a view to their exploitation, conservation and development, encompassing the exercise of the powers and prerogatives of the assigned port authority.	
Skills	<p>PA's main mission is to play the role of port administration and authority in the Autonomous Region of the Azores, guaranteeing access and circulation of people and goods by sea, and contributing to the sustainable development of the region and the country.</p> <p>The PA values are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Customer orientation. • Striving for excellence. • Safety and health at work. • Transparency and ethics. • Inclusive practices. • Solidarity practices. • Valuing people and knowledge. • Social responsibility. • Defending the public interest. • Environmental responsibility. 	
Capabilities	<p>PA aims to be a port of excellence and a reference at regional, national and international level, taking advantage of the added geostrategic value of the archipelago in the Atlantic.</p> <p>The following ports, marinas and nautical recreation centres are the main infrastructures under PA jurisdiction:</p> <p>Doors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Port of Vila do Porto (Isla Santa María) • Puerto de Ponta Delgada (Isla de São Miguel) • Port of Praia da Vitória (Terceira Island) • Angra do Heroísmo Port - "Pipas" (Terceira Island) • Port of Praia da Graciosa (Isla Graciosa) • Calheta Harbour (São Jorge Island) • Port of Velas (São Jorge Island) • Puerto de Lajes do Pico (Isla del Pico) • Port of São Roque do Pico (Isla de Pico) • Port of Madalena (Isla del Pico) • Port of Horta (Faial Island) • Puerto de Lajes das Flores (Isla de Flores) • Puerto de Santa Cruz de las Flores (Isla de Flores) 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Porto do Corvo - "Casa" (Isla de Corvo) <p>Sports ports and nautical recreation centers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lajes das Flores nautical recreation center (Isla de Flores)• Puerto Deportivo de Horta (Faial Island)• Lajes do Pico nautical recreation center (Isla de Pico)• Marina Velas (São Jorge Island)• Angra do Heroísmo marina (Terceira Island)• Puerto deportivo de Ponta Delgada (São Miguel Island)• Vila do Porto Marina (Isla Santa María) <p>It also manages 2 boat terminals.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Av. Gago Coutinho e Sacadura Cabral n.º 7, 9900-062, Horta, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 292 208 300	
	Mail	geral@portosdosacores.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://portosdosacores.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/portosdosacores
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/portsazores/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/PortsAzores
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/portos-dos-a-ores-s-a/

Business name	Ponta Delgada Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCIPD)	Logo	
Company name	Ponta Delgada Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCIPD) - Business Association of the Islands of Sao Miguel and Santa Maria		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Sao Miguel and Santa Maria - Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Ponta Delgada Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCIPD) is a business organization that carries out activities related to commerce, industry, tourism and services and which has its domicile, headquarters or permanent representation on the islands of São Miguel and Santa Maria.</p> <p>The CCIPD takes on, as a priority, the role of representing and defending the interests of its members, promoting the economic activity of the Azores region and providing services.</p>		
Skills	<p>The main functions of the CCIPD include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To promote networking between companies and entrepreneurs, in order to facilitate the exchange of experiences and the doing of business. • Spreading business opportunities. • Defend the interests of its members and the business community in general, before public and private authorities. • Implement training plans for the business sector. • Economic, legal, fiscal and commercial consultancy. 		
Capabilities	<p>La CCIPD acts, on the one hand, as a social interlocutor in the defence of employers, intervening in the areas of collective bargaining and socio-labour issues, and, on the other hand, as a socio-economist in the follow-up and defence of issues that concern the interests of local economic agents in the Azores Autonomous Region.</p> <p>Some of the services offered by the CCIPD are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Professional and business training: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Study and diagnosis of companies' training needs. – Design, implementation and follow-up of training plans. – Organization of inter- and intra-company training actions. – Carrying out information and awareness-raising actions/seminars. ▪ Legal advice: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Legal advice on various aspects. – Industrial property - preparation and instruction of applications for registration of trademarks, logos, etc. – Request for certificate of admissibility of company name. – Instruction of permit processes for the civil construction and public works sector. – Collective bargaining. – Advising the labour conciliation and arbitration committee. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Dismantling of economic activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Holding economic activity fairs and exhibitions in the region, in Madeira, on the continent and abroad. – Organization of commercial missions. – Market information. – Provision of equipment, structures and human resources for holding events. – Promotional campaigns and actions. ▪ Economic area: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Economic and fiscal advice. – Statistical analysis. – Support and advice on investment incentives. ▪ Defending member activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Organization of specialized committees with the participation of members. – Collection of limitations and/or opportunities in economic sectors. – Taking public positions based on studies and technical opinions. ▪ Participation in holidays and events. ▪ We promote your company and your brand. 		
Contact details	Direction	Rua Ernesto do Canto, 13/15 9504-531, Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 296 305 000	
	Mail	geral@ccipd.pt	
Information resources	Web	www.ccipd.pt	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ccipd
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camaradocomercio/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/camaraponta
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccipd/	

Business name	Angra do Heroísmo Chamber of Commerce - CCAH	Logo	
Company name	Angra do Heroísmo Chamber of Commerce		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla Terceira - Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Angra do Heroísmo Chamber of Commerce's (CCAH) mission is to permanently monitor the labour market, the factor market, the institutional climate and the political scenario, from a perspective of uncompromising defence of the interests common to the business fabric it represents, promoting initiatives and developing activities capable of contributing to the competitiveness of companies and the geo-economic space in which they operate.</p>		
Skills	<p>The CCAH has set itself the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Representing companies and entrepreneurs. • Ensuring institutional relations and cooperation. • Consolidate the position of strategic partner with the Government, Local Authorities, other Associations and Companies. • Strengthen the capacity to intervene at the level of the socio-economic space in which it operates. • Califying the functional organization, promoting responsibility, professionalism and competence. • Encourage initiative, flexibility and productivity in the operational structure. • Improve the level of services provided and their adaptation to the needs of the business sector. • Improve the use of available resources within the scope of the Regional Operational Program and other measures or programs that can contribute to the co-financing of relevant initiatives or actions. • Ensure the exercise of the prerogatives derived from participation in external entities of an associative or other nature. • Comply with the obligations deriving from the position of Social Interlocutor and Chamber of Commerce. • To pursue any other objectives of interest to the members, proper to the Association and to the Autonomous Region of the Azores. 		
Capabilities	<p>The CCAH, through its projects and strategies, aims to consolidate itself as an organization with a strong capacity to anticipate the challenges facing businesses and the regional economy of the Azores in a context of accelerated processes of change, having the ability to identify threats and opportunities and promote sustainable development through efficient management and allocation of available or mobilized resources.</p> <p>At the same time, the CCAH is shaping up, on the scale of its surroundings, as a true skills centre, capable of speeding up responses to the processes of globalization and the challenges of the information society.</p> <p>Some of the services offered by the CCAH are:</p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Analysis of economic indicators.▪ Search for business opportunities and grants.▪ Support for the internationalization of companies.▪ Analysis of companies' training needs.▪ Organization and promotion of inter and intra-company professional training courses.▪ Holding workshops in training areas necessary for business activity.▪ Labor market management.▪ Information on current employment support measures.▪ Business support activities.▪ Dissemination of news relevant to the region's business sector.▪ Legal advice.			
Contact details	Direction	Rua da Palha nº 4-14, 9700-144, Angra do Heroísmo, Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 295 204 810		
	Mail	geral@ccah.eu		
Information resources	Web	https://www.ccah.eu/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/camaracomercioah	
		YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/user/camaracah	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/camara.comercio.angra.heroismo/?hl=es	
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/c%C3%A2m-ara-do-com%C3%A9rcio-de-angra-do-her%C3%ADsmo/?trk=biz-companies-cym		

Business name	Horta Chamber of Commerce and Industry - CCIH	Logo	
Company name	Horta Chamber of Commerce and Industry - Association of Merchants, Industrialists, Importers and Exporters of the Islands of Faial, Pico, Flores and Corvo		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Islands of Fayal, Pico, Flores and Corvo)		
Type of service	The Horta Chamber of Commerce and Industry (CCIH) is a business organization created to respond to the needs of entrepreneurs in the commercial and industrial sector based on the islands of Fayal, Pico, Flores and Corvo.		
Skills	<p>The ICHR has set itself the following objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Represent the interests of its members before the specific government bodies of the Region and the Republic, as well as other social interlocutors. • Propose and participate, together with official bodies, in the definition of economic policy for the sectors to which it belongs. • Proposing and participating in the development of classification and quality standards for products. • Coordinate and regulate the activities of the represented sectors and protect them against unfair competition practices or measures that negatively affect their interests. • Providing services in the field of foreign and domestic trade and export promotion, specifically by issuing certificates of origin. • Represent its members in national and international organizations, official or professional, of interest to the sectors it represents. • Representing the members in the discussion and approval of collective, conventional and administrative work rules and regulations, in all their scope, including the definition of workers' duties. • Create and/or join regional or national organizations with a vocation in the fields of training, research and economic development in general in order to provide guarantees and defend business interests and the regional economy. • Organize or cooperate in the celebration of conferences, congresses, exhibitions or commercial or industrial fairs, in the country and abroad. • Promote, organize and host commercial or industrial missions to and from abroad, with a view to expanding economic exchange in general. • Enter into protocols and agreements with other associations or organizations in order to defend the legitimate interests of members and promote the exchange of interests and information at all levels, being able to integrate into unions, federations and confederations with similar objectives. • To be represented on public bodies, when by law or by invitation, it is called upon to offer collaboration. • Promote the dissemination, through the appropriate media, of information, opinions and issues that are considered to be of interest to the members or of relevant interest to their economic activities. • Promote, by the means at its disposal and through appropriate media, training programs, cultural, material and professional development of its members. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intervene, when so requested, in commercial disputes between members, between members and others, or even between entities that are not member companies, with the possibility of creating an arbitration court for this purpose. • To keep its technical and legal guidance and consultation services structured so that they can be provided to all its members. • Promote the creation of favourable conditions for investment, contributing to so that you can move to more convenient areas. • To set up and administer funds in the terms established by law. • Supporting businesses in terms of vocational training, hygiene and food safety and hygiene and safety at work. • Promote any other activities aimed at defending the interests of the members who do not contravene the law or the provisions of the organization's statutes. 									
<p>Capabilities</p>	<p>The ICHR has a strong capacity to mobilize its members in various areas of the regional economy, and great efforts have been made to ensure that the chamber is increasingly functional and tailored to the needs of its members.</p> <p>The organization is structured as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fayal Business Centre <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Investment Project Analysis Workshop. – Food Safety and Quality Office. – Trade Fairs and Events Office – Legal Workshop. ▪ Pico Business Centre ▪ Flores y Corvo Business Centre. <p>Some of the services offered by the CCIH are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Search for business opportunities and grants. ▪ Organization and promotion of professional training courses. ▪ Holding workshops and events of interest to the region's business activity. ▪ Information on current employment support measures. ▪ Business support activities. ▪ Dissemination of news relevant to the region's business sector. ▪ Legal advice. ▪ Promote actions aimed at guaranteeing food hygiene and safety in the region. 									
<p>Contact details</p>	<p>Direction</p>	<p>Largo Duque de Ávila e Bolama, Horta, Azores, Portugal</p>								
	<p>Telephone</p>	<p>(+351) 292 202 320</p>								
	<p>Mail</p>	<p>ccih@ccihorta.pt</p>								
<p>Information resources</p>	<p>Web</p>	<p>https://ccihorta.wixsite.com/ccihorta</p>								
	<p>Social networks</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="707 1512 871 1561"> <p>Facebook</p> </td> <td data-bbox="871 1512 1463 1561"> <p>https://www.facebook.com/ccihorta1893/</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="707 1561 871 1610"> <p>Instagram</p> </td> <td data-bbox="871 1561 1463 1610"> <p>https://www.instagram.com/ccih.fajal/</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="707 1610 871 1659"> <p>Twitter</p> </td> <td data-bbox="871 1610 1463 1659"> <p>-</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="707 1659 871 1695"> <p>LinkedIn</p> </td> <td data-bbox="871 1659 1463 1695"> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccihorta/</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Facebook</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/ccihorta1893/</p>	<p>Instagram</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/ccih.fajal/</p>	<p>Twitter</p>	<p>-</p>	<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccihorta/</p>
<p>Facebook</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/ccihorta1893/</p>									
<p>Instagram</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/ccih.fajal/</p>									
<p>Twitter</p>	<p>-</p>									
<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ccihorta/</p>									

Business name	Observatório do Mar dos Açores OMA	Logo	
Company name	Azores Sea Observatory		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Azores Sea Observatory (OMA) is a non-profit Technical, Scientific and Cultural Association, created in 2002 by 23 founding members linked to the Department of Oceanography and Fisheries of the University of the Azores, and which currently forms part of the Regional Network of Scientific Centres promoted by the Regional Secretariat for the Sea, Science and Technology.</p> <p>OMA's objectives are to disseminate scientific and technological culture and promote environmental interpretation and education activities in the field of Marine Sciences.</p>		
Skills	<p>The activities of the OMA are based on:</p> <p>a) Scientific dissemination and environmental education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote the use of existing equipment and resources for learning scientific and technological content in an interactive and playful way. ▪ Organize and promote public scientific exhibitions on the Azores Sea. ▪ Organize and participate in environmental education and promotion actions, aimed at society in general, the school community and sea users (fishing professionals, maritime-tourism operators and recreational users), in particular. ▪ Promote educational workshops, field activities, ecotourism and environmental and cultural interpretation. <p>b) Editing, publishing and dissemination of information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Collect and disseminate technical, scientific and cultural information about the Azores Sea. ▪ Publish and edit brochures, cards, books, audiovisual products and digital information about the Azores Sea and the history of whales a hunting in the region. ▪ Make technical and scientific information available on the website. ▪ It sells some of the previous products and themed merchandising, alluding to marine life. <p>c) Technical-Scientific Actions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Support technical and scientific actions aimed at the management of sensitive marine resources. ▪ Promote and participate in working groups and forums for technical, scientific and marine conservation debate and dissemination. ▪ Contribute to the monitoring of the impacts of human activities on different aspects of the ecology of the Azores Sea. ▪ Collect and disseminate ecological indicators for the Azores Sea, geared towards medium and long-term monitoring programs. <p>d) Support for Partners and Society</p>		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating the holding of scientific events (academic exams, conferences and workshops), political events (government meetings and others), cultural and recreational events (book presentations, exhibitions, fairs and documentary screenings). 		
Capabilities	<p>To fulfil its mission as a Science Centre, the OMA works to promote inclusion in the global information and knowledge society, with the aim of creating the right conditions for learning scientific and technological content to take place in an interactive, entertaining and motivating way in its area of activity.</p> <p>On the other hand, it aims to observe the state of the Azores Sea and promote environmentally sustainable practices that preserve resources, biodiversity and the natural functioning of marine ecosystems.</p> <p>Also, since the OMA has its headquarters at the Fábrica da Baleia de Porto Pim, in the city of Horta, the organization also has the objective of safeguarding, studying and disseminating the Ballenero Heritage of Faial and the Azores Region.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Fábrica da Baleia de Porto Pim, Monte da Guia, 9900-000, Horta, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 292 292 140	
	Mail	geral@oma.pt centrodeciencia@oma.pt	
Information resources	Web	www.oma.pt	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/oma.acores/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/fabricadabaleia/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2FOAcores
		LinkedIn	https://pt.linkedin.com/company/observat%C3%B3rio-do-mar-dos-a%C3%A7ores

Business name	Azores Maritime Operators Association - AOMA		Logo	
Company name	Azores Maritime Operators Association			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)			
Type of service	<p>The Association of Maritime Operators of the Azores (AOMA), based in Vila do Porto, is an association of entrepreneurs from the maritime and maritime-tourism sectors.</p> <p>This organization currently has more than thirty members and has established alliances with various organizations, such as the Manta Trust, the Azores Tourism Association, the Azores Sub-Aquatic Archaeological Parks, the Azores Geopark, Disabled Divers International and the Shark Project, among many others.</p>			
Skills	<p>AOMA aims to represent its members, defend their legitimate interests, continue activities and take initiatives that are useful in fulfilling its functions, including, among others, the promotion, provision of assistance and presentation of proposals aimed at regulating the maritime-tourism activity in the Azores, as well as the representation of its member operators before the government bodies of the Autonomous Region of the Azores and the Republic.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>AOMA has contributed to the pursuit of regional and national environmental interests, specifically through the promotion of the Blue Economy and the enhancement of ecosystems.</p> <p>Among the many activities carried out by this association, it is worth highlighting its contribution to carrying out maritime tourism activities in a sustainable, certified, environmentally correct and safe way, with special emphasis on the collaboration it carries out with the regional authorities, in terms of placing moorings and anchors for buoy boats on the island of Santa María.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Rua Teófilo Braga Nr. 40 9580-535 - Vila do Porto - Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 917 287 286		
	Mail	aoma.acores@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	aomacores.com		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/aoma.acores/	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Regional Directorate for Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness – DREC	Logo	
Company name	Regional Directorate for Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	The Regional Directorate for Entrepreneurship and Competitiveness (DREC) is an instrument of the Government of the Azores created with the main mission of boosting the economic development of the Azores, through the promotion of a strong, innovative and competitive business fabric.		
Skills	<p>The DREC works closely with companies, entrepreneurs and partners in the Azores Autonomous Region, with the aim of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boosting private investment: Through the creation of an attractive business environment and the availability of financial and non-financial instruments that stimulate the creation and growth of companies. ▪ Strengthening competitiveness: Promoting innovation, quality and the internationalization of companies in the Azores, so that they can compete successfully in global markets. ▪ Fostering entrepreneurship: Supporting the creation of new businesses and promoting an entrepreneurial culture in the region. ▪ Attracting foreign investment: Attracting investors to the Azores, publicizing the region's potential and facilitating investment processes. 		
Capabilities	<p>DREC's actions are aimed at building a more prosperous future for the Azores, generating more wealth, more jobs and a better quality of life for all the archipelago's inhabitants.</p> <p>Among other things, the DREC is responsible for managing and disseminating different support and subsidy initiatives in the Azores region, promoted by the regional, national and international governments, which aim to expand the region's economic base, increase its export capacity, strategically reconvert business activity and boost investment in new business areas.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Rua de São João 55, 9500-107, Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 296 309 100	
	Mail	drec@azores.gov.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://portal.azores.gov.pt/web/drec	
	Social networks	Facebook	-
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-

Business name	University of the Azores - UAc		Logo	UAc UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES
Company name	University of the Azores			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)			
Type of service	<p>The University of the Azores (UAc) is a Portuguese public university located in the Azores archipelago.</p> <p>Initially, it was created to respond to the region's multiple training needs, raise its cultural level and promote its scientific and technological development.</p> <p>Today, the level of development achieved in the Azores finds in the action developed by the University one of its main sources of dynamism. The various areas of teaching and research cultivated at the University have profoundly broadened knowledge of the complex reality of the sea, the land, life, history, society and, in general, the culture of the islands of the archipelago.</p>			
Skills	<p>The UAc develops its activity on the basis of various types of services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Teaching and knowledge dissemination services. - Research and innovation services. - Support services for students in the region. - Support services for the regional community. - Support services for foreign students and mobility programs. 			
Capabilities	<p>The UAc has a tripolar structure, with centres in the cities of Ponta Delgada (where the headquarters, the main services and the rectory are located), Angra do Heroísmo (Terceira Island) and Horta (Faial Island).</p> <p>Its structure is based on a logic of departments and schools, which are units aimed at the continuous development of teaching and research. The University also includes polytechnic higher education, which includes the Higher Schools of Health and Technology of Ponta Delgada and Angra do Heroísmo.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	R. da Mãe de Deus, 9500-321 Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 296 650 032		
	Mail	adm.secretariado@uac.pt / reitoria.grpc@uac.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://uac.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/universidade.acores	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/uni.acores/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/uacores	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidade-acores/		

Business name	OKEANOS - Institute of Marine Sciences - University of the Azores	Then	OKEANOS UNIVERSIDADE DOS AÇORES
Company name	OKEANOS - Institute of Marine Sciences - University of the Azores		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Institute of Marine Sciences (OKEANOS), located in the city of Horta, Faial Island, is a recent research unit inherited from more than 40 years of applied and fundamental marine research carried out in the Azores by the Department of Oceanography and Fisheries (DOP) of the University of the Azores.</p> <p>Its mission is to carry out in-depth scientific research in deep waters, open oceans and coastlines, to advance knowledge on a changing planet, supporting higher education, ocean literacy and the sustainable management of marine ecosystems, for the benefit of society and the environment.</p>		
Skills	<p>The institute's research focuses on the following themes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Marine ecology. ▪ Marine and coastal biodiversity. ▪ Conservation of the marine environment. ▪ Marine and environmental monitoring systems. ▪ Fishing. ▪ Aquaculture. ▪ Animal behaviour studies. ▪ Mapping habitats and migratory routes. ▪ Climate change and its effects. ▪ Oceanography. ▪ Biogeography. ▪ Environmental contamination. ▪ Marine technologies. ▪ Blue economy. ▪ Maritime organization. 		
Capabilities	<p>The research carried out by the institute focuses on deep-water ecosystems, open oceans and island coastlines, and ranges from microorganisms to the largest animal on the planet, the blue whale. Their work aims to improve understanding of species and ecosystem resilience to global change and anthropogenic pressures, promote opportunities for blue growth and develop new research technologies.</p> <p>His work also informs ocean conservation and management policies and contributes to the undergraduate, postgraduate and doctoral courses in ocean sciences taught at the University of the Azores.</p> <p>The dissemination of scientific knowledge to the public is also a key element of its strategy.</p> <p>The Institute has more than 150 members, including senior, middle and junior scientists, technicians, students and other collaborators. OKEANOS benefits from</p>		

	different facilities and resources, such as laboratories, scientific equipment, maritime platforms and has established a broad international network of scientific collaborations over the years.		
Contact details	Direction	Rua Prof. Doutor Frederico Machado, 4, 9901-862 Horta, Faial, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 292 200 400	
	Mail	oceanos.secretariado@uac.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://www.oceanos.uac.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/Oceanos.uac/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/oceanos_uac/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/oceanosuac?lang=es
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/oceanos-uac

Business name	Centre of Applied Economics Studies of the Atlantic - CEEApIA	Logo	
Company name	Centre of Applied Economics Studies of the Atlantic - CEEApIA		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores and Madeira)		
Type of service	<p>The Centro de Estudios Económicos Aplicados del Atlántico (CEEApIA) was created in 2003 as a joint initiative of the Universidad de las Azores and the Universidad de Madeira to be an instrument for supporting and fostering rigorous, innovative and high-quality research and teaching practices in management and economics at both institutions.</p> <p>Its mission is to promote theoretical and applied scientific research using its highly qualified human resources involved in research projects in the areas of business and economics.</p>		
Skills	<p>The centre's objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Contribute to the development of scientific research and the implementation of national policy in its specific area. ▪ Carry out research programs and projects. ▪ Collaborate with universities and other higher education institutions in research and postgraduate training activities. ▪ Contribute to the scientific exchange between organizations and departments linked to research. ▪ Provide services to the community, without prejudice to the scientific research included in the scope of the previous paragraphs. <p>The centre has made essential contributions in the fields of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Tourism economics. ▪ Tourism management. ▪ General economics. ▪ Social and environmental sustainability ▪ Public economy. ▪ Regional economy. ▪ Labor economics. ▪ Business management, ▪ Finance. ▪ Marketing. ▪ Human resources. ▪ International business. 		
Capabilities	<p>The Centre plays a reaffirmed role in the study of numerous economic and business issues of international interest and local application, particularly in the two island contexts of the Azores and Madeira.</p> <p>Although it is a small centre, it is dedicated to generating a growing body of research in order to publish articles in high quality academic journals and present them at renowned international conferences. Its aim is to foster the expansion of the research network by promoting conferences and seminars and facilitating interactions</p>		

	<p>between its members and leading researchers in various fields of management science and economics.</p> <p>The centre's aim is to continue sharing research results with a wider audience through media engagements, policy briefs and public conferences, to improve its partnerships with companies and organizations, to form more partnerships with prestigious universities and research institutions and to attract experienced and promising researchers in the fields of business and economics.</p> <p>In addition, they intend to continue actively participating in essential applied research, using their knowledge to foster a deeper understanding of social dynamics. In this way, they intend to help policymakers draw up more effective and better-informed policies that address the needs and challenges of society.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Rua Mãe de Deus, 9500-321, Ponta Delgada, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 296 650 087	
	Mail	ceeapla.secretariado@uac.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://ceeapla.uac.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/UAC.FEG
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/feg.uac/
		Twitter	-
	LinkedIn	https://pt.linkedin.com/company/uac-feg-faculdade-de-economia-e-gest%C3%A3o-universidade-dos-a%C3%A7ores	

Business name	Regional Science and Technology Fund - FRCT	Logo	
Company name	Regional Science and Technology Fund - FRCT		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Regional Science and Technology Fund (FRCT) is a public body supervised by the Vice-Presidency of the Regional Government of the Azores, with legal personality and administrative and financial autonomy.</p> <p>The FRCT's mission is to promote, develop and internationalize the Azores Research and Innovation Ecosystem, considering the strategic guidelines, priorities and objectives of the Regional Government's policies.</p>		
Skills	<p>To achieve this mission, the FRCT divides its activities into two main pillars:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PILLAR I - Financing and support for advanced training. <p>The Autonomous Region of the Azores has been investing in expanding the pool of Advanced Training assets, mainly since 2020, with the main objective of mitigating the quantitative and qualitative deficits that characterized its qualified human capital base.</p> <p>In order to continue strengthening the innovative, scientific and technological development of the region, in relation to the national and European context, the funding of regional Advanced Training remains a central and essential condition.</p> <p>The FRCT, through the granting of aid for research in science and technology, aims to strengthen the opportunities for advanced training in the Autonomous Region of the Azores, promote the advancement of Research and Innovation (R+i) in the Azores, renew the critical mass and foster the competitiveness of entities, contributing to the development of the regional economy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - PILLAR II - Promoting and attracting external funding for the Azores Autonomous Region. <p>The allocation of funds to European programs is one of the main means of promoting, developing and internationalizing science and technology in the Autonomous Region of the Azores.</p> <p>The Plan for the Internationalization of Science and Technology in the Azores designates the FRCT as one of the entities responsible for implementing measures aimed at the internationalization of science and technology in the Azores, based on the competencies it has been assigned to assume the responsibility of facilitating and promoting this strategy.</p> <p>The FRCT has a transversal action in all departments of the Regional Government of the Azores, in terms of regional participation in programs, projects and initiatives that involve external financing to the Autonomous Region of the Azores.</p>		

	<p>Considering the opportunity to strengthen the position of the Azores in the European Research and Innovation Space (R+), it is crucial to facilitate and encourage access by the different regional players to European initiatives and programs. It is also necessary to ensure coordination between the different regional entities and the management authorities and intermediary bodies of the operational programs.</p>			
Capabilities	<p>The FRCT aims to be the reference body in the internationalization of the regional R&D&I ecosystem by attracting external funding and contributing to the sustainable economic development of the Azores Autonomous Region.</p> <p>Some of the activities carried out by the FRCT are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up of European research and innovation programs. ▪ Participation in European cooperation networks and international associations. ▪ Participation in strategic projects. ▪ Organization of promotional, networking, training and matchmaking events. ▪ Managing and implementing the support instruments for advanced training, such as scholarships and financial aid for research in different types and scientific areas. 			
Contact details	Direction	Largo da Matriz nº45-52, 1er Piso, 9500-094, Ponta Delgada - Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 296 241 870		
	Mail	info.frct@azores.gov.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://frct.azores.gov.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=189596175000270&rdr	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/FRCTAzores	
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/frct-azores/	

Business name	São Miguel Science and Technology Park - NONAGON	Logo	
Company name	São Miguel Science and Technology Park - NONAGON		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The San Miguel Science and Technology Park (NONAGON) is the first Science and Technology Park in the Autonomous Region of the Azores and aims to become a structural organization for technological dynamization and the training of qualified human capital in the fields of information systems, communications and the monitoring and observation of the earth, space and the sea.</p> <p>The park also aims to be a catalyst for synergies in the technology transfer processes of the Azores innovation ecosystem.</p>		
Skills	<p>NONAGON aims to be an international benchmark in the valorisation of human, technological, entrepreneurial and social capital, centred on entrepreneurial skills and dynamics and supported by knowledge, technology and innovation.</p> <p>The park's strategic objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fostering the development of new leadership paradigms. ▪ To be a catalyst for innovation and creativity. ▪ Putting innovation at the centre of business competitiveness. ▪ Contribute to attracting and retaining new talent. ▪ Promote interaction between companies, knowledge centres and public entities. ▪ Fostering and promoting technology-based entrepreneurship, valuing the achievement of results. ▪ Support the promotion and establishment of regional, national and international alliances. 		
Capabilities	<p>NONAGON facilitates access to the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Access to versatile spaces for setting up companies and holding events. ▪ Business training programs for start-ups and SMEs. ▪ Organization of workshops, seminars and conferences. ▪ Human resources training programs. ▪ Programs to support and disseminate R&D&I. ▪ Search for partnership opportunities. ▪ Acceleration and Open Innovation Programs. ▪ Organization of Entrepreneurship and Innovation competitions. ▪ Detection and analysis of new business opportunities. ▪ Analysis of trends in R&D and viability of new products and services. ▪ Registration of intellectual property. ▪ Promoting contact with inverters. 		
Contact details	Direction	Rua da Tecnologia K - Epsilon, N.º 2, 9560-421, Rosário - Lagoa, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 296 249 400 / (+351) 965 985 090	

Information resources	Mail	geral@nonagon.pt		
	Web	https://nonagon.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/nonagonpark/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/nonagonpark/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/nonagonpark	
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/nonagonpark		

Business name	Terceira Island Science and Technology Park - TERINOV	Logo	
Company name	Terceira Island Science and Technology Park - TERINOV		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The mission of the Terceira Island Science and Technology Park (TERINOV) is to boost the local and regional entrepreneurial ecosystem of the Azores, reaffirming technology-based entrepreneurship based on technology, knowledge and science, and adapted to its needs and particularities as an outermost region.</p>		
Skills	<p>TERINOV aims to be a determining agent of business innovation in the Azores through the valorisation of human resources, the transfer of technology and knowledge and training.</p> <p>The organization's objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boosting the adhesion and promotion of entrepreneurship in established areas of activity. ▪ Creating a favourable environment for entrepreneurship in the Azores Autonomous Region. ▪ Promote and stimulate a culture of entrepreneurship and innovation. ▪ Increasing a contextual change in the culture of the local and regional business fabric, favouring a proactive, cooperative and innovative attitude. ▪ Promote and foster more frequent and better relations between new companies and the Azores Scientific and Technological System. ▪ Encouraging the sharing of experiences and skills. ▪ Developing events that attract creativity, innovation, business sense and other skills that are essential for the innovation of the business fabric of the Azores. ▪ Stimulate the creation of new innovative products/services- ▪ Providing a wide network of contacts, mentors and other services such as administrative, legal or consulting support to stimulate/facilitate the creation of new companies. 		
Capabilities	<p>With the aim of providing support to new innovative technology-based companies in the areas of Agribusiness, Cultural and Creative Industries, and Information and Communication Technologies, TERINOV manages a series of incubation and business development programs designed to accelerate the successful development of entrepreneurial projects and companies through a variety of business support resources and services.</p> <p>TERINOV also provides its tenants and partners with communal and private spaces where emerging and expanding companies can develop their activities, meet and share experiences in a collaborative environment, including workshops, meeting rooms, an auditorium, field plots and different laboratories. It is part of our mission to provide spaces.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Canada de Belém, 9700-702, Terra Chã, Angra do Heroísmo, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 295 249 400	

Information resources	Mail	geral@terinovazores.pt		
	Web	https://terinovazores.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/terinovazores	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/terinov_pct/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/TERINOV1	
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/18922844/admin		

Business name	Institute of Technological Innovation of the Azores – INOVA	Logo	
Company name	Institute of Technological Innovation of the Azores – INOVA		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>The Azores Institute for Technological Innovation (INOVA) was founded in 1988 as a response to the need to minimize the technological deficit that separates the region from the rest of the country and other European countries, and as a response to the specific needs of the region arising from the characteristics of the regional business fabric, which is small, fragmented and traditionally not very open to the outside world.</p>		
Skills	<p>INOVA aims to boost technological development, technology transfer, the provision of specialized and quality services to support regional industry and promote applied research.</p> <p>The main functional areas in which INOVA operates are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Biochemistry. ▪ Biology. ▪ Aquatic Sciences. ▪ Geology. ▪ Applied Mathematics. ▪ Metrology ▪ Business organization, administration and management. 		
Capabilities	<p>Since its creation, INOVA has consolidated itself as a technological infrastructure of reference in the regional context, of added strategic importance and necessary for the development of the business fabric and the economy of the Azores.</p> <p>INOVA offers the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Analysis laboratory services: Physicochemical and microbiological analysis of water, food and agri-foodstuffs, soils, substrates and sludge. ▪ Metrology laboratory services: Calibration/Testing in the areas of Mass, Temperature and Pressure. Legal Metrology in the areas of Mass, Pressure, Time, Fills, Temperature and Automatic Operating Instruments. ▪ Environmental study and analysis services: Carrying out tests and providing services in the field of monitoring and measuring environmental parameters (water, effluents, air and noise), as well as implementing projects and actions that contribute to the enhancement of the region's natural resources. ▪ Food technology study services: Carrying out studies and trials aimed at supporting the agri-food industries of the Azores Autonomous Region, in particular the dairy, meat and fishing industries, in order to promote the quality of food products and their diversification. ▪ Services of the Ribeira Grande Experimental Field: Development of tests and technological demonstration actions of interest to the Region, in the wintering complex of the Ribeira Grande Experimental Field. <p>INOVA also works on the design and development of R&D&I projects which, by their nature, involve various functional areas.</p>		

	INOVA's management considers quality to be a key factor in its culture and operations, as a provider of testing and calibration services, giving primary importance to customer satisfaction, as well as legal and regulatory requirements.		
Contact details	Direction	Estrada de São Gonçalo, S/N, 9504-540, Ponta Delgada - Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 296 201 770	
	Mail	inova@inovacores.pt	
Information resources	Web	https://www.inovacores.pt/	
	Social networks	Facebook	-
		Instagram	-
		Twitter	-
LinkedIn		https://pt.linkedin.com/company/inova-inst.-de-inova%C3%A7%C3%A3o-tecnol%C3%B3gica-dos-a%C3%A7ores	

Business name	Azores Environmental Observatory - OAA	Logo		
Company name	Azores Environmental Observatory - OAA			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)			
Type of service	The Environmental Observatory of the Azores (OAA), also known as the Angra do Heroísmo Science Centre, aims to disseminate science in an informal and entertaining way, for all ages, showing that science is accessible to everyone and that it is part of everyone's daily life.			
Skills	The OAA's work focuses on promoting experimental activities and scientific dissemination of topics related to the environment.			
Capabilities	<p>The OAA centre has various spaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A main area designed to present a main exhibition, usually of an interactive nature. ▪ A laboratory for experimental activities. ▪ A multipurpose room where complementary activities, workshops, courses, temporary exhibitions, etc. are held. ▪ A small screening room where meetings, conferences, and film screenings are held. ▪ A documentation centre. <p>The OAA carries out a series of activities to disseminate science and technology (indoors and outdoors), which are usually done in collaboration with other organizations.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Carretera Gaspar Côrte-Real (former Lonja de Pescado, opposite Prainha), 9700-030, Angra do Heroísmo - Terceira, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 295 217 845		
	Mail	angraheroismo@azores.gov.pt ccah.oaa@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://oaa.centrosciencia.azores.gov.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ObservatorioAmbienteAcoresCentroCienciaAH/?locale=pt_BR	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/oaa_centrociencia_ah/	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Seascope - Sharing Experiences		Logo	
Company name	Seascope - Sharing Experiences			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (San Miguel)			
Type of service	Seascope is a company focused on organizing sea excursions along the north coast of San Miguel Island and inland sea expeditions.			
Skills	<p>Seascope's competencies are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organization of nautical and coastal excursions. ▪ Sightings of marine fauna. ▪ Promotion of water sports (mainly kayaking, paddleboarding and water cycling). 			
Capabilities	<p>Seascope is a young and dynamic nautical tourism company with a passionate and experienced team dedicated to offering a variety of exclusive tours, from boat excursions to coastal hikes.</p> <p>Its vision is based on protecting and preserving the oceans, collaborating with communities and aiming for a more prosperous and sustainable future.</p> <p>They have a fleet of semi-rigid boats designed to face the challenges of open water. Their remarkable versatility not only guarantees safety, but also promises stable navigation.</p> <p>They also offer kayak and bicycle rental.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Rua dos Condes da Ribeira Grande, 9600-521 Ribeira Grande, São Miguel		
	Telephone	(+351) 914 410 189		
	Mail	azoreanseascope@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://azoreanseascope.mydurable.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/p/Seascope_Sharing-Experiences-61551983516541/?_rdc	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/azoreanseascope/	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores		Logo	
Company name	Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla de Flores)			
Type of service	The Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores aims to promote aquatic activities and sports, training, recreational activities and the preservation of the nautical heritage of the island of Flores.			
Skills	<p>The main activities managed by the Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Issuing recreational fishing licenses. ▪ Participation in marine and nautical courses. ▪ Sailing training and participation in competitions. ▪ Management of the historical heritage of the whale fleet and the Whale Museum of Isla de Flores. 			
Capabilities	<p>The Lajes das Flores Naval Club is responsible for the maintenance and use of the São Pedro and Formosa ballboats.</p> <p>Over the years, the club has taken part in several regattas in the Azores Autonomous Region and participated in all editions of the Regional <i>Ballenero</i> Championship.</p> <p>Likewise, the Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores is responsible for the Lajes <i>Ballenero</i> Museum and for preserving the heritage and historical memory of this activity.</p> <p>The Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores is also a member of the Portuguese Sailing Federation and one of its objectives is training and competition in light sailing.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Clube Naval de Lajes das Flores (Antigua Fábrica da Baleia - Área Portuaria), Rua do Porto, 9960-438, Lajes das Flores, Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 292 593 145		
	Mail	cnlflores@sapo.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://cnlf.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/clubenaval.flores	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/clubenavalflores/	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Floresfishing	Logo	
Company name	FloresFishing, Lda		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla de Flores y Corvo)		
Type of service	Floresfishing is an authorized maritime-tour operator specializing in sport fishing activities on Flores Island and Corvo.		
Skills	<p>His main skills are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sport fishing. ▪ Fishing for beginners. ▪ Underwater fishing. ▪ Buceo en apnea. ▪ Boat rental and accommodation. 		
Capabilities	<p>FloresFishing has a nautical license issued by the Regional Directorate for Maritime Policy.</p> <p>The company operates throughout the western group, the islands of Flores and Corvo, approximately 15 nautical miles apart. Departures can be made from any port on these islands, all of which are provided with sufficient fuel for safe travel, and all the crew are qualified, with the ship's captain being a tea master in the Local Master category.</p> <p>The company also has a motorized boat 6 meters long and 2.40 meters wide, which meets all the safety requirements demanded by law, as well as having the appropriate safety equipment for the activity carried out and the relevant insurance, with the coverage required by law.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Avenida Diogo Teive, n°18, Santa Cruz das Flores 9970-301, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 912 289 629 - (+351) 927 274 232	
	Mail	floresfishing@hotmail.com	
Information resources	Web	https://floresfishing.com/en/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/people/Floresfishing/61560109526837/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/fishingflores/?igsh=MXh4cTM4bnJ6OTFjbg%3D%3D

Business name	Association for the Development and Training of the Azores Sea (ADFMA)	Logo	
Company name	Association for the Development and Training of the Azores Sea (ADFMA)		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	The Association for the Development and Training of the Azores Sea (ADFMA) is an educational services and training organization, which acts as the managing body of the Azores Sea School, and which bases its strategic action on the construction and implementation of training actions aimed at seafarers and other professionals associated with the blue economy, as well as other related student communities.		
Skills	<p>ADFMA's objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing and administering the Azores Sea School (EMA). • Strengthen the EMA as a Professional School and Specialized Training Centre for the Sea. • Implement EMA Management Models (Operational, Administrative and Financial). • Promote new courses and continue with existing ones at DRQPE. • Supporting local institutions in the implementation and promotion of educational policies. • Promote, develop and support the implementation of support infrastructures for maritime professions. • Strengthen collaboration and links between its members and between them and public and private entities directly or indirectly involved in maritime affairs, such as the scientific community, the business sector, professional colleges and public companies in the regional administration. • Continue EMA's educational and training activities. • Approving the EMA Education Project. • Ensure the execution of the pending tasks for the installation of the EMA's technical and logistical structure. • Propose thematic areas, within the scope of professional training, which will be taught by the Azores Sea School, and which correspond to the interests of the partners and the region. • Carry out activities to value and disseminate the results of its work, and the knowledge and technologies that may be of interest to the business sector linked to the maritime economy. • Providing consultancy and technical support services to individuals and companies, including public administration bodies, in the field of training. • Promote cooperation with national and international organizations around common objectives and towards the development of certified and quality training offers for maritime professions. 		
Capabilities	ADFMA develops dynamics of collaborative actions with strategic alliances between local, regional, national and supranational multi-level actors, in traditional, emerging and complementary activities, such as shipbuilding and repair, recreational boating, fishing, aquaculture, ports, maritime transport logistics, processing and transformation of fisheries. All this is accompanied by the		

	promotion of ocean literacy, with the aim of developing the training and qualification of professional agents and learning communities.		
Contact details	Direction	Former Horta Naval Radio Station Complex, R. Jaime Lopes, 9900-038 Horta, Azores, Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 292 241 780	
	Mail	GERAL@EMAZORES.PT	
Information resources	Web	https://www.emazores.pt/associacao/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/emazores.pt
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/emazores/
		Twitter	-
LinkedIn		https://pt.linkedin.com/company/emazores	

Business name	DiveAzores	Logo	
Company name	DiveAzores LDA		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla de Fayal, with some activities on the coast and Isla de Pico and San Jorge)		
Type of service	Dive Azores is a whale and dolphin watching eco-operator based in Horta, on the island of Fayal.		
Skills	<p>Dive Azores' activities focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Submarinism. ▪ Scuba diving courses. ▪ Boat trips. ▪ Sightings of cetaceans and marine fauna. ▪ Shark diving expeditions. ▪ Research and volunteer projects. ▪ Travel information and preparation. 		
Capabilities	<p>Dive Azores offers its clients excellent whale and scuba diving watching experiences through the management of small, high quality ecotourism operations in a pleasant and relaxed environment.</p> <p>The company also strives to make positive contributions to the conservation and understanding of wildlife and marine ecosystems in the Azores through environmentally friendly practices and ongoing research that is supported by its clients.</p> <p>It also aims to increase public awareness, respect and knowledge about the marine environment and ocean conservation issues, as well as making an economic contribution to some important wildlife organizations and supporting/promoting local conservation and animal welfare initiatives.</p> <p>The company has a small buoyage centre with high safety standards and personalized service, where first-class equipment for submarine activities can be purchased. They also have a 9.60m rigid pneumatic boat and a 5.0m fiberglass boat. Both are equipped for the convenience of boaters and in accordance with EU safety standards with VHF radio, depth sounder, emergency oxygen and first aid kits, and are operated by crews with authorized experience.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Dive Azores, Horta Marina, Faial - Azores - Portugal	
	Telephone	(+351) 967 882 214	
	Mail	info@diveazores.net	
Information resources	Web	https://diveazores.net/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/diveazores.net/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/diveazores/?locale=es

		Twitter	https://twitter.com/diveazores?lang=es
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/dive-azores-15396134?trk=pub-pbmap

Business name	Clube Naval de Vila Franca do Campo		Logo	
Company name	Clube Naval de Vila Franca do Campo			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla de San Miguel)			
Type of service	A non-profit organization whose objectives are to promote sport and nautical recreation through the development of various sporting activities in the maritime environment.			
Skills	<p>The club focuses much of its action on training, competition and environmental awareness, seeking to develop in young people the ability to enjoy the sea, nature and the camaraderie that water sports provide.</p> <p>The club is also focused on promoting and developing aquatic sports and recreational activities and competitions. The focus is on these water sports:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kayak • Canoeing • Scuba diving • Sport fishing • Sailing 			
Capabilities	<p>The club's main services are as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development and promotion services for sports, tourism and entertainment activities related to the sea. ▪ Nautical and sailing services. ▪ Engine maintenance services for sports and pleasure boats. ▪ Nautical school services and navigation training. ▪ Environmental awareness services. 			
Contact details	Direction	Rua da Marina, 9680-187 Vila Franca do Campo, São Miguel - Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 296 582 333		
	Mail	geral@cnvfc.net		
Information resources	Web	https://www.cnvfc.net/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ClubeNavalVilaFrancadoCampo	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/cnvfc/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/CNVFC1	
LinkedIn		https://pt.linkedin.com/company/clube-naval-de-vila-franca-do-campo		

Business name	Norberto Diver		Logo	
Company name	Norberto Diver-Actividades Maritimas, Lda.			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (Isla de Faial y Pico)			
Type of service	Norberto Diver is a company based on the island of Faial that offers various types of experiences both on and under the sea, such as sightings of dolphins, swimming with dolphins and snorkelling.			
Skills	<p>The main activities carried out by Norberto Diver are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Catamaran rides. ▪ Whale Watching and dolphins. ▪ Coastal scuba diving. ▪ Submarinism. ▪ Shark diving. ▪ Private boat excursions. 			
Capabilities	<p>In addition to boat excursions to see different species of cetaceans, Norberto Diver organizes underwater expeditions to the Princess Alice Bank, 45 nautical miles south of Faial Island and 35 metres deep, where you can see tuna, barracudas, medregales and manta ray fish, among many other species of marine fauna.</p> <p>They also organize shallow-sea snorkelling trips focused on observing blue-footed boobies, as well as coastal snorkelling trips to more than 20 different snorkelling spots on the islands of Faial and Pico, where you can see <i>ballesta grises</i>, large dusky grouper, Mediterranean wrasse, pulp and moray eels hiding among the rocks, as well as various species of small and colourful nudibranchs, among other marine species.</p> <p>The company has different boats for each type of activity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 12 m catamaran with capacity for 12 people. ▪ Three fast and manoeuvrable zodiac boats that can be used to watch dolphins, swim with dolphins or take private boat trips around the islands of Faial and Pico. Capacity for between 14 and 12 people. ▪ Two zodiac boats specially adapted for boating, stable and with space for equipment and photographic accessories. Capacities for 10 and 8 people. 			
Contact details	Direction	Marina da Horta, 9900-018, Horta, Faial (Azores), Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 292 293 891 / (+351) 969 197 077		
	Mail	info@norbertodiver.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://www.norbertodiver.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/norbertodivercenter/?local_e=es_LA	

		Instagr am	https://www.instagram.com/norbertodiver/
--	--	---------------	---

Business name	Azores Boat Adventures		Logo	
Company name	Azores Boat Adventures			
Type of organization				
Territorial scope	Insular (San Miguel)			
Type of service	Azores Boat Adventures is a family-owned tourist entertainment company that offers various maritime activities on the north coast of the island of São Miguel to small groups of visitors with the aim of minimizing their ecological impact as much as possible and providing more personalized and welcoming experiences.			
Skills	<p>The activities of Azores Boat Adventures focus on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boat excursions. ▪ Coastal walks. ▪ Sightings of cetaceans and marine fauna. ▪ Surf tour. ▪ Snorkel. ▪ Coastal hiking. ▪ Travel planning, advice and organization. 			
Capabilities	<p>Azores Boat Adventures offers with its activities a unique opportunity to explore the impressive coastline of the island of São Miguel, particularly its north coast.</p> <p>They offer a wide range of experiences, including boat trips, surfing excursions, underwater fishing, snorkelling and coastal fishing.</p> <p>The activities are guided by experienced professionals, where there is the unique opportunity to discover the most beautiful coastline of the island of São Miguel, creating an inexplicable connection with nature. Their activities show a deep respect for nature, as well as strict monitoring, attention, care and planning on the part of the team.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Fishing port, R. do Porto, 9600-000 Rabo de Peixe, San Miguel, Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 912 971 891		
	Mail	azoresboatadventuresweb@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://azoresboatadventures.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/azores.boat.adventures/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/azores.boat.adventures/	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	https://pt.linkedin.com/company/azores-boat-adventures	

Business name	Santana Astronomical Observatory (OASA) - Ribeira Grande Science Centre	Logo	
Company name	Santana Astronomical Observatory (OASA) - Ribeira Grande Science Center		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	Regional (Azores)		
Type of service	<p>Located on Pico do Bode, in Santana, Rabo de Peixe, the Astronomical Observatory of Santana - Azores (OASA) is a unique space for scientific knowledge and dissemination in Ribeira Grande.</p> <p>It is a Science Centre that forms part of the regional network of Science Centres, distributed on all the islands of the archipelago, which seek to promote scientific knowledge and access to technological innovations. Of the various scientific areas, Ribeira Grande, with its wide view of the northern hemisphere sky, was responsible for housing the only Astronomy centre in the region.</p>		
Skills	<p>The main objectives of the OASA are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Promote scientific knowledge and access to technological innovations. ▪ Carry out knowledge dissemination activities. ▪ Carrying out astronomical observations. ▪ Develop educational activities. ▪ Attend and collaborate at national and international astronomy conferences. ▪ Organize permanent and temporary exhibitions. 		
Capabilities	<p>The OASA, as a Science Centre, seeks to create a privileged space for the dissemination of scientific knowledge and, specifically, topics related to Astronomy.</p> <p>To this end, they have all the necessary material to be a meeting place for astronomy enthusiasts and an interactive and didactic support for school programs covering scientific topics, thus creating a unique place of fun and learning for all ages and audiences.</p> <p>OASA also seeks to be a place that motivates a fascination for astronomy and feeds everyone's curiosity so that, in a playful way, they can develop their knowledge of science and the human race and is therefore open not only to schools and astronomy enthusiasts, but also to the general public.</p> <p>In addition, the observatory has all the necessary conditions for observing the stars and has the essential tools for learning and developing knowledge in Astronomy. promoting participation in observing the solar or night sky, holding thematic exhibitions and astronomy and physics workshops, and promoting the use of its mobile digital planetarium.</p>		

Contact details	Direction	Caminho Velho de Santana, Pico do Bode - Santana, 9600-096, Rabo de Peixe (San Miguel), Azores, Portugal		
	Telephone	(+351) 296 492 764 / (+351) 916 228 004		
	Mail	geral@oasa.pt		
Information resources	Web	https://oasa.centrosciencia.azores.gov.pt/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ccrg.oasa/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ccrgoasa/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/CcrgOasa	
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/observat-rio-astron-mico-de-santana--a-ores		

MARTINIQUE

Business name	Fédération des Industries Nautiques – FIN	Logo	
Company name	Fédération des Industries Nautiques – FIN		
Type of organization			
Territorial scope	National (France)		
Type of service	<p>The Federation of Nautical Industries (FIN) aims to represent, develop and promote the professions of the French nautical industry in France and internationally.</p> <p>The federation represents a network of around 6,000 companies, and its members, grouped into 9 professions in the nautical and service industry, account for more than 80% of the profession's turnover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shipbuilders. ▪ Electronic equipment manufacturers. ▪ Engine manufacturers. ▪ River hire companies. ▪ Maritime hire companies. ▪ Trade and maintenance. ▪ Services. ▪ Yachts and luxury boats. ▪ Table sports and outdoor sports. 		
Competences	<p>These are FIN competences:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acting as a privileged interlocutor for public authorities at territorial, national and European level, assisting and advising companies in the legal, social, economic, environmental and technical fields. It fulfils an information function for the public in general and the media, particularly with regard to the evolution of market trends. • At European and international level, the Federation actively participates in the development of the nautical sector, being a member of the European Boating Industry Federation and the ICOMIA federation. • At a national level, FIN is a founding member of the Shipping Confederation, which brings together the 4 major nautical families (service industries, sailors, sports ports, federations and sports organisations). The Shipping Confederation co-chairs an inter-ministerial working body with the Secretary General Mer, dependent on the Prime Minister. FIN is also a member of the French Maritime Cluster and the French Business Movement. 		
Capacities	<p>FIN's main capabilities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Representation of its members in the various French, European and international organisations for the defence of the sector's interests. ▪ Organisation and representation at international events (Nautic en Seine, Cannes Yachting Festival, International Multihull Show de la Grande Motte) and carrying out coordinated actions to facilitate the presence of its members at international boat shows. ▪ Fostering commitment to the development of sustainable boating. FIN is the only professional federation with 2 ecological organisations set up on its initiative: the 		

	<p>Association for Eco-Responsible Performance (APER) for the scrapping of boats at the end of their useful life and the pyrotechnic signalisation equipment (PYRéO) for the collection and treatment of expired pyrotechnic signals.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">FIN is also active in all matters relating to training and employment in the nautical sector. To promote its professions, its training and the attractiveness of its companies to young people, adults in retraining or looking for work, FIN has launched an ambitious communication campaign, "The nautical team returns", with the support of OPCO2i. At the same time, FIN has also undertaken an important task of renewing training content, with the aim of facilitating access to employment for adults in the process of retraining or looking for work, making the most of their skills and attracting new profiles to traditional, essentially manual professions.		
Contact details	Direction	22 rue de Madrid, 75008, Paris, France	
	Telephone	(+33) (0)1 44 37 04 00	
	Mail	info@fin.fr	
Information resources	Web	https://www.fin.fr/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/fin.fr
		Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCN8k5kjE2m4QyuMAekRySKw
		Twitter	https://x.com/i/flow/login?redirect_after_login=%2Ffr_fin
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/f%C3%A9d%C3%A9ration-des-industries-nautiques/

Business name	Territorial Collectivity of Martinique	Logo	
Company name	Territorial Collectivity of Martinique		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)		
Type of service	<p>The Territorial Collectivity of Martinique (CTM) is a single French territorial collectivity that has succeeded the Department and Region of Martinique in all its rights and obligations since 2016. Its executive body is the Executive Council, and its deliberating body is the Martinique Assembly.</p>		
Competences	<p>The competences of the CTM include those of a region and a department, and it is particularly responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic development. ▪ Education and professional training. ▪ Transport. ▪ Health development. ▪ Social development. ▪ Regional co-operation. 		
Capacities	<p>The CTM has the power to promote regional cooperation, the economic, social, health, cultural and scientific development of Martinique, foster the development of its territory, guarantee the preservation of its identity, and at the same time respect the integrity, autonomy and competences of the municipalities.</p> <p>CTM is committed to supporting many key sectors in Martinique's regional development:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Economic development: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Tourism aid. – Help for companies. – Help for digital businesses. ▪ Solidarity: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Social assistance. – Help for older people and people with disabilities. ▪ Education and training: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Student help. – Help with professional training. ▪ Culture and sport: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Aids to sporting excellence. – Assistance in audiovisual creation and production. 		
Contact details	Direction	Hôtel de la Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique, Rue Gaston Defferre - Cluny CS 30137 Fort de France - Martinique	
	Telephone	(+596) 59 63 00	
	Mail	courrier@ctm.mq	

Information resources		courrier@collectivitedemartinique.mg	
	Web	https://www.collectivitedemartinique.mg/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/collectivitedemartinique/?locale=fr_FR
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ctm_martinique/
		Twitter	https://x.com/CTM_Martinique
LinkedIn		https://www.linkedin.com/company/collectivit%C3%A9-de-martinique/	

Business name	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Martinique - CCIM	Logo	
Company name	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Martinique - CCIM		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)		
Type of service	<p>The Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Martinique (CCIM) is a public institution, endowed with legal personality and financial autonomy, and responsible for the management of a certain number of public services in the region of Martinique.</p> <p>The CCIM acts as a privileged interlocutor for public and state actors in the Martinique region, which it regularly consults for its experience and privileged relationship with companies.</p> <p>As such, CCIM represents more than 36,000 traders, industrialists and service companies. Its advisors and agents support managers throughout the life of the company: creation, acquisition, international development, sustainability and performance, sustainable development, learning and training and, finally, transmission.</p>		
Competences	<p>Competences from the following areas have been transferred to the CCIM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economic development. - Professional training. - Spatial planning. <p>The main missions and actions of the CCIM are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consultative and representative missions of the economic world: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Representing the interests of its areas of specialisation, industry and services, and providing advice and assistance. - Consulted on any matter relating to the competences transferred to the CCIM. - Promoting sectoral development plans. ▪ Interventions in economic development and business support: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating and managing business advisory and assistance centres, economic observatories, business expeditions, etc. - Providing economic and legal information for companies (local, national, international documentation centre, etc.). ▪ Administrative missions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Managing administrative procedures relating to companies and mediating between them and public administrations. ▪ Training activities in the company's competences and in the workplaces of the day: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation and administration, alone or in collaboration, of study plans and business and labour training centres. 		
Capacities	The CCIM is responsible for providing business support and promoting the economic development of the trade, industry and services sectors in Martinique.		

	The CCIM also offers macro and microeconomic studies and participates in the preparation of master plans, public action plans for economic development or land-use planning. It also participates in the management of the Gran Puerto Marítimo and SAMAC (Société Aéroportuaire Martinique Aimé Césaire).		
Contact details	Direction	50, rue Ernest DEPROGE, Fort-de-France, Martinique	
	Telephone	(+596) 55 28 00	
	Mail	contact@martinique.cci.fr	
Information resources	Web	https://www.martinique.cci.fr/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CCIMartinique
		Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/user/cci972
		Twitter	https://x.com/CCIMartinique
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cci-martinique/

Business name	Direction de la Mer de la Martinique (DM)	Logo	
Company name	Direction de la Mer de la Martinique (DM)		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)		
Type of service	<p>The Martinique Directorate for the Sea (DM) is a decentralised service of the French State responsible for implementing public policies in the field of the sea.</p> <p>The DM is divided into the following departments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Direction. ▪ Blue Economy Department. ▪ Maritime planning and the marine environment. ▪ Sea people's health. ▪ Maritime security and policing. ▪ Lighthouses and beacons - POLMAR. ▪ Antilles-Guyana Regional Operational Centre for Maritime Surveillance and Rescue (CROSS AG). ▪ Antilles-Guyana Vessel Safety Centre (CSN AG). 		
Competences	<p>The missions of the DM of Martinique are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Implementation and coordination of maritime and coastal policies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Regulate and control maritime activities. – Coordinate regulatory policies for activities carried out at sea and on the coast and ensure their coherence. – Leading the network of state services and operators responsible for these regulatory policies. – Ensure with DEAL the management and protection of the coastline and marine environment, as well as the planning of activities at sea in consultation with users. ▪ Sustainable development of maritime activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Supporting the sustainable development of blue economy sectors. – Promote the preservation of the marine environment, the prevention of marine pollution and the management of the maritime public domain. – Supervising fishing, marine farming and marine aquaculture activities to facilitate their coexistence with other activities and ensure their development while respecting the objectives of conserving fish populations, water quality and marine ecosystems. This involves the implementation of public aid to the sea fishing and marine aquaculture sectors, but also through the regulation of fishing and the coordination of fisheries surveillance actions by state services. – Encouraging maritime employment and vocational training. – Promote the economic development of recreational boating activities. ▪ Maritime safety: 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure the protection of human life at sea and the safety of boats and maritime activities, in particular, nautical leisure activities practised by a population unaccustomed to risks. - Prevent risks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Controlling the safety of ships and their equipment. o By monitoring seafarers' skills and developing maritime training. o Through the implementation of maritime navigation safety systems (beaconing, maritime traffic tracking, nautical information, etc.). - Strengthening the prevention of maritime labour risks. - Preparing for the fight against accidental contamination of the marine environment. 		
<p>Capacities</p>	<p>Among other things, DM is responsible for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Supporting the development and structuring of blue economy sectors (maritime transport and ports, marine fishing and aquaculture, professional sailing and navigation, shipbuilding and repair, marine renewable energies and other emerging activities), by following up European, national and local public aid. ▪ The management of fisheries resources, through the regulatory framework for professional and recreational maritime fishing, the supervision of the Regional Committee for Maritime Fisheries and Marine Crops and the coordination of the Martinique Regional Fisheries Management Commission. ▪ Supporting seafarers and shipowners in their administrative procedures related to the administrative management of their professional career (identification number, titles, etc.) and their boat (registration certificate, sailing licence, professional fishing boat licence and European fishing licence). ▪ Ensuring the academic supervision of maritime and aquaculture vocational training organisations, by approving the maritime training offered and providing administrative and regulatory support to schools in their maritime teaching mission. ▪ Supporting sailors and companies in the nautical sector in their administrative tasks related to the administrative management of recreational boats (registration, transfer, etc.), organising the theoretical tests for recreational sailing licences and examining requests for authorisation from training establishments and supervised submerging initiation establishments on private boats. 		
<p>Contact details</p>	<p>Direction</p>	<p>Bd Chevalier-de-Sainte-Marthe 97261 Fort-de-France Cedex</p>	
	<p>Telephone</p>	<p>(+33) (05) 96 60 80 30</p>	
	<p>Mail</p>	<p>dm-martinique@developpement-durable.gouv.fr</p>	
<p>Information resources</p>	<p>Web</p>	<p>https://www.dm.martinique.developpement-durable.gouv.fr/?lang=fr</p>	
	<p>Social networks</p>	<p>Facebook</p>	<p>-</p>
		<p>Instagram</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/mer_gouv/?hl=es</p>
		<p>Twitter</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/MerGouv/</p>
		<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/mer-gouv/</p>

Business name	Cluster Maritime Martinique (CMM)		Logo	
Company name	Martinique Maritime Cluster			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)			
Type of service	<p>The Martinique Maritime Club (CMM) is an organisation created in 2013 by and for professionals. Its aim is to bring together local maritime players, carry out their projects and develop the maritime sector in Martinique. From industry to services, the CMM is made up of companies of all sizes, centres of competitiveness, federations and associations, laboratories and research centres, schools and training organisations, local authorities and economic agents, as well as the French Marina.</p> <p>The CMM is building a true business-generating ecosystem with its members. Faced with an extremely competitive economy, it is imperative to create synergies between maritime players, so that the entire economy can benefit from the maritime sector's capacity for innovation and the business opportunities offered by activities at sea.</p>			
Competences	<p>The CMM statutes have three objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The promotion and defence of Martinique's maritime and related activities. • The study of its possibilities for the development of the marine-maritime sector. • To carry out all the actions in the areas of intervention of these activities and in particular: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Transport of goods and travellers. – Nautical. – Fishing. – Marine research and protection. – Harbour and port services. – Maritime training and employment. – Maritime finance. – Shipbuilding and repair. – Renewable energies. 			
Capacities	<p>To achieve its objectives, the CMM proposes establishing 3 vectors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Institutional communication. ▪ Operational synergies. ▪ Actions of influence. 			
Contact details	Direction	22, rue Ernest Deproge, 97200 Fort-de-France, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) (06) 96 45 12 20		
	Mail	president@cluster-maritime-martinique.org		
Information resources	Web	https://www.cluster-maritime-martinique.org/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/clustermaritimemartinique/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/ClusterMaritim1	
	LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/in/clustermaritimemartinique/		

Business name	Yacht Club Martinique		Logo	
Company name	Yacht Club Martinique			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)			
Type of service	Founded in 1935, the Yacht Club Martinique is a meeting place for lovers of sailing and water sports. With a rich history and a dynamic community, it is an important player in the promotion of sailing and the preservation of the marine environment in Martinique.			
Competences	The Yacht Club Martinique promotes sailing and protects Martinique's marine environment through events and training for sailing enthusiasts of all levels that impart sailing skills, bring the sea closer to people and raise awareness about the protection of the maritime environment.			
Capacities	<p>The Yacht Club welcomes sailors of all ages and levels and organises events and training sessions to showcase the beauty and challenges of sailing.</p> <p>The Yacht Club Martinique has state-of-the-art nautical infrastructure, with moorings for yachts of various sizes, a reception points for auxiliary boats and a hire station.</p> <p>On the other hand, the club has several qualified instructors and coaches who give lectures, training and courses throughout the year.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Boulevard Chevalier Sainte-Marthe, Fort-de-France, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 63 26 76		
	Mail	ycmq972@orange.fr		
Information resources	Web	https://www.yacht-club-martinique.com/#		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/ycmq972/?locale=fr_FR	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/yachtclubdelamartinique/?_d=1%2F	
		Twitter	-	
	LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/in/yacht-club-yacht-club-de-la-martinique-09628b121		

Business name	Marina Pointe du Bout	Logo	-	
Company name	Marina Pointe du Bout			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)			
Type of service	<p>The Pointe du Bout Marina is a port organisation located in the bay of Fort-de-France in Martinique.</p> <p>They have a small, well-protected marina with hotels in the immediate vicinity and access to a ferry with a connection to Fort de France.</p>			
Competences	Marina Pointe du Bout's main activity is the management of moorings and other port services, as well as the administration of its infrastructures and the management of companies and services offered by third parties in these infrastructures.			
Capacities	<p>The Marina can accommodate a hundred boats up to 19 metres long, 6 metres wide and 3 metres draught.</p> <p>They also have 14 moorings for visitors on holiday.</p> <p>The marina's moorings and annexed facilities offer the following services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Water and electricity supply. ▪ Reception services, tourist information, arrival declaration's ▪ Access to weather forecasts. ▪ Internet connection via wifi. ▪ Tie certificate. ▪ Air conditioning and showers available 24 hours a day. ▪ Waste collection service. ▪ Local services: shops, pharmacy, restaurants, automatic cash machines, bars, hotels, car hire, doctors, nurses, physiotherapists, hairdressers, beauty salon, casino, launderette, mini-market, water sports (day trips, boat hire, snorkelling, fishing, parasailing), beaches with tubs, access to Fort de France, etc. 			
Contact details	Direction	Rue des Bougainvillees 57, Les Trois-Îlets, 97229, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 66 07 74		
	Mail	marina.3ilets@marina3ilets.fr		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/pages/Marina%20De%20La%20Pointe%20Du%20Bout/628417910570392/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/marina3ilets/?locale=es_ES%2F	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Marina du François	Logo	-	
Company name	Marina du François			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)			
Type of service	A marina located in the centre of the east coast of Martinique, in the bay of Le François.			
Competences	The marina mainly accommodates small, motorised pleasure boats and sailboats belonging to the island's residents.			
Capacities	<p>The marina offers small facilities for mooring shallow-draft vessels, as well as basic harbour services. Sailors will find everything they need to moor their boat, carry out small repairs or refit. In addition, the marina is surrounded by restaurants, shops and other services.</p> <p>In addition to the sports harbour, there is a lively fishing harbour where local fishermen sell their fresh catches every day.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Baie du François, 97240 972, La Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 54 29 54		
	Mail	glennjeanjoseph@yahoo.fr		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=239573269400065&_rd=1	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/explore/locations/5648632/marina-du-francois/recent/	
		Twitter	-	
LinkedIn		-		

Business name	Marina du Robert	Logo		
Company name	Marina du Robert			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)			
Type of service	La Marina du Robert is a small private marina built on the foundations of an old, abandoned sugar refinery on the east coast of the island of Martinique.			
Competences	Marina du Robert was designed as a car park for small motorboats.			
Capacities	Marina du Robert offers: <ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Basic sports harbour services (mooring (about 50 points), maintenance, etc.).▪ Boat hire services.▪ Services of a small ship repair shop.▪ Catering services.▪ Accommodation services.			
Contact details	Direction	Lime kiln, Le Robert, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 65 38 74		
	Mail	marinadurobert@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://marinadurobert.fr/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/JenniferEvasion/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/explore/locations/28926423/marina-du-robert/	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Marina du Marin	Logo	
Company name	Marina du Marin		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Insular (Martinique)		
Type of service	Marina du Marin is a sports port and recreation centre located in the municipality of Marin, on the island of Martinique.		
Competences	<p>Marina du Marin offers the following services and activities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nautical: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Sailing and motorboat hire. – Fishing equipment. ▪ Leisure: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Donuts. – Boat dive. – Watercraft. ▪ Food: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Bakeries. – Restaurants – Pizzerias. ▪ Shopping: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Souvenirs – Food. ▪ Health and beauty: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Doctor/Nurse. – Physiotherapist. ▪ Technical service: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Repair of candles and candle holders. – Sale and repair of spare parts. ▪ Services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mail office. – Cajero automatic. – Laundry. 		
Capacities	<p>The marina is mainly dedicated to the reception and mooring of vessels up to 60 metres in length and 4.8 metres in draught.</p> <p>The harbour has 830 moorings, 100 boats and a team of 78 professionals who offer sailors boat handling, repair and maintenance services.</p> <p>Marina du Marin also offers a wide range of services available inside the Marina, such as fuel refuelling, an automatic laundry, a medical centre, a port workshop opens every day, video surveillance and a black water and grey water collection service.</p> <p>The area also periodically offers musical or cultural events or entertainments throughout the year.</p>		

	They also have a coworking space for companies.		
Contact details	Direction	Port de Plaisance, Bassin tortue, 97290 Le Marin, Martinique	
	Telephone	(+596) 74 83 83	
	Mail	contact@marina-martinique.fr	
Information resources	Web	https://www.marina-martinique.fr/marin/en/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/marinadumarin/
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/marinadumarin/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/MarinaduMarin
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/marina-du-marin

Business name	Université des Antilles - Pôle Martinique		Logo	
Company name	University of Antilles			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Antilles) and Insular (Pôle Martinique)			
Type of service	Nestled in the Caribbean, the University of the Antilles responds to the socio-economic challenges of its surroundings and offers an exceptional field of experimentation in diverse fields: climatology, volcanism, tropical ecosystems, health, sport and epidemiology, renewable energies, multilingualism, social inclusion, interculturality, heritage and culture.			
Competences	<p>The University of the Antilles covers all disciplinary fields. It has 13 support teams, 8 mixed research units and 4 federative structures. These units are divided into three major research areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sustainable development and biodiversity. ▪ Health, Sport and the Tropical Environment. ▪ Territories and societies. 			
Capacities	The University has different campuses throughout the French Antilles, including the island of Martinique. This entity has capacities for university training, research and participation in transnational cooperation projects in different areas.			
Contact details	Direction	Schœlcher Campus, Schœlcher, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 72 73 01		
	Mail	-		
Information resources	Web	http://www.univ-ag.fr/organisation-fonctionnement/pole-martinique		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=100058823991519	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/univantilles/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/univantilles/	
		Youtube	https://www.youtube.com/user/UnivAntillesGuyaneTV	
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/school/universit-des-antilles/?originalSubdomain=fr			

Business name	Seafret Caraibes		Logo	
Company name	Seafret Caraibes			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Logistics and transport company that promotes ecological nautical cargo in the Caribbean region.			
Competences	The company centres its activity on the maritime and fluvial transport of goods.			
Capacities	-			
Contact details	Direction	Villa Campêche, La Wallon Quarter, Les Trois-Îlets, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 696 75 48 47		
	Mail	seafret@hotmail.fr		
Information resources	Web	seafretcaraibes.com		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/SeafretCaraibes/	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	https://x.com/SeafretCaraibes	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Les Ti'Fumés de Clément		Logo	
Company name	Les Ti'Fumés de Clément			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Les Ti'Fumés de Clément is a small company dedicated to the manufacture of artisan smoked and spiced products, located in the heart of Martinique.			
Competences	Promote through know-how the local production of quality fish products from small-scale artisanal fishing, sustainable aquaculture and extensive livestock farming in Martinique.			
Capacities	It has a workshop equipped with the materials and equipment needed to process fish and other seafood products.			
Contact details	Direction	Chemin la Borélie, Quartier Dumaine, Gros-Morne 97213, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 696 73 96 98		
	Mail	contact@lestifumesdeclement.fr		
Information resources	Web	https://www.lestifumesdeclement.fr/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LesTiFumesDeClement/?locale=fr_FR	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/lestifumes/	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Skipper Antilles Charter		Logo	
Company name	Skipper Antilles Charter			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Skipper Antilles Charter is a family-run business dedicated to sea excursions and catamaran hire.			
Competences	<p>The company centres its activity on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Boat excursions along the coast of Martinique and other Grenadine islands. ▪ Multi-day cruises around the Grenadines and other Caribbean islands. ▪ Paddle. ▪ Kayak. ▪ Windsurfing, ▪ Kitesurf. ▪ Sport fishing. 			
Capacities	The company has a fleet of five perfectly equipped catamarans.			
Contact details	Direction	Patrón Antillas Charter, Marina du Marin, Le Marin 97290, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 696 17 77 99		
	Mail	skipperantillescharter@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.skipper-antilles.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/croisierecatamaranskipperantillesgrenadines/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/skipperantillescharter/?hl=es	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/company/skipper-antilles	

Business name	Punch Croisières		Logo	
Company name	Punch Croisières			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Boat hire company, both monohulls and multihulls, both short and long-stay. They also organise cruises to various Caribbean islands.			
Competences	<p>The company's main activities are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boat charter (sailboats, monohulls, catamarans, etc.). • Yacht management and boat sales. • Cruises along the coast of Martinique, Dominica, Trinidad, Antigua, Saint Lucia, Saint Vincent and the Grenadines. • Car hire. • Hire or sale of water sports equipment. • Food supplies and the local market. 			
Capacities	<p>There are 18 boats carefully selected for their seaworthiness and perfectly equipped to provide comfort and autonomy (water heater, solar panels, etc.).</p> <p>It is an environmentally responsible company, using ecological, economical, silent and low-emission vessels.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Port de Plaisance du Marin, Le Marin, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 74 89 18		
	Mail	contact@punch-croisieres.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.punch-croisieres.com/en		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://fr-fr.facebook.com/punch.croisieres/	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/punch_croisieres/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/punchcroisieres	
		LinkedIn	https://es.linkedin.com/company/punch-croisieres?trk=similar-pages_result-card_full-click	

Business name	La Survy	Logo	
Company name	La Survy Distrib		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)		
Type of service	<p>Survay is a company dedicated to providing sales, repair and maintenance services for pneumatic boats.</p> <p>They also offer sales and maintenance services for lifeboats, as well as maintenance and sales of lifeboats.</p>		
Competences	<p>Survay offers various services complementary to the sale of pneumatic boats, ferries and lifeboats.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boat sales and repair service. • Nautical certifications. • Naval safety. • Repair of PVC or NEOPRENO HYPALON pneumatic boats. • Mounting the float on the hull. • Float replacement. • General semi-rigid maintenance. • After-sales service for the ZODIAC - BOMBARD - AKA MARINE - ZODIAC MILPRO - PLASTIMO brands. • Review of rafts and life rafts. • Technical assistance for the assembly of the rafts. • Specialists in the assembly of supports for professional boats. 		
Capacities	<p>La Survay has a 300 m² studio divided into two air-conditioned rooms:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One dedicated to the repair of pneumatic vessels. • The other to overhaul rafts and lifeboats. <p>The company offers a wide selection of pneumatic vessels and rescue rafts, both for sale and for overhaul and repair services. They have a wide range of Zodiac and similar vessels, as well as rafts and other navigational and rescue equipment.</p>		
Contact details	Direction	Quartier Montgerald, 97290, Le Marin, Martinique	
	Telephone	(+596) 596 74 63 63	
	Mail	la.survay@wanadoo.fr comptasurvay@gmail.com	
Information resources	Web	https://www.la-survy-vente-reparation.com/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/p/Zodiac-La-Survay-Distrib-100064802916012/?_rdr
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/la_survy972/?api=postMessage

		Twitter	-
		LinkedIn	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/la-suryy?trk=public_profile_topcard-current-company

Business name	Bateau Centre		Logo	
Company name	Centrale du Bateau - Location & Vente - Bateaux moteur			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Company dedicated to buying, selling or renting motorboats in Martinique, Guadeloupe, San Martín and San Bartolomé.			
Competences	<p>They specialise in buying motorboats, offering:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive experience on boats. • Professional advice on buying or selling. • Adapted financing solutions. • Personalised insurance. • A fast and smooth transaction, • Register. • Network of professionals at your service. • On-demand maintenance contract service. • Searching for and importing boats. • Motorboat and yacht hire. • Customised service. • Personalised search for boats or yachts. • Photographic and video reports. • Boat test. • Update to CE standards. • Transport France - Europe - USA - Antilles. • Authorisations and certificates. 			
Capacities	<p>Hire of multiple models of motorboats or yachts for 1/2-day, one day or longer. All boats are equipped with an awning and GPS.</p> <p>There are options for wakeboarding, paddle boarding and water skiing (adults and children).</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Boulevard Allègre, Marina, Le Marin 97290, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 696 43 70 11 / (+596) 596 74 24 02		
	Mail	contact@centraledubateau.fr		
Information resources	Web	https://www.centraledubateau.fr/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CentraleduBateau.fr	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/centraledubateau/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/centralebateau	
	LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/in/sebastien-gierden-35151962		

Business name	Fort de France SNSM	Logo
Company name	SNSM - Sauvetage en Mer	
Type of organisation		
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)	
Type of service	A non-profit association whose main mission is to provide voluntary and free assistance to human lives in danger at sea and on the coast, as well as organising maritime rescue in Fort-de-France.	
Competences	<p>Their missions at sea and on the coast: Rescue, prevention and training.</p> <p>The SNSM is one of the main players in search and rescue at sea.</p> <p>Maritime rescuers intervene at the request of the regional surveillance and rescue operating centres (CROSS), carry out search operations at sea, assist boats in difficulty, assess the condition of people who need to be rescued, provide them with first aid and take the injured and shipwrecked to the shore, where other rescue organisations take care of them.</p> <p>The regional operational surveillance and rescue centres are the heart of the search and rescue system at sea. Their missions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure permanent monitoring of rescue devices. • Receiving and analysing distress messages. • Planning search and rescue operations. • Activate and coordinate the most appropriate means of intervention: boats in the area, rescue boats, helicopters, etc. <p>On the other hand, thanks to their constant monitoring of the baths on the beaches, the SNSM rescue swimmers are the first to be present in the event of an incident. Trained in first aid and intervention in aquatic environments, they are the first link in the coastal rescue chain.</p> <p>During the summer season, municipalities and coastal communities have a legal obligation to organise surveillance of their beaches. To cover this, they employ qualified rescuers who are able to carry out different types of interventions, coordinate and prevent rescues and provide first aid.</p> <p>Their missions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide assistance to bathers in danger and users of beach equipment (windsurfing boards, inflatable equipment, kitesurfing, small sailboats, etc.) in difficulty. • Administering first aid to accident victims. • Report problems to the appropriate emergency units. 	

	<p>Alongside these rescue actions, the maritime rescuers present on the beaches carry out extensive prevention work with holidaymakers to reduce the risk of accidents.</p> <p>Civil security is any measure implemented by the state to protect its population. It brings together the prevention of risks of all kinds, the information and warning of the population, as well as the protection of people, property and the environment against accidents, disasters and catastrophes. Its action is characterised by the preparation and application of appropriate measures and media in relation to the State, local authorities and other public or private persons. It is a public service in which a large number of stakeholders participate, including authorised associations such as the SNSM.</p> <p>The association also offers training services in the field of marine and coastal safety, as well as prevention and safety awareness services for the general public, through the organisation of days, demonstrations, initiations, workshops, etc.</p>									
Capacities	<p>SNSM has 206 rescue stations spread all along the coastline. 5,800 volunteer rescuers on board intervene up to 20 nautical miles from the coast from the 206 rescue stations. By 2023, 188 permanent stations covered the entire coastline. 18 seasonal stations complete the network during the summer period and serve as a link with the municipalities if the beaches monitored by the lifeguards do not have permanent lifeguard stations in the vicinity.</p> <p>Each of the permanent stations is headed by a president, assisted by a treasurer and the titular chief. It is responsible for recruiting and training its crew.</p> <p>For their part, 1,322 SNSM rescue swimmers are dedicated to securing the French coast. The stations are staffed by a crew of between 10 and 40 operational volunteers.</p> <p>1,322 SNSM rescue swimmers distributed among the 229 first aid posts that intervene in the bathing areas authorised up to 300 metres from the coast. Rescue swimmers, with an average age of between 18 and 25, made up of 2/3 men and 1/3 women, are mainly students (2/3) and young employees.</p> <p>The SNSM has a fleet of more than 785 nautical vehicles: 41 canoes, 35 1st class speedboats, 75 2nd class speedboats, 42 light speedboats, 90 motorised nautical vehicles (scooters) and 473 pneumatic speedboats, 192 of which are semi-rigid.</p>									
Contact details	Direction	Maurice Bishop Avenue, Fort-de-France 97200, Martinique								
	Telephone	(+596) 696 35 22 56								
	Mail	president.fort-de-france@snsm.org								
Information resources	Web	https://station-fortdefrance.snsm.org/								
	Social networks	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="687 1527 855 1576">Facebook</td> <td data-bbox="855 1527 1461 1576">https://www.facebook.com/SNSMFoyal/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="687 1576 855 1626">Instagram</td> <td data-bbox="855 1576 1461 1626">https://www.instagram.com/sauveteurs_en_mer/</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="687 1626 855 1675">Twitter</td> <td data-bbox="855 1626 1461 1675">https://twitter.com/@SauveteursenMer</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="687 1675 855 1738">LinkedIn</td> <td data-bbox="855 1675 1461 1738">https://mq.linkedin.com/in/snsm-fort-de-france-3792a72a4</td> </tr> </table>	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/SNSMFoyal/	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/sauveteurs_en_mer/	Twitter	https://twitter.com/@SauveteursenMer	LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/in/snsm-fort-de-france-3792a72a4
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/SNSMFoyal/									
Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/sauveteurs_en_mer/									
Twitter	https://twitter.com/@SauveteursenMer									
LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/in/snsm-fort-de-france-3792a72a4									

Business name	Martinique Tourism Committee (CMT)	Logo
Company name	Martinique Tourism Committee (CMT)	
Type of organisation		
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)	
Type of service	The Martinique Tourism Committee (CMT), which brings together elected officials, representatives of public organisations and business leaders from the world of tourism, works to showcase Martinique to the public and promote it as a destination among professionals.	
Competences	<p>Created in 2003 by the Regional and Departmental Communities of Martinique, the CMT is the institutional instrument responsible for Martinique's tourism development. It is the main actor in all of Martinique's tourism development and promotion issues.</p> <p>The Martinique Tourist Board aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revitalising the destination. • Make Martinique an emblematic destination. • Raise the quality level of services compared to competing destinations. • To have a significant impact on the local economy in order to implement a virtuous dynamic. <p>To this end, the following missions have been defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in the development and execution of the Martinique Tourism Development and Planning Plan and prepare, at the request of the Martinique Territorial Collective, all the necessary documents and studies for the implementation of political decisions. • Establish and operate a system for observing, monitoring, analysing and forecasting the different dimensions of tourism in Martinique, the tourist emitting markets and competing destinations, in order to define a strategy for the development and promotion of a reasoned and evolving Martinique. • To be a place for consultation, proposals, recommendations, coordination, needs assessment and follow-up with public authorities and companies for the design and implementation of tourism products and sectors by these partners. • Participate in the implementation of Martinique's tourism development policy, in line with the guidelines of the Regional Development Plan, the Sea Development Plan and the Tourism Development Plan. • Designing a policy for the reception of tourists in Martinique and organising useful reception actions, coordinating information on activities to promote the territory, carrying out awareness-raising actions among the Martinican population about their interest and ways of becoming positively involved in tourist reception, and supporting those responsible for projects related to major events (cultural, sporting, etc.) that could be strong vectors for promotion on foreign markets. 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participate in the implementation of the tourism vocational training policy based on the guidelines defined by the Martinique Territorial Collective. • Ensure the monitoring and carry out periodic evaluations of all its actions, as well as those of its members. • Promotion through a Commercial Action Plan. • The development and attractiveness of the territory reinforces action in Martinique through actions related to development, the valorisation of our assets, the improvement of our product, our services and our infrastructures. • The aim of strategy, engineering and foresight is to support projects, evaluate the actions carried out, help guide territorial policy and anticipate development prospects. This includes monitoring and training. 			
Capacities	<p>The CMT is structured in two workshops. The CMT's Americas Office is responsible for designing, implementing and coordinating all aspects of Martinique's tourism promotion in North America, the United States and Canada. For its part, the CMT's France-Europe workshop, promoted by the Martinique Territorial Collective and under the chairmanship of the Martinique Tourism Committee, is a veritable information exchange space dedicated to Martinique's tourism promotion.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	-		
	Telephone	-		
	Mail	infos.cmt@martiniquetourisme.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.martinique.org/fr/comite-martiniquais-du-tourisme		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/LaMartiniqueTourisme	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/lamartinique/	
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/lamartinique	
		LinkedIn	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/comit%C3%A9-martiniquais-du-tourisme	

Business name	Kato Mambo	Logo		
Company name	Sarl Kato Mambo			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Agency specialising in the organisation of sea excursions on catamarans in Martinique with 20 years' experience.			
Competences	<p>They offer a wide range of catamaran and cruise excursions around Martinique and various regions of the Caribbean.</p> <p>They also include excursions for dolphin spotting and snorkelling.</p> <p>Possibility of organising private excursions.</p>			
Capacities	<p>They offer you the chance to spend a summer's day or night on one of their stable, comfortable and spacious sailing catamarans. They have 3 catamaran models available.</p> <p>They emphasise the pleasures of sailing the Caribbean Sea in complete safety. A professional crew will accompany you on your tailor-made mini cruise.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Marina de la pointe du bout, 97229 Trois ilets, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 661 183 / (+596) 696 252 316		
	Mail	contact@kata-mambo.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.kata-mambo.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/katamambo3ilets/	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	CAP Antilles International		Logo	CAP ANTILLES INTERNATIONAL
Company name	CAP Antilles International - SARL			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Company dedicated to the sale of rigid and semi-rigid hull vessels.			
Competences	<p>The company offers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sales and maintenance of rigid-hulled boats (Capelli) with Yamaha or Suzuki engines. ▪ Sales and maintenance of semi-rigid hull boats (Capelli) with Yamaha or Suzuki engines. ▪ Sale of boat accessories and fittings. ▪ Sale of spare parts for boat engines and refuelling. ▪ Sales and maintenance of ship refurbishments. ▪ Services related to boat repair and maintenance. <p>We also have a selection of used motorboats and boat engines.</p> <p>With regard to maintenance services, they carry out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Periodic maintenance of boat engines. ▪ High pressure cleaning. ▪ Anti-fouling treatment. ▪ Repair of nautical parts. ▪ Maintenance of a semi-rigid flotation. ▪ Remoulding repairs. 			
Capacities	<p>They have an extensive catalogue of semi-rigid hull boats divided into various categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Luxury boat line. • Line of boats with superior services. • Line of boats with simple services. • Line of work boats. • They also have a wide range of rigid hull boats, divided into the following categories: • Line with cover. • Free line. 			
Contact details	Direction	32 Av Maurice Bishop, Fort-de-France 97200, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 39 33 33		
	Mail	-		
Information resources	Web	https://www.capantilles.fr/		
	Social networks	LinkedIn	https://mq.linkedin.com/in/cap-antilles-32066711b	

Business name	Carbet des Sciences		Logo	
Company name	Carbet Des Sciences - CCSTI Martinique			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Territorial reference centre for scientific, technical and industrial culture (CCSTI) in Martinique.			
Competences	<p>The Carbet des Sciences aims to make science, technology and innovation accessible to everyone, offering the public the means to learn about and reflect on the scientific and technical advances of our time, promote debate and foster vocations.</p> <p>The mission of Carbet Des Sciences son:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a link between science and society by disseminating general knowledge about science and technology to all types of audiences. • Create and disseminate educational and entertaining tools. • Coordinate scientific, technical and industrial culture actions that promote collaboration between organisations in Martinique. 			
Capacities	<p>They offer itinerant scientific activities on various themes that adapt to each type of audience, to suit big and small children. Fun and interactive, their activities are made up of manipulations, games, experiments... to favour better assimilation.</p> <p>They are also in charge of coordinating the annual event "The Science Festival in the Martinique Region".</p> <p>They also offer all their resources by reservation to schools, libraries, municipalities and other community spaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exhibition panels • Educational stuccos • Robotics kit • Models <p>Carbet des Sciences has developed extensive skills in the design of educational tools, such as games, experiments, workshops, exhibitions and caravans, land and sea educational itineraries and other events.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Gondeau, Le Lamentin 97232, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 39 86 48		
	Mail	comunicación@carbet-sciences.com		
Information resources	Web	https://www.carbet-sciences.com/		
	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/CarbetDesSciences		

	Social networks	Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/carbet_des_sciences/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/CarbetDSciences
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/carbet-des-sciences/

Business name	CAP Caravelle		Logo	
Company name	CAP Caravelle			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Boat hire and sports activities company.			
Competences	They offer fast, stable and multi-purpose boats for hire for one or several days. They also offer wakeboards, paddle boats and water ski equipment.			
Capacities	The boats on offer have capacity for seven people and are equipped with awnings, showers, ski masters, scales, benches, tables and GPS.			
Contact details	Direction	Marina du Robert - Jennifer Evasion, Le Robert, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+33) 602 06 53 98		
	Mail	katecaraibes@outlook.fr		
Information resources	Web	-		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/p/Cap-caravelle-100057332894386/?locale=ca_ES	
		Instagram	-	
		Twitter	-	
		LinkedIn	-	

Business name	Club de Découverte des Sciences Astronomiques (CDSA)		Logo	
Company name	Club de Découverte des Sciences Astronomiques (CDSA)			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	CDSA organises its activities in Martinique.			
Competences	<p>Organising actions and debates linked not only to the promotion of astronomy but also to the dissemination of scientific culture.</p> <p>For the last ten years, the CDSA has been working in Martinique, organising events for all those interested in astronomy: zenithal eclipse, science festival, starry night, media interventions, astronomy school, creation of documents, publication of information leaflets.</p> <p>To take part in the discovery of celestial objects, the CDSA makes itself available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A documentary fund (written, audiovisual and electronic documents) managed by the CDST of Saint-Pierre with which the CDSA has signed an agreement to make the documents available. ▪ Introductory astronomy courses. ▪ Sky observation sessions. ▪ Documents produced in Martinique: 			
Capacities	<p>The CDSA guaranteed the coordination of the first General States of Scientific Culture in Martinique in 1989. Since then, various public structures have been set up.</p> <p>The CDSA organises meetings and events for the general public, with material (room, space) and financial (funding for publications, posters, etc.) support from local authorities. The association has achieved a certain notoriety and has become a reference point for astronomy in Martinique.</p> <p>The CDSA has the capacity to train and sensitise the population, young people and target audiences such as nautical companies, to astronomy and the observation of stars and constellations.</p>			
Contact details	Direction	452 D résidence du vieux moulin, Fort-de-France, Martinique, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 696 45 60 56		
	Mail	contact.bietc@gmail.com		
Information resources	Web	www.cieltropical.com		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/cieltropical/?locale=fr_FR	

Business name	Centre de Decouverte des Sciences de la Terre (CDST)	Logo	-	
Company name	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Establishment for the dissemination of scientific, technical and industrial culture.			
Competences	<p>Almost 100 years after the eruption of Mount Pelée, which destroyed the town of Saint-Pierre on 8 May 1902, the elected representatives of Martinique's General Council decided to launch the project to build the Centre de Découverte des Sciences de la Terre (Earth Sciences Discovery Centre) in Saint-Pierre in July 1998. At the time, they wanted a place to remember the disaster and raise awareness of major risks. In 2004, the Centre de Découverte des Sciences de la Terre (Earth Sciences Discovery Centre) was inaugurated, with the complementary aims of disseminating scientific, technical and industrial culture and boosting Martinique's northern Caribbean region.</p> <p>The CDST is currently being overhauled.</p>			
Capacities	Today, the CDST offers temporary and permanent exhibitions and runs science workshops, particularly on volcanism and the major natural hazards to which Martinique is exposed. It also organises events (film screenings, theatrical and musical performances, etc.).			
Contact details	Direction	CDST, Habitation Perrinelle, Saint-Pierre 97250, Martinique		
	Telephone	(+596) 596 52 82 42		
	Mail			
Information resources	Web	https://cdst.e-monsite.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/collectivitedemartinique	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ctm_martinique/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/CTM_Martinique	
		LinkedIn	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/collectivit%C3%A9-de-martinique	

Business name	Observatoire du Morne des Cadets	Logo	-	
Company name	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Historic monument			
Competences	<p>Built in 1935 and listed as a Historic Monument in 2012, the Morne des Cadets Observatory is actually located on the Morne Moustin (Fonds Saint-Denis), from where it offers a breathtaking view of the UNESCO property. A cultural and scientific heritage site, it has always been occupied by people of science, including the illustrious Professor Alfred LACROIX and, until very recently, the teams from the Observatoire Volcanologique et Sismologique de la Martinique (OVSM-IPGP). It is also home to one of the world's few De Quervain-Piccard seismographs, a precious instrument dating from the early 20th century, which is also listed. Before the departure of the OVSM-IPGP, the Observatory was occasionally visited by the public. It is now completely closed.</p> <p>The Observatory is currently being refurbished as a centre for the dissemination of scientific culture on volcanological and seismological research.</p>			
Capacities	The Observatory has a viewpoint over the UNESCO property (Montagne Pelée and the Pitons du Carbet). The Observatory houses old instrumentation (including the De Quervain-Piccard seismograph, listed as a Historic Monument).			
Contact details	Direction	Morne Monstin, Fonds-Saint-Denis 97250, Martinique		
	Telephone			
	Mail			
Information resources	Web	https://www.guidemartinique.com/visites/observatoire-morne-cadets-montagne-pelee.php		
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/collectivitedemartinique	
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ctm_martinique/	
		Twitter	https://x.com/CTM_Martinique	
		LinkedIn	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/collectivit%C3%A9-de-martinique	

Business name	Maison des Volcans	Logo	-
Company name	Collectivité Territoriale de Martinique		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)		
Type of service	Natural History Museum		
Competences	<p>Created in June 1990 on the initiative of the Mayor of Morne-Rouge, Mr Pierre PETIT, who wanted to raise awareness of Mount Pelée and volcanism in Martinique, it was inaugurated in May 1991 in the presence of Maurice and Katia KRAFFT, the famous French volcanologist couple. At the time, there was no way of explaining the workings of a volcano to the general public in Martinique and raising awareness of the implications of its presence on the island. The current concept of the Maison des Volcans is to offer a natural history museum-style introduction to Mount Pelée, the volcanoes of Martinique and the Caribbean as a whole.</p> <p>The Maison des Volcans is currently being redesigned.</p>		
Capacities	The Maison des Volcans now offers exhibitions, film screenings and workshops, particularly on volcanism and the town of Morne Rouge.		
Contact details	Direction	Avenue Edgar Nestoret, Le Morne Rouge 97260, Martinique	
	Telephone	+596 596 80 71 22	
	Mail		
Information resources	Web	https://www.martinique-tour.com/offres/maison-des-volcans-le-morne-rouge-fr-1370155/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/collectivitedemartinique
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ctm_martinique/
		Twitter	https://x.com/CTM_Martinique
		LinkedIn	https://fr.linkedin.com/company/collectivit%C3%A9-de-martinique

Business name	La Pirogue Kalina	Logo	-	
Company name	La Pirogue Kalina			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	Excursion activities.			
Competences	Networking of businesses and services to promote and support the enhancement of our heritage.			
Capacities	Excursion activities.			
Contact details	Direction	10 Impasse des Amandines		
	Telephone			
	Mail	duchelp@wanadoo.fr		
Information resources	Web			
	Social networks	Facebook		
		Instagram		
		Twitter		
LinkedIn				

Business name	Office Français de la Biodiversité (OFB)	Logo	
Company name	Office Français de la Biodiversité (OFB)		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	National (France)		
Type of service	<p>The French Biodiversity Office (OFB) is a public body committed to safeguarding biodiversity in both mainland France and its overseas territories. In the French West Indies, it employs nearly 40 people in Guadeloupe and Martinique.</p> <p>The French Biodiversity Office was created on the January 1, 2020, following Act no. 2019-773 of July 24, 2019, and operates under the authority of the Ministry for Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion and the Ministry for Agriculture and Food Sovereignty. The Director General of the OFB is Olivier Thibault.</p> <p>Its mission is to protect and restore biodiversity across aquatic, terrestrial, and marine environments, playing a critical role in addressing the erosion of biodiversity. This includes combating pressures such as habitat destruction and fragmentation, various forms of pollution, over-exploitation of natural resources, the spread of invasive alien species, and the effects of climate change.</p> <p>Every day, the OFB works to engage a wide range of stakeholders, decision-makers and citizens in biodiversity preservation, including the State, local authorities, associations, businesses, scientists, farmers, fishermen, hunters, nature sports enthusiasts, etc. It plays an essential role in reducing the pressures on fauna, flora and their habitats.</p>		
Competences	<p>The creation of the French Biodiversity Office reflects the need to step up the fight to preserve living things by placing expertise and action at the service of 5 complementary missions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Environmental policing: The French Biodiversity Office contributes to the administrative and judicial policing of water, natural areas, wild flora and fauna, hunting and fishing. 2. Knowledge and expertise: A better understanding of species, environments, the services provided by biodiversity and the threats it faces is essential if we are to protect living things. 3. Support for public policies: From international to local, the OFB's teams work to support public policies to meet the challenges of preserving biodiversity. 4. Management and restoration of protected areas: Direct management of the OFB's protected areas is carried out as close to the field as possible. <p>Mobilising stakeholders and citizens: Shifting the balance in favour of biodiversity means triggering transformations that affect all aspects of human society. This challenge can only be met by mobilising everyone.</p>		
Capacities	<p>To fulfil its missions, the Office relies on multi-disciplinary teams (environmental inspectors, engineers, veterinary surgeons, technicians, administrative staff, etc.) composed of over 3,000 agents across the country. It operates on three levels:</p>		

		<ul style="list-style-type: none">• a national level, where the OFB's policy is defined and steered (national directorates and delegations);• a regional level, where regional coordination and implementation take place (regional directorates and maritime delegations);• departmental and local levels of operational and specific implementation (departmental services, marine nature parks, Agoa sanctuary, reserves and territories, etc.), supported by mobile intervention brigades and specialised units.	
Contact details	Direction	5 Rue de la Dorade, Anse à l'âne, 97229 Les Trois Ilets - Martinique	
	Telephone	05 96 70 41 42	
	Mail	sd972@ofb.gouv.fr	
Information resources	Web	https://www.ofb.gouv.fr/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/OFBiodiversite
		Instagram	https://www.instagram.com/ofbiodiversite/
		Twitter	https://twitter.com/OFBiodiversite
		LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/office-francais-biodiversite/

Business name	French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER)	Logo	
Company name	French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (IFREMER)		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	National (France)		
Type of service	<p>Ifremer (French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea) is a public industrial and commercial establishment (EPIC) dedicated to advancing the knowledge of the oceans and their resources, monitoring of the marine and coastal environment and promoting the sustainable development of maritime activities.</p> <p>The Délégation Ifremer des Antilles, located in Martinique, is the only office in the French West Indies.</p> <p>Ifremer operates since 1970 and plays a leading role in managing biological resources and the marine environment. The institute conducts research that supports public policy and contributes to the sustainable socio-economic development of the professional sectors that exploit these resources. Its Biodiversity and Environment research unit focuses primarily on fisheries, aquaculture and the marine environment.</p>		
Competences	<p>Ifremer's activities in the French West Indies are mainly focused on fisheries, aquaculture and the coastal environment. All these activities support public policies related to the sustainable development of the socio-professional sectors that rely on marine resources. Given the interconnected nature of these three areas, Ifremer adopts an ecosystem approach that integrates both biological resources and the environment:</p> <p><u>Marine fish farming</u>: this is a key focus of the Biodiversity research unit. Following research projects that achieved full mastery of the red drum (<i>Sciaenops Ocellatus</i>) rearing cycle, Ifremer is now working on transferring this expertise to the industry. This transfer is being facilitated through collaboration with the Collectivité Territoriale de la Martinique. At the same time, Ifremer is contributing its knowledge to the design and construction of a territorial Aquaculture Technical Centre, which will assume many of the technical roles previously handled by Ifremer. With this transition, the Unit will be able to focus on new research programmes such as aquaculture diversification and the relationship between aquaculture and the environment.</p> <p><u>Fisheries</u>: A major part of the research unit's activity is devoted to marine resources integrated into their environment, through the organisation and development of fisheries observatories in Martinique and Guadeloupe. The SIH tool serves as a strategic database, providing critical information in response to the increasing demand for detailed fisheries data. Through this work, an in-depth reflection on fisheries management is being undertaken with the stakeholders concerned, including first and foremost the professionals. This collaborative approach to fisheries management is supported by consolidated knowledge of the state of shared offshore resources, which forms the basis of the multidisciplinary 'MAGDELESA' Interreg Caribbean project. This project, conducted in cooperation with the FAO/COPACO and several countries in the</p>		

	<p>Lesser Antilles, promotes the sustainable development of fishing using anchored FADs (Fish Aggregating Devices).</p> <p><u>Coastal environment:</u> Ifremer is involved in answering fundamental questions about the entry of contamination (chlordecone, other agricultural pesticides, urban effluent, industrial discharges, tourist activity) into the marine environment and living organisms, as well as its transfer into the various biotic and abiotic compartments.</p>									
<p>Capacities</p>	<p>Protecting and restoring marine ecosystems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marine biodiversity and ecosystems • Ocean & climate • Extreme events • Pollution & contamination <p>Sustainable management of marine resources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fisheries & aquaculture • Health quality • Mineral resources • Energy & materials • Marine biotechnologies <p>Sharing marine data and information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensors & measurement systems • Digital ocean & modelling <p>In the French West Indies, Ifremer focuses specifically on supporting the sustainable development of the fishing and aquaculture industries, while ensuring the food quality of their products. This work is carried out in conjunction with efforts to address environmental protection, particularly concerning the quality of the marine environment.</p>									
<p>Contact details</p>	<p>Direction</p>	<p>79 route de Pointe Fort, 97231 LE ROBERT</p>								
	<p>Telephone</p>	<p>05 96 66 19 40</p>								
	<p>Mail</p>	<p>Emmanuel.Thouard@ifremer.fr</p>								
<p>Information resources</p>	<p>Web</p>	<p>https://antilles.ifremer.fr/ https://www.ifremer.fr/fr</p>								
	<p>Social networks</p>	<table border="1"> <tr> <td data-bbox="662 1368 949 1420"> <p>Facebook</p> </td> <td data-bbox="949 1368 1453 1420"> <p>https://www.facebook.com/ifremer.fr</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="662 1420 949 1471"> <p>Instagram</p> </td> <td data-bbox="949 1420 1453 1471"> <p>https://www.instagram.com/ifremer_officiel/</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="662 1471 949 1523"> <p>Twitter</p> </td> <td data-bbox="949 1471 1453 1523"> <p>https://twitter.com/ifremer_fr</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="662 1523 949 1556"> <p>LinkedIn</p> </td> <td data-bbox="949 1523 1453 1556"> <p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifremer/</p> </td> </tr> </table>	<p>Facebook</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/ifremer.fr</p>	<p>Instagram</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/ifremer_officiel/</p>	<p>Twitter</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/ifremer_fr</p>	<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifremer/</p>
<p>Facebook</p>	<p>https://www.facebook.com/ifremer.fr</p>									
<p>Instagram</p>	<p>https://www.instagram.com/ifremer_officiel/</p>									
<p>Twitter</p>	<p>https://twitter.com/ifremer_fr</p>									
<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>https://www.linkedin.com/company/ifremer/</p>									

Business name	Parc Naturel Marin de la Martinique (PNM)	Logo	
Company name	Parc Naturel Marin de la Martinique (PNM)		
Type of organisation			
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)		
Type of service	The Parc Naturel Marin de la Martinique (PNM) was created on May 5, 2017, following three years of consultation. It is the eighth marine park in France, the second in the Overseas Territories, and the second largest by surface area, after the Mayotte Marine Park in the Indian Ocean.		
Competences	<p>The general objectives of the Parc Naturel Marin de la Martinique (PNM) are divided into seven specific management targets addressing the island's unique challenges, such as natural and cultural heritage, water quality, professional fishing, and leisure activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Knowledge: Enhance understanding of Martinique's natural heritage, including river mouths, mangroves, seagrass meadows and reefs, their biodiversity and ecological functions, as well as its maritime cultural heritage. 2. Awareness: Promote awareness, starting at a young age, about the importance and preservation of Martinique's insular maritime space, and share these initiatives throughout the Caribbean. 3. Preservation: Propose measures for the protection, restoration and improvement of marine species and environments, such as corals and bay bottoms, while coordinating their management. 4. Sustainable exploitation: Support small-scale coastal fisheries and aquaculture that ensure a sustainable use of marine resources. 5. Conciliation: Recognize the strong land-sea connection, support innovative and participatory management in development projects aimed at reconciling different uses, improve water quality, and integrate the services provided by marine ecosystems. 6. Responsible activities: Engage the tourism, sport, nautical leisure activities and ports and anchorages in responsible practices by training stakeholders and installing appropriate equipment. 7. Listening: Contribute to marine use planning, prevent conflicts, and improve the monitoring of the marine environment. 		
Capacities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preserve the natural environment and its biodiversity. • Sustainably support maritime activities. • Improve water quality. • Marine environmental awareness. 		
Contact details	Direction	Rue des Pionniers. 97 200 Fort de France	
	Telephone	0596 30 22 81	
	Mail	parcmarin.martinique@ofb.gouv.fr	

Information resources	Web	https://parc-marin-martinique.fr/	
	Social networks	Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/parc.naturel.marin.martinique
		Instagram	
		Twitter	
		LinkedIn	

Business name	Parc Naturel Régional de la Martinique		Logo	
Company name	Parc Naturel Régional de la Martinique			
Type of organisation				
Territorial scope	Regional (Martinique)			
Type of service	The Joint Union of the Martinique Regional Natural Park (SMPNRM) operates under an innovative and exemplary governance model. It aims to implement a territorial development project that is shared and mutually agreed upon by local authorities, public inter-community cooperation establishments with independent taxation, and the State. This project focuses on the protection and enhancement of Martinique's heritage and landscapes.			
Competences	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Protect landscapes and their natural and cultural heritage, and contribute to their effective management; 2. Contribute to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. land use planning; b. economic, social, cultural development, and improving quality of life; c. ensuring public engagement through reception, education and information; 3. Implement experimental or exemplary actions in these areas and contribute to research programmes. 			
Capacities	<p>It has 4 strategic directions:</p> <p>Axis 1: Preserving and promoting nature together in Martinique</p> <p>Axis 2: Encourage Martinicans to be actors in their territory</p> <p>Axis 3: Bringing Martinican culture to life in the Park's projects</p> <p>Axis 4: Strengthen the performance of the Park tool</p>			
Contact details	Direction	Maison du Parc – Morne TARTENSON – BP 437		
	Telephone	05 96 64 42 59		
	Mail	contact@pnr-martinique.com		
Information resources	Web	https://pnr-martinique.com/		
	Social networks	Facebook		
		Instagram		
		Twitter	https://x.com/PNRMartinique	
	LinkedIn			

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalization for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

Co-funded by
the European Union

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101124900. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.